

SpaceTeamSat1
Preliminary Design Document
Electric Power System

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Revision History

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0.2	03.04.2023	David Freismuth, Patrick Kappl	<ul style="list-style-type: none">• Updated Figure 3.2 in response to addition of requirement 1-EPS-20.• Scrapped solar cell backup mode. Updated Figure Figure 3.3 accordingly.• Added MPPT current sensors to housekeeping data, Updated Figure 3.3 accordingly.• Deployment switch debouncing circuit has been removed.• Added chapter “Testing” and handled requirement 1-EPS-21 and 1-EPS-22 there.• New title page• Improved citations

Review History

The Preliminary Design Review (PDR) consists of two parts: Firstly, this document itself and a review meeting, in which the topics are discussed in person.

In the following table the invited reviewers are listed. Additionally, it is stated if feedback to the document was received (DOC) as well as if the person participated in the PDR meeting (PDR).

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Glossary

- ADC** Analog to digital converter; A devices that turn analog signals into digital ones. 30, 31
- ARC** Anti reflective coating; A coating that shall reduce the reflectivity of solar cells. 14
- AZUR SPACE** Manufacturer of solar cells. 15
- BCC** Battery charge controller; The circuit that is responsible for charging the CubeSat battery. Also includes battery safety features. See also BMS (Battery Management System). 7, 8, 16, 20, 24–27, 29, 35
- BMS** Battery Management System; A system that controls the charging process of a battery and provides safety features. See also Battery charge controller (BCC). 7, 24
- CC/CV** Constant Current/Constant Voltage; A battery charging scheme that first imprints a constant current, then a constant voltage onto the battery. 25
- COBC** Communication and on-board Computer; Processor that is responsible for CubeSat management task and the RF communication. 5, 30
- COTS** Component of the shelf; Commercially available parts. 5, 7, 20
- CSBI** CubeSat Bus Interface; The Bus which is used on SpaceTeamSat 1 (STS1) for communication between the subsystems. 8, 10–12, 24–27, 29, 30
- CubeSat** A satellite, that adheres to the CubeSat design specification. 1–5, 7, 8, 10, 13, 16, 20–22, 24, 26–28, 30
- DET** Direct energy transfer; Refers to a method of solar cell energy harvesting, where the voltage of the solar cells is directly facilitated. 7
- DOD** Depth of discharge; A parameter of a battery, that describes how much of its nominal capacity can be discharged without damaging the battery. 24
- DS** Deployment Switch; Mechanical switches on the outside of the CubeSat that shall prevent the premature activation of the CubeSat, while it is inserted in the launch device. 5, 8, 27, 29
- DT** Deployment Timer; Timed switch that shall prevent the premature activation of the CubeSat, while it is inserted in the launch device. 5
- EDU** The sub module that holds the payload on STS1. 30
- EPS** Electric Power System; The subsystem of a CubeSat, that provides and conditions electric energy. 2–5, 7, 8, 10, 12, 13, 16, 20, 24, 25, 27, 29, 31–33
- ESA** European Space Agency; An intergovernmental organisation of 22 member states dedicated to the exploration of space. 7, 22
- FYS** Fly-Your-Satellite; An European Space Agency (ESA) programm, that sponsors CubeSat missions with academic goals. 4

- I²C** Inter-Integrated Circuit; A hardware interface specification that features serial, synchronous communication over 2 wires. 24
- IncCond** Incremental conductance; A maximum power point tracking algorithm. 15
- LEO** Low earth orbit; An earth centered orbit whose altitude is less than 1000 km. 14, 20, 22
- MPPT** Maximum power point tracking; An algorithm or controller that drives a voltage source at its maximum power point. 7, 8, 14–16, 30, 35
- NASA** National Aeronautics and Space Administration; An independent agency of the U.S. federal government responsible for the civilian space program, as well as aeronautics and space research. 23
- NTC** Negative thermal Coefficient; Often relates to a devices that is used as temperature sensor. 31
- P&O** Perturb & Observe; A maximum power point tracking algorithm. 14–16
- PCB** Printed Circuit Board; Board that mounts electronics and the electric connections between them. 7, 16, 24, 25, 31–33
- PDR** Preliminary Design Review; A technical review, where the preliminary requirements are evaluated and locked in. Furthermore, design choices, that have been made until this point shall be challenged. 2
- POL** Point of load; Term that refers to voltage regulators that sit near to the load they are supplying. 7
- PPT** Peak power tracking; Refers to a method of solar cell energy harvesting, where the voltage of the solar cells are driven at their peak power point. 7, 14, 16
- RBF** Remove Before Flight pin; A pin that is inserted into the CubeSat. While it is inserted, most CubeSat functions are disabled.. 5, 26–29
- SCC** Solar cell controller; The circuit that is responsible driving the solar cells at their maximum power point. 16, 18, 27
- SOC** State of charge; The level of charge contained by an electric battery with respect to its nominal maximum capacity. 22, 24, 25
- SPI** Serial Peripheral Interface; A hardware interface specification that features serial, synchronous communication over 4 wires. 24, 30, 31
- STS1** SpaceTeamSat 1; The name of the first CubeSat mission of the TU Wien SpaceTeam (TUST) and the corresponding satellite. 1, 2, 4, 7, 15–18, 24
- TID** Total ionizing dose; A measure for the accumulated exposition to radiation. 37
- TUST** TU Wien SpaceTeam, The team behind STS1. 1
- UCI** Umbilical Cord Interface; External connector on the CubeSat, that is specified by the CubeSat specification. 10, 12, 29

1. Introduction

This document serves as the preliminary design document of the Electric Power System (EPS) submodule of the STS1 CubeSat. It states how the requirements, specified in the Preliminary Requirements document [1] shall be met. Table 1.1 gives an overview of where requirements are handled in this document. As this document is fabricated at an early project phase, requirements and design may be subject to change, until they are reviewed and locked in at a future Preliminary Design Review (PDR).

The document is structured as follows: chapter 2 lays out the high-level architectures and sketches the purpose of the components of the EPS. Building on that, chapter 3 goes into detail structure of the EPS parts. The suggested behaviour of the EPS is explained in chapter 4. Table 1.1 links the requirement IDs, that have been stated in [1], to their position in this document.

Requirement ID	Page	Fulfilled
1-EPS-1	Section 3.1.3	Yes
1-EPS-2	Section 3.1.3	Yes
1-EPS-3	Section 3.1.3	Yes
1-EPS-4	Section 3.1.3	Yes
1-EPS-5	Section 2.2	Yes
1-EPS-6	Section 3.5.1	Yes
1-EPS-7	Section 3.6.1	Yes
1-EPS-8	Section 3.6.1	Yes
1-EPS-9	Section 3.2.3	Yes
1-EPS-10	Section 3.2.3	Yes
1-EPS-11	Section 3.2.3	Yes
1-EPS-12	Section 3.2.3	Yes
1-EPS-13	Section 3.2.3	Yes
1-EPS-14	Section 3.2.3	Yes
1-EPS-15	Section 3.2.3	Yes
1-EPS-16	Section 3.1.3	Yes
1-EPS-17	Section 3.1.3	Yes
1-EPS-18	Section 3.1.3	Yes
1-EPS-19	Section 3.1.3	Yes
1-EPS-20	Section 3.1.3	Yes
1-EPS-21	Section 5.2	Could be fulfilled in the future
1-EPS-22	Section 5.3	Could be fulfilled in the future
FYS-EPS-1	Section 3.4	Yes
FYS-EPS-2	Section 3.4	No
FYS-EPS-3	Section 3.3.1	Yes
FYS-EPS-4	Section 3.2.3	Yes
FYS-EPS-5	Section 3.2.3	Could be fulfilled in the future
FYS-EPS-6	Section 3.2.3	Yes
FYS-EPS-7	Section 3.2.3	Yes
FYS-EPS-8	Section 3.2.3	Yes
FYS-EPS-9	Section 3.2.3	Yes
FYS-EPS-10	Section 3.3.1	Yes
FYS-EPS-11	Section 3.3.1	Yes
2-EPS-1	Section 3.2.3	Yes
2-EPS-2	Section 3.2.3	Will be evaluated in the future
2-EPS-3	Section 3.6.1	Yes
4-EPS-1	Section 3.1.3	Yes
3-EPS-1	Section 3.5.1	Yes
3-EPS-2	Section 3.5.1	Yes
3-EPS-3	Section 3.5.1	Yes
3-EPS-4	Section 3.5.1	Yes
9-EPS-1	Section 3.1.3	Yes

Table 1.1.: Links the requirement IDs to where they are described in this document.

1.1. The Electronic Power System

The EPS is the CubeSat’s subsystem that provides the electrical energy that is necessary to power all other CubeSat subsystems. The EPS includes solar cells, batteries, voltage transformation circuits

and security circuits. The EPS is not responsible for the supervision of the available energy. This means, that the EPS does not ration energy, in case the batteries run low.

1.2. Related Documents

This document relates to the following other publications. They may be referenced by the given short sign or the respective number throughout the document.

Short Sign	Document Name	Purpose
STS1PDR[2]	CubeSat: SpaceTeamSat1 Preliminary Design I: System Architecture	Describes the system architecture
STS1EPS_PR[1]	CubeSat: SpaceTeamSat1 Preliminary Requirements: Electronic Power System v1.2	States the requirements to the STS1 electronic power system
STS1DATA[3]	CubeSat: SpaceTeamSat1 Dataflow Game	Describes the data flow on STS1
STS1EPS_EVAL[4]	CubeSat: EPS Prototype Evaluation	Describes the evaluation process of the EPS prototypes
FYSD[5]	Fly Your Satellite! Design Specification Version 3.0	Describes requirements of CubeSats that participate in the FYS programm.
CDS[6]	CubeSat Design Specification Rev.12	Specifies the CubeSats standard.
JX	JAXA JEM Payload Accommodation Handbook	Specifies requirements to payloads.
NS	NASA Crewed Space Vehicle Battery Safety Requirements	States requirements to on-board batteries.
NR	NanoRacks CubeSat Deployer Interface Control Document	Specifies a CubeSat deployment system.

2. Overview

This chapter shall give an overview of the proposed architecture, in order to give a preliminary understanding of the EPS components, and thus, the sectioning of this document.

The EPS is responsible for the continuous generation and provision of electrical power at a single, unregulated voltage level. Energy is harvested solely through solar cells. Excess energy is stored in batteries, in order to continue to power the satellite in orbit sections without light incidence. The EPS also contains system-level safety features, like the Remove Before Flight pin (RBF), the Deployment Switch (DS) and a Deployment Timer (DT). All of these features shall prevent a premature activation, while the CubeSat is still mounted onto the launch vehicle. Housekeeping data like battery voltage, battery temperature, etc. is collected by the EPS, and made available to the Communication and on-board Computer (COBC) subsystem through a housekeeping data interface.

As virtually any CubeSat hardware relies on electrical power, many commercial providers have gone through the effort of developing a ready-to-use Component of the shelf (COTS) EPS. In Table 2.1 a comparison of a selection of providers and the estimated STS1 requirements are listed. It can be seen that the commercial products are over-engineered in the majority of aspects (with regards to the STS1 mission). Especially when compared to the selection of available voltage rails and the battery capacity.

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	NanoAvionics [7]	EnduroSat [8]	ISISpace [9]	Required for STS1
Voltage Rails	BAT, 3.3 V, 5 V, configurable 3 V–18 V	BAT, 3.3 V, 5 V	BAT, 3.3 V, 5 V configurable	single voltage > 5 V
Capacity	11 W h	10 W h	22.5 W h	~ 15 W h
Power	20 W per rail	-	20 W per rail	~ 20 W
Mass	300 g	208 g	184 g	~ 300 g
Misc	RTC Software configurable	Serial Interfaces 6 General Purpose Outputs RBF and DS optional	Serial Interfaces FRAM based MCU Supervisor	No software DS Deployment Timer
Heaters	yes	yes	yes	no
Price	On Request	2500 £	3300 £	-

Table 2.1.: Comparison of the EPS' of a selection of providers and the estimated requirements of STS1.

It has been decided to not implement a COTS EPS and rather develop the EPS in-house for the following reasons:

1. Building and sharing of know-how
2. Reduction of mission cost
3. Experiences from previous missions suggest, that the EPS should be as simple as possible, should contain as few features as possible and should not contain any microcontrollers. This circumstance is not applicable to most available COTS EPS.

2.1. Architecture

CubeSat architectures are categorized mainly by two criteria: The fashion in which the voltages are distributed to the subsystems, and the method by which energy is harvested from the solar cells [10]. The first criteria offers two groups: centralized and distributed architectures. Centralized architectures strive to encapsulate the whole energy transformation circuits onto a single module. Such architectures offer a variety of regulated voltages from which submodules can choose from. This allows for a space efficient design, as fewer regulators are needed. This advantage has to be bought with reduced electrical efficiency. This stems from the circumstance that the voltage regulators have to be designed for a specific peak load. However, these regulators rarely operate at peak load. This means that they cannot be optimized, hence operate at reduced efficiency. Distributed architectures address this issue, by only supplying a common bus voltage and implementing point of load (POL) regulators. These regulators sit near to the load (i.e. on the same Printed Circuit Board (PCB)). This means that each load has its own voltage regulator, which is optimizable for its specific scenario. This requires more physical space, but allows higher electrical efficiency. Furthermore, such an architecture adds redundancy to the power distribution.

Via the second criteria, CubeSat architectures are distinguishable into Direct energy transfer (DET) and Peak power tracking (PPT) topologies. In DET topologies, solar cells are hooked up directly to batteries and loads. This design is especially simple and therefore offers great potential for reliability. Since the solar cell voltage is clamped by the batteries, the efficiency however suffers. This topology also needs a shunt regulator, which burns off excess energy, produced by the solar cells, if the batteries are full. PPT architectures implement a Maximum power point tracking (MPPT) algorithm. This often comes in form of a DC/DC converter. Such architectures maximize solar cell efficiency, but require more physical space and are less reliable, due to higher part count.

Distributed architectures have been used primarily in larger satellites, because of their higher space requirements. Advances in semiconductor technology and regulator design allowed the inception of voltage regulators with footprints as small as 3 mm x 3 mm [11]. This circumstance makes distributed architectures feasible even for small CubeSats. A similar development can be observed with regards to the DET / PPT design decision. Smaller regulators allow the implementation of PPT architectures. In addition to that, the higher radiation resistance of GaN semiconductors mitigates the reliability concern.

2.1.1. Design

For the STS1 mission, it has been decided to implement a distributed architecture with PPT-driven solar cells. The distributed approach shall ensure flexibility, high efficiency and high reliability due to the avoidance of single points of failure. As STS1 does not carry an especially bulky payload, therefore space is not as restricted, as it would be in other 1U CubeSats. This further reinforces the distributed approach. It has been decided for a PPT approach, as energy is scarce on 1U CubeSats.

Therefore, power generation has to be as efficient as possible. The disadvantage in reliability shall be mitigated, by having multiple MPPTs connected in parallel. Most EPS designs directly connect the MPPTs to the battery. It has been decided to not follow that topology and add a separate BCC. The reason is that this controller adds battery safety features, that would otherwise have been added by discrete circuitry. Furthermore, most MPPT are not very flexible with regards to battery chemistry and battery pack configuration.

By adhering to these decisions and to system requirements 1 and 2 [2], the architecture depicted in Figure 2.1 can be deducted. The components and their functions are elaborated upon in the following list:

1. **External Charger:** Connects to the Umbilical Cord Interface (UCI) of the satellite and allows charging of the CubeSat batteries on the ground. It is possible to charge the batteries, even when the safety features of the CubeSat (i.e. DS, DT and RBF) are in effect. However, it is not possible to power other satellite subsystems via the external charger, while the safety features are in effect.
2. **Bus Gate:** Consists of multiple switches, that connects the EPS-internal power bus to the system bus interface. The Bus Gate is controlled by Deployment Timer, an over-current protection circuit and a deployment switch.
3. **Battery Pack:** Contains battery cells that store excess energy generated by the solar cells. Allows operation of the satellite, when no energy is harvested by the solar cells.
4. **Temperature Sensor:** Measures the temperature of the battery pack, and distributes this information to the housekeeping block and to the battery controller.
5. **Solar Cell:** Allows generation of electrical energy in orbit.
6. **Deployment Switch:** Switches that are actuated, when the satellite is inserted into the launch device. When actuated, the power flow of solar cells and battery is interrupted.
7. **Remove Before Flight Pin:** While this pin is inserted into the satellite, the power flow of battery and solar cells is interrupted.
8. **Voltage and Current Sensor:** Measures voltage and current readings. This information is collected by the housekeeping block. During the development it will be evaluated in detail which parameters are required.
9. **Battery Controller:** Controls charge and discharge rate of the battery pack. Monitors battery voltage level and temperature. Provides the “Battery OK” signal to the CubeSat Bus Interface.
10. **MPPT Controller:** Keeps the connected solar cell at its maximum point of power by utilizing a Maximum Point of Power Tracking mechanism (MPPT), in order to optimize energy generation. Provides a regulated voltage at its output.
11. **Deployment Timer:** Timer that is started once all DSs are no longer actuated and the RBF has been removed. After expiration of the timer, an electrical signal is emitted.
12. **Housekeeping:** Collects data of the sensors on the EPS and provides this data via an interface.
13. **Umbilical Cord Interface (UCI):** Interface to the umbilical cord connector. This connector allows ground-based debugging and battery charging after assembly of the CubeSat.
14. **CubeSat Bus Interface:** Interface to the CubeSat system bus.
15. **Antenna Deployment Switch:** A Switch that can be actuated from the CubeSat Bus Interface (CSBI). If triggered, a high current path to the antenna deployment mechanism is opened.
16. **Antenna Deployment:** The antenna deployment mechanism.

Figure 2.1.: The block diagram of the EPS.

2.2. Interfaces

The EPS has an interface to the CubeSat system bus, where it provides a single power bus, some signals, and the housekeeping data. According to the distributed system approach, the EPS does not guarantee a fixed voltage level on the power bus. That is why other subsystems have to implement additional voltage regulators to power their individual components. The EPS does not expose a control interface to the CSBI. Other subsystems are therefore not able to change the behavior of the EPS. This fulfills requirement 1-EPS-5. table 2.2 and table 2.3 shows the pin assignment of the CSBI.

Furthermore, the EPS connects to the Umbilical Cord Interface (UCI). Here, the external charging port is connected. table 2.4 shows the EPS relevant pins of the UCI.

Pin Header X-		
	Pin Function	Used in Subsystem
1	2	GND
3	4	GND
5	6	VBUS
7	8	VBUS
9	10	GND
11	12	SPARE_1
13	14	EDU_HEARTBEAT
15	16	UART_COBC_EDU_TX
17	18	UART_COBC_EDU_RX
19	20	GND
21	22	EDU_EN
23	24	EDU_UPDATE
25	26	GND
27	28	EDU_SPI_CLK
29	30	EDU_SPI_MOSI
31	32	EDU_SPI_MISO
33	34	EDU_SPI_CS1
35	36	EDU_SPI_CS2
37	38	EDU_SPI_CS3
39	40	GND
41	42	SPARE_2
43	44	SPARE_3
45	46	SPARE_4
47	48	GND
49	50	GND

Table 2.2.: The definition of the CSBI header in X- direction.

Pin Header X+		
	Pin Function	Used in Subsystem
1	2	GND
3	4	GND
5	6	EPS_BAT_FAULT
7	8	SPARE_6
9	10	SPARE_7
11	12	SPARE_8
13	14	UCI_COBC_UART_TX EPS, COBC
15	16	UCI_COBC_UART_RX EPS, COBC
17	18	UCI_COBC_3V3 EPS, COBC
19	20	GND
21	22	EPS_BAT_GOOD
23	24	EPS_ANT_DEPLOY EPS, COBC
25	26	EPS_CHARGING EPS, COBC
27	28	GND
29	30	COBC_SPI_CLK EPS, COBC
31	32	COBC_SPI_MOSI EPS, COBC
33	34	COBC_SPI_MISO EPS, COBC
35	36	COBC_SPI_CS1 EPS, COBC
37	38	COBC_SPI_CS2 EPS, COBC
39	40	COBC_SPI_CS3 EPS, COBC
41	42	GND
43	44	VBUS
45	46	VBUS
47	48	GND
49	50	GND

Table 2.3.: The definition of the CSBI header in X+ direction.

UCI Pin header		
	Pin Function	Used in Subsystem
1	EPS_BAT_P	EPS
2	EPS_BAT_N	EPS
3	N/C	
4	N/C	
5	N/C	
6	N/C	
7	N/C	
8	N/C	
9	N/C	

Table 2.4.: The pin assignments of the UCI connector. Only the EPS relevant pins are shown.

3. Components

Chapter 2 laid out the high level architecture of the CubeSat. This chapter focuses on the technological details and states the detailed description of the EPS components. The sections in this chapter first give an overview over the respective subject. Design decisions, based on that information, is then discussed in the “Design” subsections.

3.1. Solar Cells and Solar Cell Controller

The solar cells are responsible for energy generation on the CubeSat. They are the sole energy source of the system and are therefore an integral part of the mission. Several solar cell types are available, which mainly differ in their achievable efficiency η and idle voltage V_0 . Amorphous silicon solar cells are one of the cheapest variants available and achieve efficiencies of 10%, while multi-junction cells are the pinnacle of solar cell technology. Through their multi-layered structure, they are able to harvest a broader light spectrum and can achieve efficiencies of up to 46% [12]. However, most of those multi-junction cells with high counts of layers are in an experimental development state and are therefore relatively expensive and potentially unreliable.

In [13], a study of the achievable energy generation on a 1U CubeSats is made. A configuration where each CubeSat side is covered in simple silicon solar cells with an area of 54.6 cm² is assumed. The simulation suggests an ideally achievable mean power of 1.36 W. Triple junction solar cells have been subjected to the same simulation and achieved a mean ideal power of 3.06 W. When considering temperature dependency and total reflection properties of the cover glass, the mean power value of the triple junction cell configuration drops to 2.15 W. Under the same conditions, a deployable solar panel configuration achieves a mean power value of 4.55 W

3.1.1. Efficiency

The efficiency factor of a solar cell is not constant. It primarily depends on temperature, light incidence angle, and aging due to radiation. These effects shall be discussed here briefly.

Temperature

Solar cell efficiency drops with increasing temperature. This is due to increasing internal resistance and reverse saturation current [14]. The effect is primarily notable in a decreased open-circuit voltage. In [15] it is stated, that the efficiency of silicon cells drops by 8% per Kelvin. It is therefore important to ensure good thermal conductivity between solar cells and CubeSat structure in order to keep them at a lower temperature. This can be achieved by using special resins.

Light Incidence Angle

Due to projection, the energy density that is captured by the solar cells decreases, as the angle of incidence increases. Additionally to that, the reflectivity of the cover glass may be dependent on the incidence angle. An extreme case of that effect is total reflection. It causes the reflection of the whole energy of certain wavelengths at certain incidence angles. To mitigate these losses, solar cells often are treated with optic coatings that reduce reflectivity. In [16] an Anti reflective coating (ARC) is investigated. The paper comes to the conclusion that due to the ARC, the solar cell efficiency stays almost constant for incidence angles of 0° to 45° . At an angle of 60° , the efficiency drops by 1.7%. Another study [17] compares the efficiencies of solar cells with and without ARC. It comes to the conclusion that the solar cell without ARC reaches an efficiency of 14.02%, while the one with ARC performed at 20.67%. ARCs therefore should be a part of any solar cell.

Aging

Aging in solar cells is primarily induced by radiation. High energy particles may dislocate atoms in the solar cell crystal lattice. These defects cause degradation in the transport properties of the lattice. Subsequently, this leads to a decrease in open-circuit voltage, short circuit current, and increase of internal resistance. Therefore the efficiency is decreasing. In [18] this effect is investigated. The paper states, that the efficiency of a polycrystalline solar cell drops from 13.5% to 6.5%, after being subjected to a dose of 1000 kGy. Depending on the orbit inclination, the dose per year in Low earth orbit (LEO) may range from 100 rad ($\cong 10$ kGy) to 10000 rad ($\cong 1000$ kGy) [19]. This means, that the solar cell efficiency may be halved within one year of satellite operation. The only possibility to protect the solar cells is via the thickness of the protective glass. In [20], a model based analysis is made, that comes to the conclusion, that solar cells only lose about 1% of efficiency after being 1 year in a LEO orbit.

3.1.2. Power Point Tracking

PPT architecture implement circuits that maximize the power that can be extracted from solar cells. There are multiple algorithms that aim to fulfill that task. A selection of the most popular ones shall be presented here. [21] [22].

Perturb and Observe

Perturb & Observe (P&O) is a popular tracking algorithm, due to its good trade-off between simplicity and efficiency. The algorithm increases or decreases the duty cycle periodically. If the extracted power decreased after such a step, the next step direction is inverted (Figure 3.1). Consequently, with static external conditions, the algorithm oscillates around the maximum power point. This may lead to voltage ripples in the output signal. Furthermore, depending on the step size and the step frequency, the algorithm may underperform, if external conditions change too quickly. In [22] P&O is investigated. At a rotational rate of $1 \frac{^\circ}{s}$, P&O achieves an efficiency of 98.6%. Omission of an MPPT controller leads to an efficiency of 86.5%. At $20 \frac{^\circ}{s}$ the efficiency of the P&O algorithm drops to 52.6%.

Figure 3.1.: A visual description of the P&O MPPT algorithm. [23]

Incremental Conductance

Incremental conductance (IncCond) tries to mitigate the shortfalls of P&O, by tracking the conductance of the solar cell. At the maximum power point, the incremental conductance $\frac{\Delta I}{\Delta V}$ is equal to the instantaneous conductance $-\frac{I}{V}$. The algorithm regulates the solar cell voltage to that point in a step-less manner. This allows faster reactions to movements of the maximum power points. Hence, start-up time and oscillation at the maximum power point decreases. However, the algorithm requires complex calculations, which implies that IncCond MPPT controllers are more expensive.

Fractional Voltage

Fractional Voltage is an indirect MPPT method. This means, that the maximum power point is not measured directly, but is predicted by a model assumption. The fractional voltage algorithm uses the circumstance, that the relationship between solar cell open-circuit voltage V_{oc} and maximum power voltage V_{mpp} is quite constant. Therefore it is feasible to derive the maximum power point from the open-circuit voltage and drive the solar cells at that fixed voltage. This technique has superior properties when subjected to quickly varying irradiation conditions [22]. The non-perfect relationship between V_{oc} and V_{mpp} however degrades the achievable efficiency. Furthermore, the solar cells have to be disconnected periodically, for the measurement of V_{oc} .

3.1.3. Design

This section describes the detailed design of the solar panels, the solar cell controller and how it shall fulfill the STS1 requirements.

Solar Cells

STS1 will mount 8 solar cells of the type AZUR SPACE 3G30A. The datasheet can be found in the appendix Appendix A.1.

Solar Interface	1 °/s	1 °/s with BCC eff.	20 °/s	20 °/s with BCC eff.
P&O	98.6%	83.8%	52.6%	44,7%
DET	86.5%	73,5%	86.5%	73,5%

Table 3.1.: Comparison of MPPT algorithm efficiencies at different CubeSat spin rates, based on [22]. BCC efficiency has been assumed to be 85%.

Panels

The solar cells are mounted onto the A side of the CubeSat panels. These panels are made of FR4 (i.e. ordinary PCB material). The configuration of the panels can be seen in fig. 3.2. The solar cells are glued onto the solar panel with a thermally conductive, outgassing free resin (e.g. the NASA approved Epotek 4110-LV appendix A.2). Additionally to that, the electric contacts are soldered to the copper pads of the panel. The solar cells are oriented in such a way, that lorentz forces cancel out each other. This solar panel configuration fulfills the requirements 1-EPS-16, 1-EPS-17, 1-EPS-18 and 1-EPS-20. No solar cells are mounted on the Z- face. This fulfills requirement 4-EPS-1. As the panels are fixed to the CubeSat structure, and are not extendable, requirement 1-EPS-19 is fulfilled. Also mounted onto the A side of each of the panels are UV- and temperature sensors. This leads to the partial fulfillment of 3-EPS-1.

Side B of the panel is used to house the solar cell controllers. By placing the solar cell controllers on the solar panels, space is freed on the EPS PCB stack, that can be used for additional batteries. The 5 V output of the solar cell controllers is connected to the main EPS PCB via 8 Harwin L-Tek connectors (see appendix A.3.1 and appendix A.3.2 for reference.). This fulfills requirement 1-EPS-1.

Solar Cell Controllers

In Section 2.1.1, it has been stated, that a PPT architecture shall be implemented. This shall ensure a higher efficiency and a higher flexibility with regards to battery technology and battery charge circuits. The advantage of MPPT controllers diminishes, with increasing CubeSat spin rate. This relationship can be seen in Table 3.1. For this reason, STS1 will incorporate hysteresis rods as detumbling mechanism. In [24], it is stated, that the rotation rate of a 3U CubeSat in orbit can be brought down to approximately 1 °/s within a week. A self-made simulation suggests a 30-day detumbling period. This serves as motivation to implement an MPPT controller.

As Solar cell controller (SCC), the SPV1040 IC (Appendix A.4) is used. The decision for this IC is based on a prototype evaluation that has been done in an evaluation[4]. The SPV1040 implements the P&O algorithm. In theory, other algorithms promise a better efficiency, however [21] states, that in reality, the differences are marginal. Figure 3.3 depicts the configuration of SCCs.

The SPV1040 includes an input polarity protection. Inverse connection of the solar cells therefore will not destroy solar cells or parts of the EPS. This fulfills requirement 1-EPS-2 and 1-EPS-3. The regulator operates from an input voltage range of 0.3 V–5.5 V. Requirement 1-EPS-4 is therefore fulfilled.

Simulations

Two Simulations have been made, to evaluate the performance of the solar cells [25]. The first simulation evaluated the effect of temperature and sun angle on the power generation. The other one

Panel Y+, Y-

(a) The solar panels in Y+ and Y- direction.

Panel X-

(b) The solar panel in X- direction.

Panel X+

(c) The solar panel in X+ direction.

Panel Z+

(d) The solar panel in Z+ direction.

Figure 3.2.: The configuration of the solar panels on STS1. The drawings show the A side of the panels.

Figure 3.3.: The configuration of the SCCs on STS1.

Figure 3.4.: Results of a simulation that calculated the generated electric power under varying solar incidence angle and temperatures. In Figure 3.4a and Figure 3.4b a temperature of 28°C and 60°C respectively has been assumed.

Figure 3.5.: Power generation under 1000 different rotation rates.

explored the impact of rotation direction on the power generation. The goal of these simulations is to verify that requirement 9-EPS-1 can be fulfilled. The following two paragraphs explain in detail the results of these simulations.

Solar angle and temperature The power generation of the solar panels under varying sun incidence angles has been simulated. Additionally, the temperature gradients of the optimum power point voltage and current have been considered. The parameters have been taken from Appendix A.1. The results are shown in Figure 3.4. Solar cell temperature for 1u CubeSat in LEO does not exceed 60°C [26, 27], hence this case has been chosen as worst case. If all CubeSat poses are assumed as equally possible, a mean power generation of 2.12 W can be expected. This circumstance fulfills requirement 9-EPS-1.

Rotation direction Random rotation rates from the interval $[-2\pi, 2\pi]$ rad/s in the CubeSat's three axes are assumed. The CubeSat is rotated and the power generation over the duration of an orbit (approximately 90 min) is calculated. No eclipse is simulated, hence the CubeSat is illuminated the whole time. Eventually, the mean of the power values is calculated. This is done several times, in order to be able to detect a dependency of power generation to the rotation direction. The results are shown in ???. The distribution of the power values is not spread out. Hence, the rotation direction does not seem to influence the power generation. This simulation suggests a power generation of 2.53 W . If an eclipse ratio of 60 % is assumed, a mean, orbit specific power generation of 1.52 W is achieved. This complies with requirement 9-EPS-1.

3.2. Battery and Battery Charge Controller

Battery and BCC are responsible for the energy storage on the CubeSat. They allow operation of the CubeSat during the eclipse portion of the orbit. Additionally to that, the implementation of a battery allows higher short term power draw than would be possible via solar cells alone. The BCC's tasks are to monitor the charge state of the battery, the charging of the battery according to that charge state, and to ensure compliance to the battery's safe charge/discharge parameters. The following sub sections describe the technological considerations regarding battery and BCC.

3.2.1. Battery

Practically, electrochemic batteries are the only feasible energy storage devices for CubeSats, as other technologies either lack the energy densities or are far too expensive. Some CubeSats rely on Li-Ion capacitors alone, or in combination with a battery. This configuration shall not be considered, as such a solution would most likely not meet the space requirements of the EPS.

Due to the cost-sensitive nature of most CubeSat projects, the batteries of choice will be selected from the COTS sector. In Table 3.2 the most common battery chemistries used in CubeSat missions are shown. Figure 3.6 shows the relative distribution of the chemistries. It can be seen that Li-ion is the prevalent technology. This is mainly due to the technology's superior energy density and longevity.

As most COTS batteries have not been designed for usage in space, they have to undergo rigorous testing, before being sent to the launch provider. The following sections shall identify the factors that may lead to accelerated battery degradation and malfunction.

Full Name	Chemical Abbreviation	Short Name	Characteristics
Lithium manganese oxide	LiMn2O4	LMO	Low cost, high discharge rate capability, good safety, low specific energy.
Lithium manganese nickel	LiNiMnCoO2	NMC	Low cost, high specific energy, good discharge rate capability, low resistance, good safety.
Lithium nickel cobalt aluminum oxide	LiNiCoAlO2	NCA	The highest specific energy and cycle life, lower discharge rate capability, good safety.
Lithium nickel cobalt oxide	LiNiCoO2	NCO	Rarely used
Lithium cobalt oxide	LiCoO2	LCO	Expensive, low specific energy, lower discharge rate capability, poor safety.
Lithium iron phosphate	LiFePO4	LFP	Highest discharge rate capability, low specific energy, excellent safety.

Table 3.2.: Comparison of the most common battery technologies, used in CubeSats. Reprint from [28]

Figure 3.6.: The distribution of battery chemistries in CubeSat missions. Reprint from [28].

Battery Chemistry Name	Charging Temperature	Thermal Runaway Temperature
Lithium manganese oxide	0 °C to 45 °C [29]	250 °C
Lithium manganese nickel	0 °C to 50 °C [30]	170 °C
Lithium nickel cobalt aluminum oxide	0 °C to 45°C [31]	150 °C
Lithium nickel cobalt oxide	No data available	210 °C
Lithium cobalt oxide	0 °C to 45°C [32]	150 °C
Lithium iron phosphate	0 °C to 60°C [33]	270 °C

Table 3.3.: Comparison of operating temperatures and thermal runaway temperatures of different battery chemistries. Values for charging temperatures have been taken from commercially available battery cells. Thermal runaway temperature have been taken from the Battery University website[34].

Temperature

Temperature is one of the main factors that contributes to battery degradation. It is also the initiator of the most significant battery failure mode: thermal runaway. Depending on the orbit, the CubeSat surface may be subjected to temperature swings of ± 100 °C. The temperature inside the CubeSat does not fluctuate that extremely, nevertheless, it has to be evaluated, if the battery’s temperature is within its specification. Table 3.3 shows the temperature ranges of the most common battery chemistries. It is notable, that none of the technologies can be charged below 0 °C. At that temperatures, Li-Ion technologies show severely increased internal resistance. Also, at such low temperature, lithium plating may occur, which may lead to catastrophic faults. For that reason, most CubeSat designs implement a heater element, that keeps the battery’s temperature above 0 °C. On the other end of the spectrum, the battery temperature is limited by the thermal runaway effect. At elevated temperatures an exothermic chemical reaction takes place, which accelerates itself due to the increasing temperature in the battery. The higher the SOC (State of charge), the stronger this reaction takes place. It often leads to the destruction of the battery. Bigger battery packs often include a cooling element to prevent thermal runaway from happening. CubeSat often omit such a mechanism, as the increased thermal emission relative to bigger satellites makes it improbable that the thermal runaway temperature is reached.

Radiation

Radiation leads to a degradation of the cathode material and a decomposition of the electrolyte. The effect is a lowered capacity. In a study [35], LFP batteries have been subjected to radiation. A capacity loss of over 25 % after approximately 10 Mrad has been observed. CubeSat batteries in LEO are assumed to be subjected to 10 krad–30 krad of dosage [36]. This would result in a capacity loss of 0.1 %, hence the effect of radiation on the battery’s capacity can be neglected.

Vacuum

When batteries are placed into a vacuum, two issues emerge. The first one being outgassing. Non-perfect seals may lead to evacuation of gas from the battery. This gas may interfere with other components of the CubeSat. For that reason, a “thermal bakeout” has to be performed onto the battery before commissioning of the CubeSat. The specific outgassing process is prescribed by the launch provider. Often, ESA test procedure ECSS-Q-ST-70-02C [37] is used.

Figure 3.7.: A battery qualification process as suggested by [28].

The second issue targets the performance of the battery. Electrolyte-leaks lead to continuous degradation of the battery capacity. Leakage test, like the ones defined in ECSS-E-HB-20-02A [38], aim to detect such leaks.

Vibration

Vibration at the start of the launch device poses a mechanical threat to the battery. Launch providers therefore demand a test regimen to be executed. The exact test process may vary between providers, but National Aeronautics and Space Administration (NASA) test specification JSC 66548 [39] may serve as reference.

Qualification and Flight Acceptance

Due to their high energy density, most batteries are considered as dangerous goods. Therefore, it is advisable to comply with safety regulations, when it comes to handling, transportation and implementation of batteries. Regulations for handling and transportation are stated in UL 1642 [40], UN 38.3[41, 42], and IEC 62281[43].

As already mentioned in previous sections, launch providers may require additional testing procedures with regards to batteries. There is no universal test standard, that is accepted by all providers, but it is advisable to follow standards like JSC 66548 [39], JSC 20793 [44], or ECSS-E-HB-20-02A [38]. All of those standards adhere to a scheme as it is depicted in Figure 3.7. In the following list, the phases of this scheme shall shortly be explained:

1. **Requirement assessment & Market Survey:** The requirements of the mission are identified and the market is explored. This results in a list of requirements for the dimensions, weight, energy storage capability, power capability, lifetime, safety, and monitoring features of the batteries and a list of suppliers that may fulfill them.
2. **Engineering Test:** A selection of promising candidates are procured. Preliminary tests shall evaluate the compliance to space critical areas (i.e. vacuum, vibration, radiation). Furthermore, performance, lifetime, and safety shall be explored.
3. **Qualification Test:** Thorough testing, that qualifies the used technology for space usage. May include destructive testing.
4. **Lot/batch acceptance Test:** Once the used technology is locked in, lot acceptance tests are undertaken, to rule out manufacturing differences between lots.
5. **Flight acceptance Test:** Tests that are applied to the systems that will be used in the flight model. Will require rigorous documentation. Because the test subject will be used on the mission, the tests cannot be destructive.

3.2.2. Battery Charge Controller

BCCs (in some cases also called BMS) manage the charging processes, that are specific to each battery chemistry and provides mechanisms that ensure a safe battery operation. The most common safety functions can be seen in the following list:

- Overcharge protection
- Over-discharge protection
- Discharging over-current protection
- Charging over-current protection
- Short circuit detection

More advanced BCC functions include SOC detection, battery health monitoring and battery conditioning. Such functions are often controlled via SPI (Serial Peripheral Interface) or I²C (Inter-Integrated Circuit) and are therefore reserved for more complex systems.

Some BCCs are integrated into the battery pack. This allows a smaller overall form factor. Such battery packs often are pre-certified and are deemed as being more safe than battery cells alone. External BCC implementation bring the advantage of higher functional flexibility, which often leads to a better integration into the system.

3.2.3. Design

The following sections lay out the design decisions regarding battery and BCC on STS1.

Battery

Due to the highest charging temperature range and the highest thermal runaway temperature, the LFP battery chemistry has been chosen. Cells of the form factor 26650, with an capacity of 3.3 A h and a nominal voltage of 3.2 V will be used (see Appendix A.6 for reference). The cells will be arranged in a 2SP1 configuration. This results in a voltage range of 5 V–7.2 V and a capacity of 6.6 A h (\cong 21.12 W h). As the CSBI will be primarily driven by the battery voltage, the requirement 1-EPS-9 is fulfilled. The batteries discharge capability of 9.9 A (\cong 31.68 W) fulfills requirement 1-EPS-11 . The battery capacity (assuming a maximum Depth of discharge (DOD) of 75 %) fulfills requirement 2-EPS-1 . There is not enough data to be able to fulfill requirement 2-EPS-2 . This case has to be evaluated in future tests.

For simplicity's sake, it has been decided to not implement a battery heating mechanism. Data from the Pegasus mission fortifies this decision, as it shows that the battery temperature only sporadically drops below 0 °C (see Figure 3.8). The moments of sub-zero temperature are in earth's shadow. There, little to none battery charging would take place anyway. Increased battery stress is therefore unlikely. To further protect the battery pack from sub-zero temperature, the battery pack will be wrapped in thermal isolating foil.

The selected batteries are not of the pouch type. Requirement FYS-EPS-7 is therefore fulfilled.

The batteries will be soldered onto a EPS PCB. This PCB will be mounted inside the CubeSat. Requirement FYS-EPS-8 is therefore fulfilled. As the PCB has an edge length of approximately 83 mm and the electrical inhibits will be mounted on the same PCB, the length to the first inhibit can not be farther away than 152 mm. Requirement FYS-EPS-9 is therefore fulfilled.

Figure 3.8.: Temperature data from the Pegasus mission. [45]. The red graph shows the battery temperature.

An integrated battery charge balancing mechanism shall be implemented. BQ29209DRBT shall provide the balancing feature.

A battery test regimen, compatible to JSC 20793[44] shall be defined and executed in the future. This would fulfill requirement FYS-EPS-5.

Battery Charge Controller

Based on a prototype evaluation [4], the LTC4020 (Appendix A.5) has been chosen as BCC. The switching regulator controls the charging process of the battery via a CC/CV scheme. The safety functions “Overcharge protection”, “Over-discharge protection”, “Discharging over-current protection” and “Charging over-current protection” are configurable via external circuitry and will be set to 7.2 V, 5 V, 10 A ($\cong 3C$), and 1.5 A ($\cong 0.5C$) respectively. Battery short is detected by the regulator. In that case, the battery will be disconnected from the power bus. These safety functions fulfill the requirement FYS-EPS-4 and FYS-EPS-6. The regulator also track the battery temperature and stops the charging process, if the temperature is outside the range of 0°C–60°C.

A capacitor bank on one of the EPS PCBs will ensure an output voltage ripple of less than 100 mV. This fulfills requirement 1-EPS-10.

The LTC4020 will drive the the CSBI pin EPS_CHARGING high, if the battery is charging. In all other cases, the pin is pulled low. This fulfills requirement 1-EPS-13.

Circuitry in the vicinity of the BCC will detect two charge states of the battery. The first should trigger, if the battery’s SOC is below 10 %, is not connected, or is shorted (i.e. battery fault). The second state is triggered if the battery’s SOC is above 75 % (i.e. battery good). Those circuits shall be implemented as opamp comparators with an hysteresis of 50 mV. The battery fault trigger shall pull the CSBI pin EPS_BAT_FAULT to high. If not triggered, the pin shall be pulled low. This fulfills requirement 1-EPS-14. The battery good trigger shall pull the CSBI pin EPS_BAT_GOOD high. If not triggered, the pin shall be pulled low. This fulfills requirement 1-EPS-12.

Figure 3.9.: A block diagram of the BCC and the components in its vicinity.

The BCC shall also include a high current path, that is activated, once CSBI pin `EPS_ANT_DEPLOY` is pulled high by another sub system. If `EPS_ANT_DEPLOY` is pulled low, the current path shall be disabled. This current path will be implemented as open drain FET port. The drain pin of the FET and a connection to the positive terminal of the battery shall be connected to a Harwin L-Tek connector (see appendix A.3.1. No switch interruptions shall be between the battery terminal and the Harwin connector. This ensures a high reliability of the antenna deployment mechanism. Two SI7272DP-T1-GE3 (Appendix A.7) shall be used as FET in parallel. One such device contains two FETs, which shall both be connected in parallel. This leads to 4 transistor being connected in parallel. This configuration should provide redundancy and a higher reliability. This fulfills requirement 1-EPS-15.

An overview of the BCC can be seen in Figure 3.9.

3.3. Safety Circuits

Safety circuits are there to prevent dangerous situations. On CubeSats the most common safety feature are the following ones:

Remove Before Flight Pin The RBF's primary function is to prevent premature battery discharge while the CubeSat is stored at the launch provider's site. Additionally to that, it prevents the CubeSat's activation until it is ready to be launched.

Deployment Switches & Deployment Timer The deployment switches, together with the deployment timer, prevent the CubeSat activation while it is inserted in the launch device and shortly after the CubeSat has been deployed from the launch devices.

Battery protection Battery protection circuits shall prevent overcharge/overdischarge/thermal runaway of the battery. This topic is explained in Section 3.2.

3.3.1. Design

Remove Before Flight Pin

For a detailed understanding of the position of the RBF please refer to Figure 2.1. The RBF is responsible to create a connection on two different sections on the EPS circuit.

1. **Solar cells:** The RBF creates a connection between the positive voltage output of the SCCs and the input supply of the BCC. This leads to the disconnection of all the solar cells from any other system if the RBF is inserted.
2. **Battery:** The RBF creates a connection between the positive battery terminal and the BCC. This leads to the disconnection of the battery from any other system. This functionality together with the functionality of the DS, leads to the partial fulfillment of the requirement FYS-EPS-2 - "External Charger Independence".

Those two connections of the RBF lead to the fulfillment of the requirement FYS-EPS-11 - "Remove-Before-Flight pin".

Deployment Switches

The DSs are responsible for creating a connection, or separation, in three points on the EPS circuit. For a detailed understanding of the position of the DS please refer to Figure 2.1.

1. **Solar cells:** Two DSs connected in series are located between the positive voltage output of the SCCs and the input supply of the BCC.
2. **Battery negative terminal:** One DS is located between the negative battery terminal and the BCC. Two DSs in series are located between the positive battery terminal and the GND connection of the BCC.
3. **Power bus:** One DS is located in the Bus Gate, Section 2.2, where it disconnects the output of the BCC from the CSBI.

Two of the DSs are centred at the $-Z$ end face of a rail standoff. All the DSs activation force is not be greater than 3 N. Those three connections of the DSs lead to the fulfillment of the requirement FYS-EPS-10 - "Deployment Switches".

Deployment Timer

The deployment timer shall ensure, that the CubeSat activates only after it has been deployed from the launch device and some distance has been gained. After all deployment switches have been released and the RBF pin has been pulled, a 30 min timer shall be started. If a single or multiple deployment switches are actuated, or the RBF pin is inserted during this time, the timer stops and resets itself. If the timer has been started, and 30 min have elapsed, the deployment timer's switch in the bus gate shall permanently be closed. After the 30 min timer has elapsed once, the deployment timer shall no longer be able to open its switch. Figure 3.10 shows this operation in a flow chart. Figure 3.11 depicts a block diagram of the deployment timer and the bus gate. This fulfills requirement FYS-EPS-3.

Figure 3.10.: A flow chart describing the operation of the deployment timer.

Battery Protection

The design of battery protection feature is explained in Section 3.2.

3.3.2. Latch-up Protection

In order to prevent latch-ups, a high side current switch is implemented, as part of the bus gate. The switch disconnects the CSBI pin VBUS from the EPS, if more than 5 A current flow have been detected. After a short time (multiple seconds, the exact time will be defined at a later stage) the switch reengages the current flow.

3.4. External Charger

The external charging is realized via an extra PCB. This PCB includes the same BCC as the BCC on the EPS. This means it uses the same charge controller IC, as well as the same safety features as described in section 3.2.3. The output of the BCC of this external PCB is connected via the UCI to the battery pack. This connection between the UCI and the battery pack skips the DSs and the RBF, which leads to the fact that it can charge the batteries during ground processing no matter the states of the DSs or the RBF. This lead to the fulfillment of the requirement FYS-EPS-1 - "External Charger". However this contradicts FYS-EPS-2 - "External Charger Independence" as it is possible to power all the subsystems with the external charger if the DSs and the RBF are released. We do not plan to fulfill this requirement as it would lead to an additional circuit domain split via the UCI between the battery and the BCC on the EPS.

Figure 3.11.: The bus gate block.

3.5. Housekeeping Data

Housekeeping data allows to monitor the state of CubeSat in a testing environment and while it is in orbit. The following section elaborates on which data is collected and how it is made available.

3.5.1. Design

The following list enumerates the values that will be measured. This fulfills requirement 3-EPS-1.

1. Temperature of each battery cell
2. Battery pack current
3. Battery cell voltages
4. Battery pack voltage
5. Solar cell current of each cell
6. Solar cell voltage of each cell
7. Output current of each MPPT
8. Voltage of the MPPT bus
9. Current of the MPPT bus
10. Surface temperature of the solar panels
11. UV incidence onto the solar panels

The measurements are executed by 6 MAX11632EEG+ Analog to digital converter (ADC). Two of those (ADC1 and ADC2) are connected to the EDU SPI bus (CSBI X- pins. 27 to 38). The remaining two (ADC3 and ADC4) connect to the COBC SPI bus (CSBI X+ pins. 29 to 40). This fulfills requirement 3-EPS-4. The EDU and COBC SPI interfaces are only connected to their respective ADCs. EDU and COBC are therefore only allowed to configure the ADCs and read out values from the ADC. This fulfills 1-EPS-6.

ADC1 and ADC3 measure the 7 solar cell voltages and 7 solar cell currents. ADC2 and ADC4 measure the battery cell voltages, the battery pack current, and the battery pack voltage. With a maximum sample rate of 300 ks/s, requirement 3-EPS-2 can be fulfilled. The measured values are only readable via the SPI interfaces, which are not accessed by the EPS. Therefore no measurements can be stored by the EPS. This fulfills requirement 3-EPS-3.

Temperature measurement is done via 3 NTC sensor (NXFT15XH103FEAB035). Two of them are glued to the respective cells of the battery pack. The third one is placed onto the battery pack. A 50 μ A constant current source supplies the NTCs, in order to get a measurable signal.

Current measurements are done via an hall-effect based sensor (TMCS1101-Q1).

The voltages are measured directly by the ADCs.

An overview of the complete housekeeping data acquisition setup can be seen in Figure 3.14.

3.6. Mechanics

The following section explains the mechanical structures of the EPS.

3.6.1. Design

Most of the EPS's components will be placed on four PCBs. The template is defined in a GitHub repository [46]. This template fulfills requirement 1-EPS-7. The PCBs are stackable via Samtec ESQT-125-03-M-D-309 connectors. This fulfills requirement 1-EPS-8. The EPS stack will consist of 4 PCBs with cutouts for 2 batteries. The batteries are soldered to the bottom PCB. Additionally to that, they are hold down from the top via a screwed clamp. In Figure 3.12 and Figure 3.13, the EPS PCB assembly is depicted. It can be seen, that the assembly fulfills requirement 2-EPS-3.

Figure 3.12.: A rendering of the EPS PCB assembly.

Dept.	Technical reference	Created by David Freismuth 19.04.2022	Approved by	
		Document type	Document status	
		Title EPS_Assembly	DWG No.	
		Rev.	Date of issue	Sheet 1/1

Figure 3.13.: A drawing containing the measurements of the EPS PCB assembly.

Figure 3.14.: The setup of the housekeeping data acquisition.

4. Behaviour

System requirement 1 demands, that either the solar cells or the battery must be able to drive the power bus, if the respective other part is currently not able to provide power. This circumstance implies four states of operation. These states and the respective conditions of battery and solar cells are depicted in ???. The battery state *operable* and *not operable* refer to the ability of the battery to provide electrical power. The state *not operable* could be caused by a low charge level. In this case, this state is temporary, until the charge level is high enough again. Another reason for the *not operable* state is an internal short of the battery. This fault implies, that the battery is stuck in the *not operable* state, and can not recover.

High power In this state, the solar cells generate power. The battery is operable and is being discharged or charged, depending on the current power demand of the subsystems and solar cell output. See Figure 4.1a for reference.

Solar power only Only the solar cells provide power. This may be caused by a low battery charge level, or a permanent battery fault. The power bus is only driven by the solar cells. The BCC is supplied with the MPPT bus voltage. If the battery is not faulty, the BCC would try to charge it. In this state, the provided voltage on the bus may be volatile, as the light incidence on the solar cells varies strongly over the orbit. The “Battery OK” signal issues this state to other systems, so they may act accordingly. See Figure 4.1b for reference.

Battery power only The solar cells do not provide any energy. This may be the case, if the CubeSat traverses the shade of the earth. The power bus is driven by the battery charger, and in extension by the battery. This continues as long as there is charge left, or the solar cells provide power again. See Figure 4.1c for reference.

No power Solar cells and battery do not provide any power. In this state the power bus is not driven. The EPS does not provide any energy. This results in no operation of the CubeSat. See Figure 4.1d for reference.

Power Flow

(a)

Power Flow

(b)

Power Flow

(c)

Power Flow

(d)

Figure 4.1.: The power flow in the EPS during the respective states of operation.

5. Testing

This chapter explains the test regimes that shall be executed, in order to verify the fulfillment of the requirements. As this document is written in an early design phase, the test regimes may not be complete yet and may be expanded later on.

5.1. Battery

As specified in Section 3.2.3, the battery pack shall be tested according to JSC 20793[44]. This would fulfill the requirement FYS-EPS-5.

5.2. Temperature

Temperature tests shall verify that all requirements are upheld within the temperature range of -5°C – 60°C . The concrete tests are still to be defined. This will fulfill the requirement 1-EPS-21.

5.3. Radiation Hardness

Radiation tests shall verify that all requirements are upheld until a Total ionizing dose (TID) of 100 krad. The concrete tests are still to be defined. This will fulfill the requirement 1-EPS-22.

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A. Appendix

A.1. Azurspace 3G30A Datasheet

30% Triple Junction GaAs Solar Cell Assembly
 Type: TJ Solar Cell Assembly 3G30A
Improved Voltage at Maximum Power Point

This cell type is an InGaP/GaAs/Ge on Ge substrate triple junction solar cell assembly (efficiency class 30%). The solar cell assembly has an improved grid-design and is equipped with an integral bypass diode, interconnectors and cover glass.

3G30A

30% Triple Junction GaAs Solar Cell Assembly

Type: TJ Solar Cell Assembly 3G30A

Design and Mechanical Data

Base Material	GaInP/GaAs/Ge on Ge substrate
AR-coating	TiO ₂ /Al ₂ O ₃
Dimensions	40.15 x 80.15 mm ± 0.1 mm
Cell Area	30.18 cm ²
Average Weight	≤ 118 mg/cm ²
Thickness	280 ± 25 μm
Coverglass	CMX 100
Coverglass thickness	100 μm
Interconnectors (3x front side/ 1x diode)	Kovar coated with Ag
Dimensions (interconnector)	6.5 x 7.53 mm
Interconnector thickness	25 μm

Electrical Data (SCA)

		BOL	2.5E14	5E14	1E15
Average Open Circuit V _{oc}	[mV]	2690	2606	2554	2512
Average Short Circuit I _{sc}	[mA]	519.6	517.9	513.4	501.3
Voltage at max. Power V _{mp}	[mV]	2409	2343	2288	2244
Current at max. Power I _{mp}	[mA]	502.9	501.7	499.1	485.1
Average Efficiency η _{bare} (1367 W/m ²)	[%]	29.3	28.4	27.6	26.3
Average Efficiency η _{bare} (1353 W/m ²)	[%]	29.6	28.7	27.9	26.6

Standard: CASOLBA 2005 (05-20MV1, etc); Spectrum: AMO WRC = 1367 W/m²; T = 28 °C

@fluence 1 MeV [e/cm²]

Acceptance Values (SCA)

Voltage V _{op}	2350 mV
Min. average current I _{op avg} @ V _{op}	500 mA
Min. individual current I _{op min} @ V _{op}	470 mA

Shadow protection

Integrated protection diode	V _{forward} (620 mA) ≤ 2.5 V
T = 25°C ± 3°C	I _{reverse} (2.8 V) ≤ 100 μA

Temperature Gradients

		BOL	2.5E14	5E14	1E15
Open Circuit Voltage	ΔV _{oc} /ΔT↑ [mV/°C]	- 6.2	- 6.5	- 6.6	- 6.7
Short Circuit Current	ΔI _{sc} /ΔT↑ [mA/°C]	0.36	0.33	0.35	0.38
Voltage at max. Power	ΔV _{mp} /ΔT↑ [mV/°C]	- 6.7	- 6.8	- 7.1	- 7.2
Current at max. Power	ΔI _{mp} /ΔT↑ [mA/°C]	0.24	0.20	0.24	0.28

@fluence 1 MeV [e/cm²]

Threshold Values

Absorptivity	≤ 0.91 (with CMX 100 AR)
Pull Test	> 7 N at 0° (with standard Kovar interconnector)

A.2. EPO-TEK E4110-LV

EPO-TEK[®] E4110-LV

Technical Data Sheet
For Reference Only

Electrically Conductive, Silver Epoxy

Date: September 2017
Rev: VII
No. of Components: Two
Mix Ratio by Weight: 10 : 1
Specific Gravity: Part A: 3.10 Part B: 0.96
Pot Life: 6 Hours
Shelf Life- Bulk: One year at room temperature

Recommended Cure: 150°C / 1 Hour

Minimum Alternative Cure(s):

May not achieve performance properties listed below

150°C / 15 Minutes

80°C / 3 Hours

23°C / 3 Days

NOTES:

- Container(s) should be kept closed when not in use.
- Filled systems should be stirred thoroughly before mixing and prior to use.
- Performance properties (rheology, conductivity, others) of the product may vary from those stated on the data sheet when bi-pak/syringe packaging or post-processing of any kind is performed. Epoxy's warranties shall not apply to any products that have been reprocessed or repackaged from Epoxy's delivered status/container into any other containers of any kind, including but not limited to syringes, bi-paks, cartridges, pouches, tubes, capsules, films or other packages.
- Syringe packaging will impact initial viscosity and effective pot life, potentially beyond stated parameters.

Typical Properties: Cure condition: 150°C / 1 Hour Different batches, conditions & applications yield differing results.

Data below is not guaranteed. To be used as a guide only, not as a specification. * denotes test on lot acceptance basis

PHYSICAL PROPERTIES:

* Color (before cure):	Part A: Silver	Part B: Clear
* Consistency:	Smooth flowing paste	
* Viscosity (23°C) @ 100 rpm:	350 - 850	cPs
Thixotropic Index:	1.9	
* Glass Transition Temp:	≥ 40	°C (Dynamic Cure: 20-200°C/ISO 25 Min; Ramp -10-200°C @20°C/Min)
Coefficient of Thermal Expansion (CTE):		
Below Tg:	50	x 10 ⁻⁶ in/in°C
Above Tg:	283	x 10 ⁻⁶ in/in°C
Shore D Hardness:	60	
Lap Shear @ 23°C:	1,080	psi
Die Shear @ 23°C:	≥ 5	Kg 1,778 psi
Degradation Temp:	365	°C
Weight Loss:		
@ 200°C:	0.33	%
@ 250°C:	0.65	%
@ 300°C:	1.19	%
Suggested Operating Temperature:	< 250	°C (Intermittent)
Storage Modulus:	788,340	psi
Ion Content:	Cl ⁻ : 332 ppm	Na ⁺ : 0 ppm
	NH ₄ ⁺ : 27 ppm	K ⁺ : 0 ppm
* Particle Size:	≤ 45	microns

ELECTRICAL AND THERMAL PROPERTIES:

Thermal Conductivity:	1.8	W/mK
* Volume Resistivity @ 23°C (150°C/1 Hour):	≤ 0.0005	Ohm-cm
* Volume Resistivity @ 23°C (25°C 40-60%RH/3 Day Cure):	≤ 0.009	Ohm-cm

Epoxyes and Adhesives for Demanding Applications™

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EPO-TEK® E4110-LV Advantages & Suggested Application Notes:

- Very low viscosity, silver-filled epoxy which can be applied by hand, brushing, roll coating, tooth-picking or stamping, or spraying.
- After cure, it has a shiny, almost metallic looking finish. This can be used to repair surface imperfections in metal coating applications such as electroplating or sputtering processes.
- Suggested applications:
 - Electronics - filling vias at the PCB level for top-to-bottom connections; EMI & Rf shielding applications.
 - Hybrids - electrically conductive potting for radar systems. The potting can be self-leveling, trapping no voids, and non-cracking with performance.
 - Optics - die-attaching LED's by the stamping process, or pin-transferring applications.
- NASA approved, low outgassing epoxy – <http://outgassing.nasa.gov/>

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A.3. Solar Panel Connectors

A.3.1. Male Connector

Customer Information Sheet

DRAWING No.: M80-836XXXX

IF IN DOUBT - ASK

NOT TO SCALE

THIRD ANGLE PROJECTION

ALL DIMENSIONS IN mm

SPECIFICATIONS:
MATERIAL:
 MOLDING = GLASS-FILLED PPS, UL94V-0, BLACK
 CONTACT = BRASS
 LATCH = COPPER ALLOY
FINISH:
 CONTACT:
 22 = 0.75µm GOLD ON CONTACT AREA,
 0.3µm 90/10 TIN/LEAD ON TAILS
 42 = 0.75µm GOLD ON CONTACT AREA,
 0.3µm 100% TIN OVER NICKEL ON TAILS
 45 = 0.75µm GOLD
 LATCH = NICKEL
ELECTRICAL:
 CURRENT RATING AT 25°C = 3.0A MAX
 CURRENT RATING AT 85°C = 2.2A MAX
 WORKING VOLTAGE = 800V AC/DC
 VOLTAGE PROOF = 1200V AC/DC
 CONTACT RESISTANCE = 25mΩ MAX
 INSULATION RESISTANCE = 100MΩ MIN
MECHANICAL:
 DURABILITY = 500 OPERATIONS
ENVIRONMENTAL:
 TEMPERATURE RANGE = -55°C TO +125°C
PACKING:
 TUBE, 2-OFF M80-0030006 STRAIN RELIEF STRAPS
 PER CONNECTOR IN BAG
 FOR COMPLETE SPECIFICATION, SEE COMPONENT
 SPECIFICATION C005XX (LATEST ISSUE).

RECOMMENDED PCB LAYOUT
 TOLERANCE $\pm 0.05\text{mm}$

ORDER CODE:
M80-836XXXX
 No. OF CONTACTS:
 02 - 07, 17, 22
 FINISH:
 22 - GOLD, 90/10 TIN/LEAD
 42 - GOLD, 100% TIN OVER NICKEL
 45 - GOLD

MGP	5	21.07.21	30679
NAME	ISS.	DATE	CN/CO
APPROVED: MGP			
CHECKED: RTP			
DRAWN: R. ADDE			
CUSTOMER REF.:			
ASSEMBLY DRG:			

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			FINISH: SEE ABOVE	DRAWING NUMBER: M80-836XXXX

Mouser Electronics

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Harwin:

[M80-8360222](#) [M80-8360442](#) [M80-8360422](#) [M80-8360445](#) [M80-8360242](#)

A.3.2. Female Connector

Customer Information Sheet

DRAWING No.: M80-898XXXX IF IN DOUBT - ASK (C) NOT TO SCALE THIRD ANGLE PROJECTION ALL DIMENSIONS IN mm

BRITISH STANDARD
 ORDER CODE: TO BS9525 F0033
B5740-1XX-F-C-X
 TOTAL No. OF CONTACTS: _____
 02 - 07 & 17
 FINISH: _____
 0 = GOLD CLIP, TIN SHELL
 2 = GOLD CLIP, GOLD SHELL

ORDER CODE:
M80-898XXXX
 TOTAL No. OF CONTACTS: _____
 02 - 07 & 17
 FINISH: _____
 01 = GOLD CLIP, TIN SHELL
 05 = GOLD CLIP, GOLD SHELL

SECTION X-X

SPECIFICATIONS:

MATERIAL:
 MOULDING = GLASS-FILLED POLYESTER UL94V-0, BLACK
 CLIP = BERYLLIUM COPPER
 SHELL = COPPER ALLOY

FINISH:
 01 = 0.30µ GOLD CLIP, 4.0µ 100% TIN OVER NICKEL SHELL
 05 = 0.30µ GOLD CLIP, 0.28µ GOLD SHELL

ELECTRICAL:
 CUURRENT RATING AT 25°C = 3.0A MAX
 CURRENT RATING AT 85°C = 2.2A MAX
 WORKING VOLTAGE = 800V AC/DC
 VOLTAGE PROOF = 1200V AC/DC
CONTACT RESISTANCE:
 INITIAL: 20mΩ MAX
 AFTER CONDITIONING: 25mΩ MAX
INSULATION RESISTANCE:
 INITIAL = 1000MΩ MIN
 AFTER CONDITIONING = 100MΩ MIN

MECHANICAL:
 DURAILITY = 500 OPERATIONS
ENVIRONMENTAL:
 TEMPERATURE RANGE = -55°C TO +125°C
 PACKING = BAG (CONTACTS AND MOULDINGS UN-ASSEMBLED)
 FOR COMPLETE SPECIFICATION, SEE COMPONENT SPECIFICATION C005XX (LATEST ISSUE)

NOTES:

1. RECOMMENDED WIRE TYPE = BS3G210 TYPE A, PTFE INSULATED, 24 - 28 AWG. MAX INSULATION DIAMETER = Ø1.10mm. STRIP WIRE BY 2.00mm.
2. RECOMMENDED HAND CRIMP TOOL = M22520/2-01 WITH POSITIONER T5747. SEE TOOLING INSTRUCTION SHEET IS-01 FOR COMPLETE CRIMPING INFORMATION.
3. CONTACT INSERTION & EXTRACTION TOOL = Z80-280. REFER TO INSTRUCTION SHEET IS-25 FOR ASSEMBLY INSTRUCTIONS.

MSP	12	29.10.14	12649
NAME	ISS.	DATE	C/NOTE
APPROVED:		M.PERREN	
CHECKED:		S.BENNETT	
DRAWN:		W. J. BOURNE	
CUSTOMER REF.:			
ASSEMBLY DRG:			

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TOLERANCES
 X. = ±1mm
 X.X = ±0.25mm
 X.XX = ±0.10mm
 X.XXX = ±0.01mm
 ANGLES = ±5°
 UNLESS STATED

MATERIAL:
 SEE ABOVE
FINISH: SEE ABOVE
S/AREA: mm²

TITLE: DATAMATE CRIMP
 SIL SOCKET ASSEMBLY
 SMALL BORE (24 - 28AWG)
DRAWING NUMBER:
M80-898XXXX

SHT
 2 OF 2

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[B5740-104-F-C-2](#) [B5740-107-F-C-2](#) [B5740-103-F-C-2](#) [B5740-105-F-C-2](#) [B5740-117-F-C-2](#) [M80-8980305](#) [M80-](#)
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A.4. Solar Cell Controller

High efficiency solar battery charger with embedded MPPT

Features

- 0.3 V to 5.5 V operating input voltage
- 140 mΩ internal synchronous rectifier
- 120 mΩ internal power active switch
- 100 kHz fixed PWM frequency
- Duty cycle controlled by MPPT algorithm
- Output voltage regulation, overcurrent and overtemperature protection
- Input source reverse polarity protection
- Built-in soft-start
- Up to 95% efficiency
- TSSOP8 package 3x4.4 mm

Applications

- Smart phones and GPS systems
- Wireless headsets
- Small appliances, sensors
- Portable media players
- Digital still cameras
- Toys and portable healthcare

Description

The SPV1040 device is a low power, low voltage, monolithic step-up converter with an input voltage range from 0.3 V to 5.5 V, capable of maximizing the energy generated by solar cells (or fuel cells), where low input voltage handling capability is extremely important. Thanks to the embedded MPPT algorithm, even under varying environmental conditions (such as irradiation, dirt, temperature) the SPV1040 offers maximum efficiency in terms of power harvested from the cells and transferred to the output. The device employs a voltage regulation loop, which fixes the charging battery voltage via a resistor divider.

It is possible to set the maximum output current according to charging requirements by a sense resistor .

The SPV1040 protects itself and other application devices by stopping the PWM switching if either the maximum current threshold (up to 1.8 A_{pk}) is reached or the maximum temperature limit (up to 155 °C) is exceeded. An additional built-in feature of the SPV1040 is the input source reverse polarity protection, which prevents damage in case of reverse connection of the solar panel on the input.

Product status link

[SPV1040](#)

Product summary

Order code	SPV1040T
Package	TSSOP8
Packing	Tube
Order code	SPV1040TR
Package	TSSOP8
Packing	Tape and reel

Product label

1 Block diagram

Figure 1. Block diagram

Figure 2. Simplified application circuit

In order to set up the application and simulate the related test results please go to www.st.com.

2 Pin description

Table 1. Pin description

Pin	Name	Type	Description
1	MPP-SET	I	Non-inverting input to sense the PV cell voltage. It cannot be left floating.
2	GND	Ground	Power ground reference.
3	LX	I	Booster inductor connection.
4	VOUT	O	Booster output voltage.
5	VCTRL	I	Inverting input of constant Voltage control loop. It cannot be left floating.
6	ICTRL_MINUS	I	Inverting input of constant current control loop. Connect to GND if not used: cannot be left floating.
7	ICTRL_PLUS	I	Non-inverting input of constant current control loop. Connect to GND if not used: cannot be left floating.
8	XSHUT	I	Shutdown input pin: XSHUT = low, the device in power off mode. XSHUT = high, the device is enabled for operating mode. This pin cannot be left floating.

Figure 3. Pin connection top view

AM02613v1

3 Electrical ratings

Table 2. Absolute maximum ratings

Symbol	Parameter	Value	Unit
VOUT	VOUT pin voltage range	[-0.3, 5.5]	V
LX	LX pin voltage range	[-5.5, VOUT]	
VOUT-V _{LX}	Maximum voltage drop between VOUT and LX pins	[5.5]	
MPP-SET	Analog input	[-5.5, VOUT]	
VOUT-V _{MPP-SET}	Maximum voltage drop between VOUT and MPPT pins	[5.5]	
XSHUT	Analog input	[-5.5, VOUT]	
VOUT-V _{XSHUT}	Maximum voltage drop between VOUT and X-SHUT pins	[5.5]	
ICTRL_PLUS	Analog input	[-0.3, VOUT]	
ICTRL_MINUS	Analog input	[-0.3, VOUT]	
VCTRL	Analog input	[-0.3, VOUT]	
GND	Ground	0	

Table 3. Thermal data

Symbol	Parameter	Value	Unit
R _{thj-amb}	Thermal resistance, junction-to-ambient	135	°C/W
T _{jop}	Junction operating temperature	-40 to 125	°C
T _{stg}	Storage temperature	-40 to 150	°C

Note: R_{thJA} has been measured on a 2-layer PCB: FR4, 35 μ m Cu thickness, 2.8 cm²

4 Electrical characteristics

$V_{MPP-SET} = 0.5\text{ V}$, $V_{CTRL} = I_{ctrl+} = I_{ctrl-} = \text{GND}$, $XSHUT = 0.5\text{ V}$, $T_J = -40\text{ °C}$ to 125 °C , unless otherwise specified.

Table 4. Electrical characteristics

Symbol	Parameter	Test conditions	Min.	Typ.	Max.	Unit
Input source section						
$V_{MPP-SET}$	Low boost voltage threshold	$V_{OUT} = 3.3\text{ V}$	0.4	0.45	0.50	V
I_q	Quiescent current	$I_{LOAD} = 0\text{ mA}$, $V_{CTRL} = 2\text{ V}$, $V_{OUT} = 3.3\text{ V}$		60	80	μA
I_{SD}	Shutdown current	$V_{OUT} = 3.3\text{ V}$, $V_{CTRL} = 2\text{ V}$, $I_{LOAD} = 0\text{ mA}$, $XSHUT = \text{GND}$		0.7	5	
I_{rev}	Reverse input source current	$V_{MPP-SET} = -4\text{ V}$, $V_{OUT} = 1.5\text{ V}$		1	5	
V_{UVLO}	Undervoltage lockout threshold for turn ON @ $V_{OUT} = 3.3\text{ V}$	$V_{MPP-SET}$ increasing		0.27	0.34	V
	Undervoltage lockout threshold for turn OFF @ $V_{OUT} = 3.3\text{ V}$	$V_{MPP-SET}$ decreasing	0.14	0.24		
Power section						
$R_{DS(on)-N}$	N-channel power switch ON resistance				120	$\text{m}\Omega$
$R_{DS(on)-P}$	P-channel synchronous rectifier ON resistance	$V_{CTRL} = 2\text{ V}$			140	
Control section						
$V_{MPPT-THR}$	MPPT-mode threshold	V_{OUT} increasing, $V_{MPP-SET} = 1.5\text{ V}$	1.7	1.8	2	V
V_{OUT}	Output voltage range	$V_{MPP-SET} \geq 1.5\text{ V}$	2		5.2 ⁽¹⁾	V
P_{OUT} ⁽²⁾	Maximum output power	$V_{MPP-SET} \geq 1.5\text{ V}$			3	W
I_{LX}	Maximum inductor current peak		1.5	1.65	1.8	A

Symbol	Parameter	Test conditions	Min.	Typ.	Max.	Unit
F _{PWM}	PWM signal frequency		70	100	130	kHz
V _{REF}	Internal V _{CTRL} reference voltage	V _{OUT} ≥ 1.8 V, V _{CTRL} increasing	1.2	1.25	1.3	V
V _{ICTRL}	Sensing current offset	I _{CTRL+} - I _{CTRL-} decreasing	40	50	60	mV
XSHUT	XSHUT logic low	XSHUT increasing		0.27	0.34	V
	XSHUT logic High	XSHUT decreasing	0.14	0.24		
Thermal shutdown						
T _{shutdown}	Overtemperature threshold for turn OFF	Temperature increasing		155		°C
	Overtemperature threshold for turn ON	Temperature decreasing		130		

1. According to the absolute maximum ratings the output charge voltage cannot be above 4.8 V but if a higher V_{OUT} up to 5.2 V is needed, a Schottky diode must be placed between the L_x and V_{OUT} pins as shown in Figure 1. In such way the Schottky diode in parallel to the embedded P-channel MOSFET reduces the voltage drop between the VLX pin and the V_{OUT} pin determined by the body diode when the internal PMOS is OFF from 0.7 V down to 0.3 V.
2. Given $T_j = T_a + R_{thJA} \times P_D$, and assuming $R_{thJA} = 135 \text{ }^\circ\text{C/W}$, and that in order to avoid device destruction T_{jmax} must be $\leq 125 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$, and that in the worst conditions $T_A = 85 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$, the power dissipated inside the device is given by: $P_D \leq (T_j - T_A) / R_{thJA} = 295 \text{ mW}$. Therefore, if in the worst case the efficiency is assumed to be 90%, then $P_{IN-MAX} = 3.3 \text{ W}$ and $P_{OUT-MAX} = 3 \text{ W}$.

5 Typical characteristics

Table 5. Typical Conversion Efficiency

$V_{IN}[V]$	$P_{IN}[W]$	$P_{OUT}/P_{IN}[\%]$
1.50	0.25 to 2.0	80% to 90%
2.00	0.25 to 2.5	80% to 95%
2.50	0.25 to 3.0	80% to 95%

Test conditions (ref to Figure 1):
 $10\mu H \leq L \leq 100\mu H$ ($L_{DCR} \leq 0.3\Omega$);
 $R_S = 0\Omega$; R_{F1} , R_{F2} and C_F unmounted;
 $ICTRL+ = ICTRL- = GND$

Figure 4. V_{LX} and I_{LX} waveforms - $D = 39\%$

Figure 5. V_{LX} and I_{LX} waveforms - $D = 68\%$

6 Detailed description

The SPV1040 is a monolithic, high efficiency, low voltage, self-powered DC-DC converter that operates over a 0.3 V to 5.5 V DC input voltage range and provides a single output voltage. The device provides regulated output voltage and current by sensing the VCTRL feedback of the external resistor divider and the voltage drop on the external sense resistor R_s , respectively. High efficiency is ensured by low power consumption in any working mode and by the embedded perturb and observe MPPT algorithm. The SPV1040 guarantees its own safety and application safety by stopping the N-channel power switch in case of overcurrent or overtemperature conditions.

6.1 Soft-start

In order to guarantee the power-up even when VOUT is very low (battery completely discharged), a proper start-up strategy has been implemented. Taking into account that the device is powered by the VOUT voltage, If VOUT is lower than 0.8 V, the device moves from power off to soft-start mode and the current flows from the input to output through the intrinsic body diode of the synchronous rectifier. In this condition VOUT follows the LX voltage. The IC exits start-up mode when VOUT reaches 0.8 V.

6.2 Start-up mode

When VOUT goes above 0.8 V but it is still lower than 2 V, a proper biasing of both MOSFETs is not guaranteed yet. In such conditions, the N-channel power switch is forced ON with a fixed duty cycle and the energy is transferred to the load via the intrinsic body diode of the P-channel synchronous switch. If the shutdown overcurrent limit is exceeded, the power switch is immediately turned OFF. The SPV1040 leaves start-up mode as soon as VOUT goes above 2 V.

6.3 MPPT mode

Once the device has exited start-up mode, the SPV1040 enters MPPT mode to search for the maximum power point. The perturb and observe algorithm is based on monitoring either the voltage or the current supplied by the DC power source unit so that the PWM signal duty cycle is increased or decreased step-by-step according to the input power trend. Refer to [Figure 6](#), which illustrates the MPPT working principle.

6.4 Constant voltage regulation

The constant voltage control loop consists of an internal voltage reference, an op-amp and an external resistor divider that senses the battery voltage and fixes the voltage regulation set-point at the value specified by the user.

6.5 Constant current regulation

The constant current control loop consists of an op-amp and an external sense resistor that feeds the current sensing circuit with a voltage proportional to the DC output current. This resistor determines the current regulation set-point and must be adequately rated in terms of power dissipation. It provides the capability to fix the maximum output current to protect the battery.

6.6 Overcurrent protection (OVC)

When the current that flows through the inductor reaches 1.8 A (overcurrent shutdown limit), the N-channel power switch is immediately forced OFF and the P-channel synchronous rectifier is switched ON. Once the overcurrent condition has expired (the inductor current goes below $1.8 A_{pk}$) the N-channel power switch is turned back ON.

6.7 Overtemperature protection

When the temperature sensed at silicon level reaches 155 °C (overtemperature shutdown limit), the N-channel power switch is immediately forced OFF and the P-channel synchronous rectifier is switched ON. The device becomes operative again as soon as the silicon temperature goes below 130 °C.

6.8 Shutdown mode

The XSHUT pin low shuts OFF all internal circuitry, achieving the lowest power consumption mode.

6.9 Undervoltage lockout

In order to prevent batteries from over-discharging, the device turns OFF in case of MPPSET voltage is lower than 0.24 V (no irradiation). A hysteresis has been implemented to avoid unpredictable ON-OFF switching.

6.10 Reverse polarity

In order to avoid damage to the device and battery discharge when the solar panel connection is reverse-inserted, a dedicated protection circuit has been implemented. In such condition, the SPV1040 stays OFF until the panel is inserted correctly.

Figure 6. MPPT working principle

6.11 Burst mode

When the output voltage reaches the battery charge voltage, the MPP-SET voltage drops below 450 mV, or the output current reaches the output maximum current limit, the duty cycle D drops down to 10% and the device evolves from operating mode to burst mode. The converter no longer works at constant frequency, but at frequencies gradually lower (1 T_{ON} over 1 PWM cycle, 1 T_{ON} over 2 PWM cycles, ..., 1 T_{ON} over 16 PWM cycles) prior to entering sleep-in mode.

6.12 Sleep-in mode

Once sleep-in mode has been entered, no current is provided to the load. The device exits this mode once the cause, which forced it into this state, is no longer present.

7 Package information

In order to meet environmental requirements, ST offers these devices in different grades of ECOPACK® packages, depending on their level of environmental compliance. ECOPACK® specifications, grade definitions and product status are available at: www.st.com.

ECOPACK® is an ST trademark.

7.1 TSSOP8 package information

Figure 7. TSSOP8 package outline

Table 6. TSSOP8 package mechanical data

Dim.	mm		
	Min.	Typ.	Max.
A			1.20
A1	0.05		0.15
A2	0.80	1.00	1.05
b	0.19		0.30
c	0.09		0.20
D	2.90	3.00	3.10
E	6.20	6.40	6.60
E1	4.30	4.40	4.50

Dim.	mm		
	Min.	Typ.	Max.
e		0.65	
L	0.45	0.60	0.75
L1		1.00	
L2		0.25	
k	0		8
aaa			0.10

Note: Dimensions D does not include mold flash or protrusions. Mold flash or protrusions do not exceed 0.15 mm per side.
Dimension E1 does not include interlead flash or protrusions. Interlead flash or protrusions do not exceed 0.25 mm per side.

7.2 TSSOP8 packing information

Figure 8. TSSOP8 carrier tape outline

Figure 9. TSSOP8 reel outline

Revision history

Table 7. Document revision history

Date	Revision	Changes
08-Oct-2010	1	First release.
06-Apr-2011	2	Updated the cover page, DFN8 information deleted, <i>Chapter 3</i> , <i>Chapter 4</i> and <i>Chapter 6</i> .
04-Oct-2011	3	– Updated <i>Figure 1</i> , <i>Figure 2</i> , <i>Table 2</i> and <i>Table 5</i> – Minor text changes.
25-Jul-2012	4	Updated <i>Figure 4</i> , <i>Figure 5</i> , <i>Figure 6</i> , <i>Figure 7</i> , <i>Figure 8</i> , and <i>Figure 9</i> .
21-Mar-2013	5	Updated <i>Figure 1</i> and <i>note 1</i> in <i>Table 5</i> .
26-Sep-2016	6	Added <i>Section 7.2 : "Packing information"</i> .
06-Feb-2017	7	Update TSSOP8 package information.
17-Jan-2020	8	Figures from 4 to 9 replaced by <i>Table 5</i> ; minor text changes.
2-Feb-2021	9	Updated <i>Table 1</i> . Pin description and <i>Table 2</i> . Absolute maximum ratings

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A.5. Battery Charge Controller

55V Buck-Boost Multi-Chemistry Battery Charger

FEATURES

- **Wide Voltage Range: 4.5V to 55V Input, Up to 55V Output (60V Absolute Maximums)**
- **Synchronous Buck-Boost DC/DC Controller**
- **Li-Ion and Lead-Acid Charge Algorithms**
- **±0.5% Float Voltage Accuracy**
- **±5% Charge Current Accuracy**
- **Instant-On for Heavily Discharged Batteries**
- **Ideal Diode Controller Provides Low Loss PowerPath When Input Power is Limited**
- **Input Voltage Regulation for High Impedance Input Supplies and Solar Panel Peak Power Operation**
- **Onboard Timer for Protection and Termination**
- **Bad Battery Detection with Auto-Reset**
- **NTC Input for Temperature Qualified Charging**
- **Binary Coded Open-Collector Status Pins**
- **Low Profile (0.75mm) 38-Pin 5mm × 7mm QFN Package**

APPLICATIONS

- Portable Industrial and Medical Equipment
- Solar-Powered Systems
- Military Communications Equipment
- 12V to 24V Embedded Automotive Systems

DESCRIPTION

The **LTC®4020** is a high voltage power manager providing PowerPath™ instant-on operation and high efficiency battery charging over a wide voltage range. An onboard buck-boost DC/DC controller operates with battery and/or system voltages above, below, or equal to the input voltage.

The LTC4020 seamlessly manages power distribution between battery and converter outputs in response to load variations, battery charge requirements and input power supply limitations.

The LTC4020 battery charger can provide a constant-current/constant-voltage charge algorithm (CC/CV), constant-current charging (CC), or charging with an optimized 4-step, 3-stage lead-acid battery charge profile. Maximum converter and battery charge currents are resistor programmable.

The IC's instant-on operation ensures system load power even with a fully discharged battery. Additional safety features include preconditioning for heavily discharged batteries and an integrated timer for termination and protection.

LT, LT, LTC, LTM, Linear Technology and the Linear logo are registered trademarks and PowerPath is a trademark of Linear Technology Corporation. All other trademarks are the property of their respective owners. Protected by U.S. Patents, including 7583113 and 8405362.

TYPICAL APPLICATION

Buck-Boost DC/DC Converter Controller with PowerPath Battery Charger Accepts Inputs from 4.5V to 55V and Produces Output Voltages Up to 55V

5V to 30V 6-Cell Lead-Acid Supply/Charger Maximum Power Efficiency vs VIN (Application Circuit on Page 37)

LTC4020

ABSOLUTE MAXIMUM RATINGS

(Note 1)

PV_{IN} , SENSVIN.....	-0.3 to 60V
BST1, BST2.....	-0.3 to 66V
SW1, SW2.....	-2 to 60V
SENSVIN – PV_{IN}	-0.3 to 60V
BST1 – SW1, BST2 – SW2.....	-0.3 to 6V
SENSVIN – SENSTOP, SENSBOT – SENSGND	-0.3 to 0.3V
CSP, CSN	-0.3 to 60V
CSP – CSN.....	-0.3 to 0.3V
STAT1, STAT2, SHDN	-0.3 to 60V
V_{FBMAX} , V_{INREG} , V_{FB} , V_{FBMIN} , BAT, FBG.....	-0.3 to 60V
MODE.....	-0.3 to 6V
Status Pin Currents: STAT1, STAT2	5mA
Operating Junction Temperature Range (Note 2).....	-40°C to 125°C
Storage Temperature Range	-65°C to 150°C

PIN CONFIGURATION

ORDER INFORMATION

(<http://www.linear.com/product/LTC4020#orderinfo>)

LEAD FREE FINISH	TAPE AND REEL	PART MARKING*	PACKAGE DESCRIPTION	TEMPERATURE RANGE
LTC4020EUHF#PBF	LTC4020EUHF#TRPBF	4020	38-Lead (5mm × 7mm) Plastic QFN	-40°C to 125°C
LTC4020IUHF#PBF	LTC4020IUHF#TRPBF	4020	38-Lead (5mm × 7mm) Plastic QFN	-40°C to 125°C

Consult LTC Marketing for parts specified with wider operating temperature ranges. *The temperature grade is identified by a label on the shipping container.

For more information on lead free part marking, go to: <http://www.linear.com/leadfree/>

For more information on tape and reel specifications, go to: <http://www.linear.com/tapeandree/>. Some packages are available in 500 unit reels through designated sales channels with #TRMPBF suffix.

ELECTRICAL CHARACTERISTICS The ● denotes the specifications which apply over the specified operating junction temperature range, otherwise specifications are at $T_A = 25^{\circ}\text{C}$ (Note 2). $PV_{IN} = \text{SENSVIN} = \text{CSP} = \text{CSN} = \text{BAT} = 20\text{V}$, $\text{SHDN} = 2\text{V}$, $C_{(TG1, BG1, TG2, BG2)} = 1000\text{pF}$, $V_{RNG/SS} = 2\text{V}$.

SYMBOL	PARAMETER	CONDITIONS	MIN	TYP	MAX	UNITS	
Buck-Boost Switching Converter							
V_{IN}	Operating Voltage Range	PV_{IN} , SENSVIN	●	4.5	55	V	
UVLO	V_{IN} Supply UVLO (Rising)	DC/DC Functions Enabled	●	3.6	4.0	4.4	V
	V_{IN} Supply UVLO Hysteresis	V_{IN} Falling			0.4		V
	SENSVIN Supply UVLO (Rising)	INTV _{CC} Enabled			3.4		V
	SENSVIN UVLO Hysteresis	SENSVIN Falling			0.3		V
	BST Supplies UVLO (Rising)	BST1 – SW1; BST2 – SW2;	●	3.0	3.3	3.8	V
	BST Supplies UVLO Hysteresis	SW1, SW2 = 0V			0.4		V

4020fd

ELECTRICAL CHARACTERISTICS The ● denotes the specifications which apply over the specified operating junction temperature range, otherwise specifications are at $T_A = 25^\circ\text{C}$ (Note 2). $PV_{IN} = SENSEVIN = CSP = CSN = BAT = 20V$, $SHDN = 2V$, $C(TG1, BG1, TG2, BG2) = 1000pF$, $V_{RNG/SS} = 2V$.

SYMBOL	PARAMETER	CONDITIONS		MIN	TYP	MAX	UNITS
INTV _{CC}	Boost Refresh Supply Voltage	$I_{LOAD} = 5mA$	●	4.85	5.0	5.15	V
	Boost Refresh Supply Dropout	$PV_{IN} = 4.5V$; $I_{INTVCC} = 5mA$			4.46		V
	Boost Refresh Supply Short-Circuit Current Limit	$V_{INTVCC} = 0V$	●	85	150		mA
I _{PVIN}	PV_{IN} Operating Current	Note 3; $I_{TH} = 0V$	●		1.6	3	mA
	Shutdown Current	$V_{SHDN} = 0$	●		3	6	μA
I _{SENSEVIN}	SENSEVIN Operating Current		●		0.25	0.5	mA
	Shutdown Current	$V_{SHDN} = 0$	●		25	60	μA
I _{SENSTOP}	SENSETOP Operating Current				32.5		μA
	Shutdown Current	$V_{SHDN} = 0$			0.1		μA
V _{FBMAX}	DC/DC Converter Reference	Charging Terminated	●	2.7	2.75	2.8	V
SHDN	IC Enable Threshold (Rising) Threshold Hysteresis		●	1.175	1.225	1.275	V
	SHDN Pin Bias Current				10		nA
V _{SENS}	DC/DC Converter Inductor Current Limit (Average Value)	$V_{SENSEVIN} - V_{SENSTOP}$; $V_{SENSEGND} - V_{SENSEBOT}$	●	45	50	60	mV
	Reverse Current Inhibit (Average Value)	V_{ITH} Falling (TG2 Disabled) V_{ITH} Rising (TG2 Enabled)	●	0	2	6	mV
I _{LIMIT}	Inductor Current Limit Programming	$V_{LIMIT} = 0.5V$; $V_{LIMIT}/V_{SENS(MAX)}$			20		V/V
	I _{LIMIT} Pin Bias Current		●	47.5	50	52.5	μA
I _{TH}	Error Amp Current Limit	$V_{FBMAX} = 0$, $V_{ITH} = 1.3V$			8		μA
	Error Amp Transconductance	$V_{FBMAX} = 2.75V$; $V_{ITH} = 1.3V$			95		umho
V _C	High Side Current Sense Transconductance	$(V_{SENSEVIN} - V_{SENSETOP})$ to I_{VC} $V_C = 1.8V$			200		umho
	Low Side Current Sense Transconductance	$(V_{SENSEGND} - V_{SENSEBOT})$ to I_{VC} $V_C = 1.8V$			200		umho
DC _{MAX}	Maximum Duty Cycle	BG2: $t_{ON} \cdot f_0$	●	70	80		%
f ₀	Switching Frequency	$R_{RT} = 100k$ $R_{RT} = 50k$ $R_{RT} = 250k$	●	235	250	265	kHz
t _{ON}	Minimum On Time	BG2	●		150	250	ns
t _{OFF}	Minimum Off Time	TG1	●		300	500	ns
t _{TR}	Gate Drive Transition Time	TG1, BG1, TG2, BG2			5		ns
t _{NOL}	Gate Drive Non-Overlap time	(TG1 – SW1) to BG1, (TG2 – SW2) to BG2			75		ns

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ELECTRICAL CHARACTERISTICS The ● denotes the specifications which apply over the specified operating junction temperature range, otherwise specifications are at $T_A = 25^\circ\text{C}$ (Note 2). $PV_{IN} = \text{SENSVIN} = \text{CSP} = \text{CSN} = \text{BAT} = 20\text{V}$, $\text{SHDN} = 2\text{V}$, $C(\text{TG1, BG1, TG2, BG2}) = 1000\text{pF}$, $V_{\text{RNG/SS}} = 2\text{V}$.

SYMBOL	PARAMETER	CONDITIONS	MIN	TYP	MAX	UNITS	
Battery Charger							
V_{BAT}	Charger Output Voltage Range		●		55	V	
V_{FB}	Float Reference	CC/CV Charging (MODE = 0V)	●	2.4875 2.475	2.5 2.525	V V	
	Auto Recharge Voltage	% of Float Reference	●	96.5	97.5	98.5	%
	Precondition Threshold (Rising)	% of Float Reference	●	68	70	72	%
	Precondition Hysteresis				85	mV	
	Absorption Reference	Lead-Acid Charging (MODE = INTV _{CC})	●	2.4875 2.475	2.5 2.525	V V	
V_{FB}	Float Reference	% of Absorption Reference	●	91.5	92.5	93.5	%
	Bulk Charge Threshold (Falling)	% of Absorption Reference	●	86	87.5	89	%
	Precondition Threshold (Rising)		●	68	70	72	%
	Precondition Hysteresis				85	mV	
	Voltage Reference	CC Charging (MODE = - NC -)	●	2.4875 2.475	2.5 2.525	V V	
$V_{\text{IN_REG}}$	Input Regulation Reference	% of Float (CC/CV), Safety (CC), or Absorption (LA) Reference	●	98	100	102	%
V_{FBMIN}	Instant-On Reference	% of Float (CC/CV) or Absorption (LA) Reference	●	84	85	86	%
	C/10 Detection Enable (Rising) Hysteresis (Falling)			2.175 20		V mV	
	Instant-On Charge Current Reduction Threshold	$V_{\text{CSN}} - V_{\text{BAT}}$; Note 4			0.45	V	
	C/10 Detection Enable C/10 Detection Hysteresis	$V_{\text{CSN}} - V_{\text{BAT}}$ Falling $V_{\text{CSN}} - V_{\text{BAT}}$ Rising			1.05 150	V mV	
	Charge Current Reduction Gain	$\Delta V_{\text{CS(MAX)}} / \Delta(V_{\text{CSN}} - V_{\text{BAT}})$; Note 4			-33	mV/V	
I_{BATQ}	Battery Bias Currents with PowerPath Switcher Disabled	$I_{\text{CSP}} + I_{\text{CSN}} + I_{\text{BAT}}$	●		9	18	μA
CSN, CSP	Charger Current Sense Pin Operating Bias Currents	$I_{\text{CSP}} = I_{\text{CSN}}$; Charging Enabled			40	μA	
	Charger Current Sense Limit Voltage	$V_{\text{CSP}} - V_{\text{CSN}}$	●	47.5	50	52.5	mV
	Charger Current Sense Termination Voltage (C/10)	$V_{\text{CSP}} - V_{\text{CSN}}$; MODE = 0V	●	3	5	7	mV
	Charger Current Sense Precondition Voltage	$V_{\text{CSP}} - V_{\text{CSN}}$; $V_{\text{FB}} = 1.5$	●	1.5	3	4.5	mV
	Sense Input UVLO UVLO Hysteresis	V_{CSP} Rising (Charging Enabled) V_{CSP} Falling (Charging Disabled)	●	1.6	1.75 100	1.9	V mV
CSOUT	Offset	$V_{\text{CSP}} = V_{\text{CSN}}$	●	0.225	0.25	0.290	V
	Gain	$\Delta V_{\text{CSOUT}} / \Delta(V_{\text{CSP}} - V_{\text{CSN}})$	●	19	20	21	V/V
RNG/SS	Current Limit Programming	$V_{\text{RNG/SS}} = 0.5\text{V}$; $V_{\text{RNG/SS}} / V_{\text{CS(MAX)}}$	●	18	20	22	V/V
NTC	NTC Range Limit (High)	V_{NTC} Rising	●	1.30	1.35	1.40	V
	NTC Range Limit (Low)	V_{NTC} Falling	●	0.27	0.3	0.33	V
	NTC Range Hysteresis	% of $V_{\text{NTC(H,L)}}$			20	%	
I_{NTC}	NTC Pin Bias Current	$V_{\text{NTC}} = 0.8\text{V}$	●	47.5	50	52.5	μA
	NTC Disable Current	INTC Pin Current (Falling)			3.5	μA	
	NTC Disable Current Hysteresis				2	μA	
V_{BGATE}	Gate Clamp Voltage	$V_{\text{CSN}} - V_{\text{BGATE}}$	●	7	9.5	12	V
	C/10 Detection Enable (Falling) C/10 Detection Enable Hysteresis	$V_{\text{CSN}} < 7\text{V}$			0.425 0.125	V V	

4020td

ELECTRICAL CHARACTERISTICS The ● denotes the specifications which apply over the specified operating junction temperature range, otherwise specifications are at $T_A = 25^\circ\text{C}$ (Note 2). $PV_{IN} = \text{SENSVIN} = \text{CSP} = \text{CSN} = \text{BAT} = 20\text{V}$, $\text{SHDN} = 2\text{V}$, $C(\text{TG1}, \text{BG1}, \text{TG2}, \text{BG2}) = 1000\text{pF}$, $V_{\text{RNG/SS}} = 2\text{V}$.

SYMBOL	PARAMETER	CONDITIONS	MIN	TYP	MAX	UNITS	
BGATE	BGATE Pull-Down Current	Charging Enabled		15		μA	
	BGATE Pull-Up Current	Charging Disabled; $V_{\text{CSN}} - V_{\text{BGATE}} = 2\text{V}$		15		μA	
	BGATE Standby Pull-Down Current	$V_{\text{SHDN}} = 0\text{V}$		120		μA	
	Ideal Diode Pull-Down Current	Charging Disabled; $V_{\text{BAT}} - V_{\text{CSN}} = 0.5\text{V}$		500		μA	
	Ideal Diode Forward Voltage	$V_{\text{BAT}} - V_{\text{CSN}}$; V_{CSN} Measured Through 100Ω Series Resistor	●	5	14	20	mV
TIMER	Timer High Threshold			1.5		V	
	Timer Low Threshold			1.0		V	
	C/10 Mode Threshold (Rising)		●	0.4	0.5	0.6	V
	C/10 Mode Hysteresis			225		mV	
	Timer Source/Sink Current	$V_{\text{TIMER}} = 1.25\text{V}$	●	8.5	10	11.5	μA
$V_{\text{STAT(L)}}$	Status Pins Enabled Voltage	$I_{\text{STAT1}} = 1\text{mA}$; $I_{\text{STAT2}} = 1\text{mA}$	●	0.15	0.4	V	
		$I_{\text{STAT1}} = 5\text{mA}$; $I_{\text{STAT2}} = 5\text{mA}$	●	0.75	2.5	V	
I_{VFBMIN}	Instant-On Feedback Bias Current			10		nA	
I_{VFB}	Feedback Pin Bias Current			10		nA	
$I_{\text{VIN_REG}}$	Input Regulation Bias Current			10		nA	
I_{FBG}	Pin Current (Disabled)	$V_{\text{SHDN}} = 0\text{V}$; $V_{\text{FBG}} = 55\text{V}$		10		nA	
R_{NTC}	NTC Minimum Disable Resistance		●	250	400	$\text{k}\Omega$	
R_{FBG}	FBG Resistance to SGND	$I_{\text{FBG}} = 1\text{mA}$	●	20	50	Ω	

Note 1: Stresses beyond those listed under Absolute Maximum Ratings may cause permanent damage to the device. Exposure to any Absolute Maximum Rating condition for extended periods may affect device reliability and lifetime.

Note 2: The LTC4020 is tested under pulsed load conditions such that $T_J \approx T_A$. The LTC4020E is guaranteed to meet specifications from 0°C to 85°C junction temperature. Specifications over the -40°C to 125°C operating junction temperature range are assured by design, characterization, and correlation with statistical process controls. The LTC4020I is guaranteed over the full -40°C to 125°C operating junction temperature range. The junction temperature (T_J) is calculated from the ambient temperature (T_A) and power dissipation (PD) according

to the formula $T_J = T_A + (\text{PD} \cdot \theta_{JA})$. Note that the maximum ambient temperature consistent with these specifications is determined by specific operating conditions in conjunction with board layout, the rated package thermal resistance and other environmental factors. This IC includes overtemperature protection that is intended to protect the device during momentary overload. Junction temperature will exceed 125°C when overtemperature protection is active. Continuous operation above the specified maximum operating junction temperature may impair device reliability.

Note 3: ICC does not include switching currents. $V_{\text{BST1}} = V_{\text{BST2}} = V_{\text{INTVCC}}$ and $V_{\text{SW1}} = V_{\text{SW2}} = 0\text{V}$ for testing.

Note 4: See Typical Performance Characteristics

TYPICAL PERFORMANCE CHARACTERISTICS $T_A = 25^\circ\text{C}$, unless otherwise noted.

$V_{\text{FLOAT(CC/CV)}}$ or, $V_{\text{ABSORB(Lead-Acid)}}$ Reference vs Temperature

$V_{\text{FLOAT(Lead-Acid)}}$ Reference vs Temperature

V_{FBMAX} Reference vs Temperature

Shutdown Current vs Temperature ($I_{\text{PVIN}} + I_{\text{SENSVIN}} + I_{\text{SENSTOP}}$)

$I_{\text{NTV}_{\text{CC}}}$ Short-Circuit Current Limit vs Temperature

Maximum Charge Current (Percent of Programmed I_{CSMAX}) vs RNG/SS Voltage

Instant-On: Maximum Charge Current (Percent of I_{CSMAX}) vs $V_{\text{CSN-BAT}}$

I_{BATQ} ($I_{\text{BAT}} + I_{\text{CSN}} + I_{\text{CSP}}$) vs V_{BAT} PowerPath Switcher Disabled

I_{BATQ} ($I_{\text{BAT}} + I_{\text{CSN}} + I_{\text{CSP}}$) vs Temperature PowerPath Switcher Disabled

TYPICAL PERFORMANCE CHARACTERISTICS $T_A = 25^\circ\text{C}$, unless otherwise noted.

PIN FUNCTIONS

TG1 (Pin 1): V_{IN} side (step-down) primary switch FET gate driver output.

BST1 (Pin 2): Boosted supply rail for V_{IN} side (step-down) switch FETs. Connect 1 μ F capacitor from this pin to SW1. Connect 1A Schottky diode cathode to this pin, anode to INTV_{CC} pin.

SENSGND (Pin 4): Kelvin connection for PGND used for SENS_{BOT} current sense reference.

SENSBOT (Pin 5): Ground Referred Current Sense Amplifier Input. Inductor current is monitored via a PGND referenced current sense resistor (R_{SENSEB}), typically in series with the source of the V_{IN} side synchronous switch FET. Kelvin connect this pin to the associated sense resistor. Inductor current is limited to a maximum average value (I_{LMAX}), and corresponds to 50mV across this sense resistor during normal operation.

$$R_{SENSEB} = 0.05/I_{LMAX}$$

Set $R_{SENSEB} = R_{SENSEA}$, as described in SENSTOP pin description. A filter capacitor (C_{SENSB}) is typically connected from SENS_{BOT} to SENSGND for noise reduction.

$$C_{SENSB} \sim 1nS/R_{SENSEB}$$

See Applications Information section.

SENSTOP (Pin 6): V_{IN} Referred Current Sense Amplifier Input. Inductor current is monitored via a V_{IN} referenced current sense resistor (R_{SENSEA}), typically in series with the drain of the V_{IN} side primary switch FET. Kelvin connect this pin to the associated sense resistor. Inductor current is limited to a maximum average value (I_{LMAX}), and corresponds to 50mV across this sense resistor during normal operation.

$$R_{SENSEA} = 0.05/I_{LMAX}$$

Set $R_{SENSEA} = R_{SENSEB}$, as described in SENS_{BOT} pin description.

SENSVIN (Pin 7): Kelvin connection for input supply (V_{IN}) used for SENSTOP current sense reference. Input power supply pin for most internal low current functions. Typical pin bias current is 0.25mA.

RT (Pin 8): System Oscillator Frequency Control Pin. Connect resistor (R_{RT}) from this pin to ground. Resistor

value can range from 50k Ω (500kHz) to 500k Ω (50kHz). $R_{RT} = 100k\Omega$ yields 250kHz operating frequency. See Applications Information.

SHDN (Pin 9): Precision Threshold Shutdown Pin. Enable threshold is 1.225V (rising), with 100mV of input hysteresis. When in shutdown, all charging functions are disabled and input supply current is reduced to 27.5 μ A. Typical SHDN pin input bias current is 10nA.

V_{IN_REG} (Pin 10): Input Voltage Regulation Reference. Battery charge current is reduced when the voltage on this pin falls below 2.5V. Connecting a resistor divider from V_{IN} to this pin enables programming of minimum operational V_{IN} voltage for the battery charging function. This is used to program the peak power voltage for a solar panel, or to help maintain a minimum voltage on a poorly regulated input supply. This pin should not be used to program minimum operational V_{IN} voltage with low impedance supplies. Should the input supply begin to collapse, the LTC4020 reduces the DC/DC converter input power such that programmed minimum V_{IN} operational voltage is maintained. If the voltage regulation feature is not used, connect the V_{IN_REG} pin to V_{IN} or INTV_{CC}. Typical V_{IN_REG} pin input bias current is 10nA. See Applications Information.

MODE (Pin 11): Charger Mode Control Pin. Short this pin to ground to enable a constant-current/constant-voltage (CC/CV) charging algorithm. Connect this pin to pin INTV_{CC} to enable a 4-step, 3-stage lead-acid charging algorithm. Float this pin to force a constant-current (CC) charging function. See Applications Information section.

STAT1 (Pin 12): Open-collector status output, typically pulled up through a resistor to a supply voltage. This status pin can be pulled up to voltages as high as 55V when the pin is disabled, and can sink currents up to 1mA when logic low (<0.4V). Pull down currents as high as 5mA (absolute maximum) are supported for higher current applications, such as lighting LEDs.

If the LTC4020 is configured for a CC/CV charging algorithm, the STAT1 pin is pulled low while battery charge currents exceed 10% of the programmed maximum (C/10). The STAT1 pin is also pulled low during NTC faults. The STAT1 pin becomes high impedance when a charge cycle

PIN FUNCTIONS

is terminated or when charge current is below the C/10 threshold.

If the LTC4020 is configured for a CC charging algorithm, the STAT1 pin is pulled low during the entire charging cycle. The STAT1 pin becomes high impedance when the charge cycle is terminated.

If the LTC4020 is configured for a lead-acid charging algorithm, the STAT1 pin is used as a charge cycle stage indicator pin, and pulled low during the bulk and absorption charging stages. The pin is high impedance during the float charging period and during NTC or bad battery faults.

See Applications Information section.

STAT2 (Pin 13): Open-collector status output, typically pulled up through a resistor to a supply voltage. This status pin can be pulled up to voltages as high as 55V when disabled, and can sink currents up to 1mA when enabled (<0.4V). Pull down currents as high as 5mA (absolute maximum) are supported for higher current applications, such as lighting LEDs.

If the LTC4020 is configured for a CC/CV charging algorithms, the STAT2 pin is pulled low during NTC faults or after a bad battery fault occurs.

If the LTC4020 is configured for a CC charging algorithms, the STAT2 pin is pulled low during NTC faults.

If the LTC4020 is configured for a lead-acid charging algorithm, the STAT2 pin is used as a charge cycle stage indicator pin, and pulled low during the bulk and float charging stages. The pin is high impedance during the absorption charging stage and during NTC or bad battery faults.

See Applications Information section.

TIMER (Pin 14): End-Of-Cycle Timer Programming Pin. If a timer based charging algorithm is desired, connect a capacitor (C_{TIMER}) from this pin to ground. If no timer functions are desired, connect this pin to ground.

End-of-cycle time (in hours) is programmed with the value of C_{TIMER} following the equation:

$$T_{\text{EOC}} = C_{\text{TIMER}} \cdot 1.46 \times 10^7;$$

During CC/CV or lead-acid charging algorithms, a bad battery fault is generated if the battery voltage does not reach the precondition threshold voltage within 1/8 of T_{EOC} , or:

$$T_{\text{PRE}} = C_{\text{TIMER}} \cdot 1.82 \times 10^6.$$

A 0.2 μ F capacitor is typically used for CC/CV charging, which generates a 2.9 hour timer T_{EOC} , and a precondition limit time of 22 minutes. A 0.47 μ F capacitor is typically used for a lead-acid charger, which generates a 6.8 hour absorption stage safety timeout.

RNG/SS (Pin 15): Battery Charge Current Programming Pin. This pin allows dynamic adjustment of maximum charge current, and can be used to employ a soft-start function.

Setting the voltage on the RNG/SS pin reduces maximum charge current from the value programmed. The maximum charge current is reduced to the fraction of programmed current (as per the sense resistor, RCS) corresponding to the voltage set on the pin (in volts). This pin has an effective range from 0 to 1V.

For example, with 0.5V RNG/SS on the pin, the maximum charge current will be reduced to 50% of the programmed value set by the sense resistor values.

50 μ A is sourced from the RNG/SS pin, so maximum charge current can be programmed by connecting a single resistor ($R_{\text{RNG/SS}}$) from RNG/SS to ground, such that the voltage dropped across the resistor is equivalent to the desired pin voltage:

$$V_{\text{RNG/SS}} = 50\mu\text{A} \cdot R_{\text{RNG/SS}}$$

Soft-start functionality can be implemented by connecting a capacitor ($C_{\text{RNG/SS}}$) from RNG/SS to ground, such that the time required to charge the capacitor is the desired soft-start interval (T_{SS1}). The voltage that corresponds to full programmed inductor current on the RNG/SS pin is 1V, so the relation for this capacitor reduces to:

$$C_{\text{RNG/SS}} = 50\mu\text{A} \cdot T_{\text{SS1}}$$

PIN FUNCTIONS

The RNG/SS pin is pulled low during periods when charging is disabled, including NTC faults, bad battery faults, and normal charge cycle termination. This allows for a graceful start after faults and when initiating new charge cycles, should soft-start functionality be implemented.

Both a soft-start capacitor and a programming resistor can be implemented in parallel.

RNG/SS voltage can also be manipulated using an active device, such as employing a pull-down transistor to disable charge current or to dynamically servo maximum charging current. Because this pin is internally pulled to ground during fault conditions, active devices with low-impedance pull up capability cannot be used.

See Applications Information section.

NTC (Pin 16): Battery Temperature Monitor Pin. Connect a 10k Ω , $\beta = 3380$ NTC thermistor from this pin to ground.

The NTC pin is the input to the negative temperature coefficient temperature monitoring circuit. This pin sources 50 μ A, and monitors the voltage created across the 10k Ω thermistor. When the voltage on this pin is above 1.35V (0 $^{\circ}$ C) or below 0.3V (40 $^{\circ}$ C), charging is disabled and an NTC fault is signaled at the STAT1 and STAT2 status pins. If the internal timer is being used, the timer is paused, suspending the charging cycle until the NTC fault condition is relieved. There is approximately 5 $^{\circ}$ C of temperature hysteresis associated with each of the temperature thresholds. The NTC function remains enabled while thermistor resistance to ground is less than 250k Ω . If this function is not desired, leave the NTC pin unconnected or connect a 10k resistor from the NTC pin to ground. The NTC pin contains an internal clamp that prevents excursions above 2V, so the pin must not be pulled high with a low impedance source. A low impedance element can be used to pull the pin to ground.

VFB (Pin 17): Battery Voltage Feedback Pin. Battery voltages are programmed through a feedback resistor divider placed from the BAT pin to FBG.

During CC/CV charging, the battery voltage references are:

$$\text{Float Voltage (V}_{\text{FLOAT}}) = 2.5\text{V}$$

$$\text{Trickle Charge Voltage (V}_{\text{TRK}}) = 1.75\text{V}$$

$$\text{Auto-Restart Voltage (V}_{\text{RESTART}}) = 2.4375$$

During lead-acid charging, the battery voltage references are:

$$\text{Absorption Voltage (V}_{\text{ABSOR}}) = 2.5\text{V}$$

$$\text{Float Charge Voltage (V}_{\text{FLT}}) = 2.3125\text{V}$$

$$\text{Trickle Charge Voltage (V}_{\text{TRK}}) = 1.75\text{V}$$

$$\text{Bulk Recharge Voltage (V}_{\text{BULK}}) = 2.1875\text{V}$$

With R_{FB1} connected from BAT to VFB and R_{FB2} connected from VFB to FBG, the ratio of (R_{FB1}/R_{FB2}) for the desired programmed battery float voltage (CC/CV charging) or absorption voltage (lead-acid charging) follows the relation:

$$R_{\text{FB1}}/R_{\text{FB2}} = (\text{V}_{\text{FLOAT/ABSORB}})/2.5 - 1 \quad (\text{V})$$

FBG (Pin 18): Voltage Feedback Divider Return. This pin contains a low impedance path to signal ground, used as the ground reference for voltage monitoring feedback resistor dividers. When V_{IN} is not present or the LTC4020 is in shutdown, this pin becomes high impedance, eliminating current drain from the battery associated with the feedback resistor dividers.

V_{FMIN} (Pin 19): Minimum voltage feedback pin for instant-on operation. Minimum DC/DC converter output voltage (V_{OUTMIN}) is programmed using this pin for instant-on functionality. V_{OUTMIN} is programmed through a feedback resistor divider placed from the CSP pin to FBG.

If the battery voltage is below the voltage level programmed using this pin, the LTC4020 controls the external PowerPath FET as a linear pass element, allowing the DC/DC converter output to achieve the minimum programmed voltage. Maximum battery charge current is reduced as the voltage across the PowerPath FET increases to control power dissipation.

The internal V_{FMIN} voltage reference is 2.125V. With a resistor (R_{MIN1}) connected from CSP to V_{FMIN}, and a resistor (R_{MIN2}) connected from V_{FMIN} to FBG, the ratio of these resistors for the desired minimum converter output voltage follows the relation:

$$R_{\text{MIN1}}/R_{\text{MIN2}} = (\text{V}_{\text{OUT(MIN)}}/2.125) - 1$$

PIN FUNCTIONS

Using the same resistor values for battery voltage programming, or $R_{FB1} = R_{MIN1}$ and $R_{FB2} = R_{MIN2}$, yields an instant-on voltage that is 85% of V_{FLOAT} (CC/CV charging) or V_{ABSORB} (lead-acid charging):

$$V_{OUT(MIN)} = 0.85 \cdot V_{FLOAT/ABSORB}$$

BAT (Pin 20): Battery Voltage Monitor Pin. This pin serves as the positive reference for the LTC4020 ideal diode function.

If a system load occurs that is large enough to collapse the DC/DC converter output while charging is terminated or disabled, and the battery is disconnected (PowerPath FET is high impedance), the ideal diode function engages the PowerPath. This function powers the system load from the battery, and modulates the PowerPath FET gate such that the system output voltage is maintained with 14mV across the PowerPath FET, provided the voltage drop due to $R_{DS(ON)} < 14mV$. This allows large loads to be accommodated without excessive power dissipation in the body diode of the PowerPath FET.

BGATE (Pin 21): PowerPath FET Gate Driver Output.

This pin is controls the multiple functions of the PowerPath FET.

This pin is pulled low during a normal charging cycle, minimizing the FET series impedance between the DC/DC converter output and the battery.

The BGATE pin is also forced low when the DC/DC converter is disabled, maintaining a low impedance connection to power the system from the battery.

When BGATE is pulled low, CSP BGATE is limited internally to 9.5V, so if $CSP > 9.5V$, BGATE is maintained by an internal clamp at $CSP - BGATE = 9.5V$. The BGATE pin must be near ground or at the clamp voltage for C/10 detection to occur.

If the battery voltage is lower than the instant-on threshold (see V_{FBMIN}), BGATE servos the PowerPath FET impedance such that a voltage drop between the CSN pin and the BAT pin is created while battery charging continues. If the $V_{CSN} - V_{BAT}$ voltage exceeds 0.4V, maximum charge current is reduced to decrease power dissipation in the PowerPath FET.

When the DC/DC converter is enabled, but the battery charge cycle has terminated, BGATE is pulled high to disconnect the battery from the converter output. The battery is also disconnected in the same manner during NTC faults. The ideal diode function is active during these periods, however, so if a system load occurs that is larger than what the DC/DC converter can accommodate, the battery can supply the required current, and the BGATE pin will be servo controlled to force a voltage drop of only 14mV across the PowerPath FET. The ideal diode function is disabled during bad battery faults.

If a PowerPath FET is not being used, such as with a lead-acid charging application, connect a 0.1nF capacitor from BGATE to CSN.

CSN (Pin 22): Battery Charger Current Sense Negative Input. Connect this pin to the negative terminal of the battery charge current sense resistor (R_{CS}) through a 100 Ω resistor. Connect a filter capacitor between this pin and the CSP pin for ripple reduction. See Applications Information section.

The value of the sense resistor is related to the maximum battery charge current (I_{CSMAX}):

$$R_{CS} = 0.05/I_{CSMAX}$$

This pin also serves as the negative reference for the LTC4020 ideal diode function (see BAT).

CSP (Pin 23): Battery Charger Current Sense Positive Input. Connect this pin to the positive terminal of the battery charge current sense resistor (R_{CS}) through a 100 Ω resistor. Connect a filter capacitor between this pin and the CSN pin for ripple reduction. See Applications Information section.

The value of the sense resistor is related to the maximum battery charge current (I_{CSMAX}) such that:

$$R_{CS} = 0.05/I_{CSMAX}$$

CSOUT (Pin 24): Current Sense Amplifier Output and Charge Current Monitor. Connect 100pF capacitor to ground.

PIN FUNCTIONS

Pin output impedance is 100kΩ, so any loading for monitors must be high impedance. The sense output voltage follows the relation:

$$V_{CSOUT} = 0.25 + 20 \cdot (V_{CSP} - V_{CSN})$$

CSOUT is only active while battery charger functions are operating. CSOUT pin voltage is pulled to 0V after charge cycle termination or during fault conditions.

I_{LIMIT} (Pin 25): Switched Inductor Maximum Current Programming Pin. This pin allows dynamic adjustment of DC/DC converter maximum average inductor current, and can be used to employ a soft-start function.

Setting the voltage on the I_{LIMIT} pin reduces maximum average inductor current from the value programmed. The inductor current limit is reduced to the fraction of programmed current (as per the sense resistors) corresponding to the voltage set on the pin (in volts). This pin has an effective range from 0 to 1V.

For example, with 0.5V on the pin, the maximum inductor current will be reduced to 50% of the programmed value set by the sense resistor values.

50μA is sourced from this pin, so maximum inductor current can be programmed by connecting a single resistor (R_{ILIMIT}) from I_{LIMIT} to ground, such that the voltage dropped across the resistor is equivalent to the desired pin voltage:

$$V_{ILIMIT} = 50\mu A \cdot R_{ILIMIT}$$

Soft-start functionality can be implemented by connecting a capacitor (C_{ILIMIT}) from I_{LIMIT} to ground, such that the time required to charge the capacitor is the desired soft-start interval (T_{SS2}). The voltage that corresponds to full inductor current on the I_{LIMIT} pin is 1V, so the relation for this capacitor reduces to:

$$C_{ILIMIT} = 50\mu A \cdot T_{SS2}$$

I_{LIMIT} voltage can also be manipulated using an active device, such as employing a pull-down transistor to disable DC/DC converter current or to dynamically servo maximum current. Because this pin is internally pulled to

ground during portions of the converter power-up cycle, active devices with low impedance pull-up capability cannot be used.

V_{FBMAX} (Pin 26): DC/DC Converter Output Feedback Pin. Maximum DC/DC converter output voltage (V_{OUTMAX}) is programmed using this pin. When a battery charge cycle is terminated or disabled, and the battery is disconnected (PowerPath FET is high impedance), the converter output will servo to this maximum voltage.

The internal V_{FBMAX} voltage reference is 2.75V. With a resistor (R_{MAX1}) connected from CSP to V_{FBMAX} and a resistor (R_{MAX2}) connected from V_{FBMAX} to FBG, the ratio of R_{MAX1}/R_{MAX2} for the desired maximum DC/DC converter output voltage follows the relation:

$$R_{MAX1}/R_{MAX2} = (V_{OUTMAX}/2.75) - 1$$

Using the same resistor values for battery voltage programming, or R_{FB1} = R_{MAX1} and R_{FB2} = R_{MAX2}, yields an instant-on voltage that is 110% of V_{FLOAT} (CC/CV charging) or V_{ABSORB} (lead-acid charging):

$$V_{OUTMAX} = 1.1 \cdot V_{FLOAT}/ABSORB$$

ITH (Pin 27): DC/DC Converter Voltage Loop Compensation Pin. See Applications Information section for compensation component selection details.

VC (Pin 28): DC/DC Converter Current Loop Compensation Pin. See Applications Information section for compensation component selection details.

BST2 (Pin 30): Boosted supply rail for V_{OUT} side (step-up) switch FETs. Connect a 1μF capacitor from this pin to SW2. Connect a 1A Schottky diode cathode to this pin, anode to INTV_{CC} pin.

TG2 (Pin 31): V_{OUT} side (step-up) synchronous switch FET gate driver output.

SW2 (Pin 32): Switched node for step-up switches. Connect the switched inductor to this pin. Connect the primary switch FET drain and synchronous switch FET source to this pin.

PIN FUNCTIONS

BG2 (Pin 33): V_{OUT} side (step-up) primary switch FET gate driver output.

INTVCC (Pin 34): Boosted Driver Refresh Supply. This supply is regulated to 5V and is current limited to 150mA. Connect a 2.2 μ F ceramic capacitor from this pin to PGND. Boosted supply refresh diode anodes are connected to this pin. Using this pin to power external 5V circuitry is not recommended.

PGND (Pin 35): Switch high current return path for step-up primary and step-down synchronous switches.

PVIN (Pin 36): High Current Input Supply Pin. Connect 10 μ F decoupling capacitor from this pin to PGND. The PV_{IN} pin provides input supply current for the INTV_{CC} internal 5V linear regulator.

BG1 (Pin 37): V_{IN} side (step-down) synchronous switch FET gate driver output.

SW1 (Pin 38): Switched node for step-down switches. Connect the switched inductor to this pin. Connect the primary switch FET source and synchronous switch FET drain to this pin.

SGND (Pins 3, 29, Exposed Pad 39): Signal Ground Reference. Connect to the output decoupling capacitor negative terminal and battery negative terminal. The exposed pad (39) must be soldered to PCB ground (SGND) for electrical connection and rated thermal performance.

BLOCK DIAGRAM

DC/DC Controller Block Diagram

BLOCK DIAGRAM

Battery Charger Block Diagram

OPERATION

Functional Overview

The LTC4020 is an advanced high voltage power manager and multi-chemistry battery charger designed to efficiently transfer power from a variety of sources to a system power supply rail and a battery.

The LTC4020 contains a step-up/step-down DC/DC controller that allows operation with battery and system voltages that are above, below, or equal to the input voltage (V_{IN}). A precision threshold shutdown feature allows incorporation of input voltage UVLO functionality using a simple resistor divider. When in low current shutdown mode, the IC input supply bias is reduced to only 27.5 μ A.

The LTC4020 charger is programmable to produce optimized charging profiles for a variety of battery chemistries. The LTC4020 can provide a constant-current/constant-voltage charge characteristic with either C/10 or timed termination for use with lithium based battery systems, a constant-current characteristic with timed termination, or an optimized 4-step, 3-stage lead-acid charge profile.

Maximum battery charge current is programmable using a sense resistor, and a charge current range adjust pin allows dynamic adjustment of maximum charge current. A switcher core current limit adjust pin also allows dynamic limiting of power available to the system by virtue of limiting maximum current in the DC/DC converter inductor.

The LTC4020 preconditions heavily discharged batteries by reducing charge current to one-fifteenth of the programmed maximum. Once the battery voltage climbs above an internally set threshold, the IC automatically increases maximum charging current to the full programmed value. A bad battery detection function signals a fault and suspends charging should a battery not respond to preconditioning.

Battery temperature is monitored using a thermistor measurement system. This feature monitors battery temperature during the charging cycle, suspending the charge cycle and signaling a fault condition if the battery temperature moves outside a safe charging range of 0°C to 40°C. The charge cycle automatically resumes when the temperature returns to that safe charging range.

Instant-on PowerPath architecture ensures that an application is powered immediately after an external voltage is applied, even with a completely dead battery, by prioritizing power to the application. Since the controller output (V_{OUT}) and the battery (BAT) are sometimes decoupled, the LTC4020 includes an ideal diode controller, which guarantees that ample power is always available to V_{OUT} if there is insufficient power available from the DC/DC converter. Should there be no input power available (V_{IN}), the LTC4020 makes a low impedance connection from the battery to V_{OUT} through the PowerPath FET. Battery life is maximized during periods of input supply disconnect by reducing the LTC4020 battery standby current to less than 10 μ A.

The LTC4020 contains two digital open-collector outputs that provide charger status and signal fault conditions. These binary coded pins signal battery charging, standby or shutdown modes, battery temperature faults, and bad battery faults.

DC/DC Converter Operation (See Block Diagrams)

The LTC4020 uses a proprietary average current mode DC/DC converter architecture.

As shown in Figure 1, when V_{IN} is higher than V_{OUT} during step-down (buck) operation, switches A (driven by pin TG1) and B (driven by pin BG1) perform the PWM required for accommodating power conversion. Ideally, switch D (driven by pin TG2) would conduct continuously and switch C (driven by pin BG2) would stay off, making PWM switching action much like that in a synchronous buck topology. Switch D uses a bootstrapped driver, however, so switch C conducts for a minimum on time of 150nS each cycle to refresh the driver and switch D is disabled to accommodate this refresh time. A 75ns non-overlap period, separates the conduction of the two switches, preventing shoot-through currents.

When V_{IN} is lower than V_{OUT} during step-up (boost) operation, switches C and D perform the PWM required for accommodating power conversion. Ideally, switch A would conduct continuously and switch B would stay off, making

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PWM switching action much like that in a synchronous boost topology. Since switch A also uses a bootstrapped drive, however, the B switch conducts for 100ns during this refresh period. A 75ns non-overlap period, separates the conduction of the two switches, preventing shoot-through currents.

If V_{IN} is close to V_{OUT} , the controller operates in 4-switch (buck-boost) mode, where both switch pairs PWM simultaneously to accommodate conversion requirements.

The LTC4020 senses the DC/DC converter output voltage using a resistor divider feedback network that drives the V_{FBMAX} pin. The difference between the voltage on the V_{FBMAX} pin and an internal 2.75V reference is converted into an error current by the voltage loop transconductance amplifier (EA-V). This error current is integrated by a compensation network to produce a voltage on pin ITH. The ITH compensation network is designed to optimize the response of the converter to changes in load current while the converter is in regulation. At regulation, the ITH pin will servo to a value that corresponds to the average inductor current of the DC/DC converter.

Inductor current is monitored through two like value sense resistors, placed in series with each of the V_{IN} side converter switches, A and B. The sum of these sensed currents yields a reasonably accurate continuous representation of inductor current.

The voltage produced on the ITH pin is translated into an offset at the input of the two current sense amplifiers. The difference between this offset voltage and the sum of the voltages is sensed on the SENSTOP and SENSBOT pins, then is converted to error currents by the current sense transconductance amplifiers (EA- C_A and EA- C_B). These error currents are summed and integrated by a compensation network to produce a voltage on the pin VC. This compensation network is designed to optimize the response of the converter duty cycle to required changes in inductor current.

The VC pin voltage is compared to an internally generated ramp, and the output of this comparison controls the duty cycle of the charger's switches.

Figure 1 shows a simplified diagram of the four power switches and their connections to the IC, inductor, V_{IN} , V_{OUT} , ground, and current sense elements.

Figure 1. Converter Switch Diagram

Figure 2. Operating Regions vs Duty Cycle (DC)

Reverse current protection is accomplished through disabling the V_{OUT} side synchronous switch (D) during initial power-up, when the converter is in step-up duty cycle limit, and when ITH falls to a voltage that corresponds to $<1/25$ of programmed I_{LMAX} . Once these conditions subside, the D switch remains disabled for an additional 128 clock cycles.

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Battery Charger Operation (See Block Diagrams)

During the majority of a normal battery charge cycle, the LTC4020 makes a low impedance connection between the battery and the DC/DC converter output through the PowerPath FET, as in Figure 3. This PFET is controlled by the LTC4020 through modulation of the BGATE pin, which is connected to the FET gate. When charging is disabled, the FET is disabled, disconnecting the battery from the converter output by pulling the gate of the PowerPath FET high via the BGATE pin. The converter output is regulated by V_{FBMAX} while the FET is disabled. When normal charger operation resumes, the gate is pulled low. As the BGATE pin is a slow-moving node, C/10 detection is disabled until the BGATE pin approaches its normal operating voltage, which prevents premature C/10 detection during reconnection of the battery. The slow movement of BGATE can also cause the converter output to regulate to V_{FBMAX} for a short time during start-up until the FET is enabled. This FET is also linearly controlled during low battery conditions to enable the instant-on function, where the converter output can be separated from a heavily discharged battery to power the rest of the system before the battery voltage responds to charging. C/10 detection is also disabled when the charger is operating in instant-on mode. This FET is also automatically configured as a 14mV ideal diode, which provides a low loss path from the battery to the output when system loads require power from the battery while the battery is disconnected from the converter output.

Figure 3. Battery Charger PowerPath Diagram

The battery charger takes control of the DC/DC converter operation by modulating the ITH pin voltage in response to sensed battery charge current, battery voltage, and input voltage. The converter thus provides exactly the amount of power required to satisfy both the system load and battery charger requirements.

Battery charge current is monitored via an external sense resistor connected to the pins CSP and CSN. The voltage across this resistor is amplified internally by a factor of 20, which is output onto pin CSOUT. This output voltage rides on top of a constant 250mV offset. The CSOUT pin voltage drives an internal transconductance amplifier that servos the DC/DC converter's ITH pin voltage in response to the current requirements of a charging battery. CSOUT voltage is also used internally as a charge current monitor to detect <C/10 current thresholds.

Battery voltage is monitored via the VFB pin. This voltage drives a transconductance amplifier that servos the DC/DC converter ITH pin voltage in response to voltage developed on a charging battery. The transition from constant-current (CC) to constant-voltage (CV) charging modes is also detected using this transconductance amplifier. The VFB voltage is used for all battery voltage monitor thresholds, each being defined as a percentage of the internal 2.5V reference voltage.

Input voltage regulation is implemented via the V_{IN_REG} pin for use with poorly regulated or high impedance supplies. This pin drives a transconductance amplifier that reduces the ITH pin voltage in response to voltage sensed on the V_{IN_REG} pin falling through 2.5V. This transconductance amplifier remains active even while battery charging is disabled, so the input regulation feature continues to operate regardless of the state of a charge cycle.

The LTC4020 contains an internal charge cycle timer that is used for time based control of a charge cycle. This function is enabled by connecting a capacitor to the TIMER pin. Grounding this pin disables all timer functions. The timer is used to terminate a successful CC or CC/CV charge cycle after a programmed end-of-cycle (T_{EOC}) time. This timer is also used to transition a lead-acid charger to float charging if charge current does not fall adequately during the absorption phase of the charge cycle within the programmed T_{EOC} time.

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Use of the timer function also enables bad battery detection during CC/CV or lead-acid charging. This fault condition is achieved if the battery does not respond to preconditioning ($V_{FB} < 1.75V$), such that the charger remains in (or enters) precondition mode after one-eighth of the programmed T_{EOC} time. A bad battery fault halts the charging cycle, and the fault condition is reported on the status pins.

CC/CV Charging Overview (MODE = 0V)

To program the LTC4020 for CC/CV charging, connect the MODE pin to ground. This mode is commonly used for Li-Ion, Li-Polymer, and $LiFePO_4$ battery charging.

If the voltage on the VFB pin is below 1.75V, the LTC4020 engages precondition mode, which provides low level charge currents to gently increase voltage on heavily discharged batteries. During preconditioning, the maximum charge current is reduced to one-fifteenth of the programmed value as set by R_{CS} , the battery charge current programming resistor. Full charge current capability is restored once the voltage on VFB rises above 1.75V. Full charge current capability remains until the VFB pin approaches the 2.5V float voltage. This is the constant-current (CC) portion of the charge cycle.

When the voltage on the VFB pin approaches the 2.5V float voltage, the charger transitions into constant-voltage (CV) mode, and charge current is reduced from the maximum programmed value. If timer termination is used, the safety timer period starts when CV mode is initiated, and the charge cycle will terminate when the timer achieves end-of-cycle (T_{EOC}). This timer is typically programmed to achieve T_{EOC} in three hours, but can be configured for any amount of time by setting an appropriate timing capacitor value (C_{TIMER}).

During CV mode, the required charge current is steadily reduced as the battery voltage is maintained such that the voltage on the VFB pin remains close to 2.5V. If the charger is configured for C/10 termination, when the battery charge current falls below one-tenth of the programmed maximum current ($<C/10$), the charge cycle will terminate and the charger indicates not charging on the status pins.

When timer termination is used, the charger continues to operate with charging current less than one-tenth of the

programmed maximum current. The STAT1 status pin, however, responds to the $<C/10$ current level regardless of termination scheme, so the IC will indicate a not charging status when the charging current is below the C/10 current level. The charge cycle will continue, however, and the charger will source $<C/10$ current into the battery. Programmed float voltage is maintained while the charger tops-off the battery with low currents until the programmed T_{EOC} time has elapsed, at which time the charge cycle will terminate, charge current flow into the battery will be disabled, and the battery will be disconnected from the converter output.

After termination, if the battery discharges such that the voltage on the VFB pin drops to 2.4375V, or 97.5% of the programmed float voltage, a new charge cycle is automatically initiated.

	TYPICAL CC/CV CHARGE CYCLE VOLTAGES (PER CELL)	
	Li-Ion	LiFePO ₄
Precondition	2.94V	2.52V
Float	4.2V	3.6V
Recharge	4.095V	3.51V

Lead-Acid Charging Overview (MODE = INT_VCC)

To program the LTC4020 for lead-acid charging, connect the MODE pin to the $INTV_{CC}$ pin. The LTC4020 supports a 4-step, 3-stage lead-acid charging profile.

The first step of the charging profile provides low level charge current to gently increase voltage on heavily discharged batteries. If the voltage on VFB is below 1.75V, which corresponds to just over 10V for a 6-cell (12V) battery, the maximum charge current is reduced to one-fifteenth of the programmed value as set by R_{CS} . Once the VFB voltage rises above 1.75V, full charge current capability is restored, and the bulk charging stage begins.

The bulk charging stage of the charge profile, which is the first stage of 3-stage battery charging, is a constant-current charging stage, with the maximum programmed charge current forced into the battery. This continues until the battery voltage rises such that the VFB pin approaches the 2.5V absorption reference voltage.

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As the bulk charging stage completes and the voltage on the VFB pin rises to approach 2.5V, the charger transitions into the absorption stage, which is the 2nd stage of 3-stage battery charging. During the absorption stage, the required charge current is steadily reduced as the battery voltage approaches the absorption voltage. This is a constant-voltage charging stage, as the battery voltage is maintained such that the VFB pin remains close to the 2.5V absorption reference voltage. It is during this stage that the battery stored charge increases to 100% capacity. The 2.5V absorption reference typically corresponds to 14.4V for a 6-cell battery.

When the absorption stage charge current is reduced to one-tenth of the programmed maximum current, the charger will initiate the third stage in the charge profile, the float charging stage. The safety timer can be used with a lead-acid charger to limit the duration of the absorption stage of the charging profile. The timer is initiated at the start of the absorption stage, and forces the charger into float if the charge current does not fall to the required one-tenth of the programmed maximum current during the absorption stage before the timer reaches T_{EOC} . A 0.47 μ F capacitor on the TIMER pin is typically used, which generates a 6.8 hour absorption stage safety timeout.

Once the float charging stage is initiated, the battery reference voltage is reduced to 92.5% of the absorption voltage, or 2.3125V. The battery voltage is maintained at a voltage corresponding to this reference voltage, and maximum charge current is reduced to one-fifteenth of the programmed maximum. This level corresponds to 13.3V for a 6-cell battery.

Once float charging is achieved, the LTC4020 charger remains active and will attempt to maintain the float voltage on the battery indefinitely. During float charging, if a load on the battery exceeds the maintenance charge current of one-fifteenth of the programmed maximum, the battery voltage will begin to discharge. If a load discharges the battery such that the voltage on VFB falls to 2.1875V, corresponding to 12.6V for a 6-cell battery, the LTC4020 restarts the full 3-stage charging cycle by reinitiating the bulk charging stage. Bulk charging is engaged by resetting the internal VFB reference to the 2.5V absorption voltage

reference and increasing the charge current capability to the programmed maximum.

	TYPICAL LEAD-ACID CHARGE CYCLE VOLTAGES (12V System)
Precondition	10.1V
Absorption	14.4V
Float	13.3V
Bulk Restart	12.6V

CC Charging Overview (MODE = NC)

To program the LTC4020 for CC charging, leave the MODE pin unconnected. This mode can be used for charging NiCd and NiMH batteries, supercap charging, or in any other application where a timed current source is desired. CC mode can also be used when the voltage dependent precondition mode is not desired.

In CC mode, the LTC4020 will maintain full programmed charge current capability for the duration of the timer period. The trickle charge function is disabled, although maximum charge current will be reduced during lower deck operation if there is excessive voltage (>0.3V) imposed across the PowerPath FET. The charger will terminate the charge cycle and the PowerPath FET will become high-impedance once timer EOC is reached.

While the charge cycle is designed to be voltage independent, a maximum V_{BAT} voltage can be programmed corresponding to $V_{FB} = 2.5V$, allowing constant-voltage functionality at that level if desired.

Once the timer reaches T_{EOC} and the charge cycle terminates, input power or SHDN must be cycled to initiate another charge cycle. If the timer function is disabled (TIMER = 0V), the current source function remains active indefinitely.

Note: For nickel-chemistry batteries (e.g. NiCd or NiMH), the possibility of overcharging must be considered. A typical method is to charge with low currents for a long period of time. NiCd and NiMH batteries can absorb a C/300 charge rate indefinitely. Shorter duration charging is possible using a timed current source charge algorithm. It is recommended to ensure a depleted battery before charging, then subsequently charge the battery to no more than 125% capacity. For example, a depleted 2000mAh NiMH battery is charged with 2.5A for one hour.

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DC/DC CONVERTER SECTION

Output Voltage Programming

The LTC4020 DC/DC converter maximum output voltage, or voltage safety limit, is set by an external feedback resistive divider, providing feedback to the V_{FBMAX} pin. This divider sets the output voltage that the converter will servo to when the PowerPath FET is high impedance, which occurs after charge cycle termination or during a charge cycle fault.

Figure 4. V_{OUT} Safety Limit Programming

The resultant feedback signal is compared with the internal 2.75V voltage reference by the converter error amplifier. The output voltage is given by the equation:

$$V_{OUT} = 2.75V \cdot \left(1 + \frac{R_{MAX1}}{R_{MAX2}}\right)$$

where R_{MAX1} and R_{MAX2} are defined as in Figure 4.

The values for R_{MAX1} and R_{MAX2} are typically the same as those used for the divider that programs battery voltage (to the VFB pin; see Battery Charger section), to yield a DC/DC converter maximum regulation voltage, or safety limit, that is 10% higher than the battery charge voltage.

R_{SENSEA} , R_{SENSEB} : DC/DC Converter Current Programming

The LTC4020 performs inductor current sensing via two resistors connected in series with the V_{IN} side switches (see Figure 1). The high side sense resistor (R_{SENSEA}) is connected between V_{IN} and the drain of the top side switch FET (A). Both nodes on the sense resistor must be Kelvin connected to the IC via the pins SENSVIN and SENSTOP. Likewise, the low side sense resistor (R_{SENSEB}) is connected between the source of the bottom side switch FET (B) and

PGND. Both nodes on the sense resistor must be Kelvin connected to the IC, via the pins SENSBOT and SENSEGND.

Both of these sense resistors must be of equal value, and that value programs the switched inductor maximum average current in the DC/DC converter inductor (I_{LMAX}) such that:

$$R_{SENSEA} = R_{SENSEB} = \frac{0.05}{I_{LMAX}}$$

When the converter is stepping down, or operating in buck mode, the inductor current will be roughly equivalent to the converter output current. Input supply current (I_{IN}) will be less than the inductor current (I_L), such that:

$$I_L \sim I_{IN} \cdot \left(\frac{V_{IN}}{V_{OUT}}\right)$$

When the converter is stepping up, or operating in boost mode, the inductor current will be roughly equivalent to the converter input current. Inductor current (I_L) will be greater than output current (I_{OUT}), such that:

$$I_L \sim I_{OUT} \cdot \left(\frac{V_{OUT}}{V_{IN}}\right)$$

Overcurrent Detection

The LTC4020 also contains an overcurrent detection circuit that monitors the low side current sense resistor, or SENSBOT–SENSEGND input. Should that circuit detect a voltage on that input that is less than $-150mV$ or greater than $100mV$, or roughly 3x the maximum average current, all of the switches are disabled for four (4) clock cycles.

Parasitic inductances on non-ideal layouts and or body-diode commutation charge can cause voltage spikes across the sense resistor at the beginning of synchronous FET conduction. The LTC4020 overcurrent circuitry is somewhat resistant to these leading edge spikes but, in some cases, the overcurrent circuit can be prematurely triggered. This is identified by the repeated 4-cycle switch off-time that occurs should premature triggering occur. Placing a ceramic capacitor across the SENSBOT–SENSEGND input pins near the IC will generally eliminate

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premature triggering by high pass filtering the current sense signal. Setting the τ of the effective filter in the range of 1ns is generally sufficient to shunt errant signals, such that:

$$C_{\text{SENSEB}} \sim \frac{1\text{ns}}{R_{\text{SENSEB}}}$$

Programming Switching Frequency

The RT frequency adjust pin allows the user to program the LTC4020 DC/DC converter operating frequency from 50kHz to 500kHz.

Higher frequency operation is desirable for smaller external inductor and capacitor values, but at the expense of increased switching losses and higher gate drive currents. Higher frequencies may also not allow sufficiently high or low duty cycle operation due to minimum on/off time constraints. Lower operating frequencies require larger external component values, but result in reduced switching losses yielding higher conversion efficiencies.

Operating frequency (f_0) is set by choosing an appropriate frequency setting resistor (R_{RT}), connected from the RT pin to ground. This resistor is required for operation; do not leave this pin open. For a desired operating frequency, R_{RT} follows the relation:

$$R_{\text{RT}} = 100\text{k}\Omega \cdot \left(\frac{f_0}{250\text{kHz}} \right)^{-1.0695}$$

Figure 5. RT vs Operating Frequency

Input Supply Decoupling

The LTC4020 is typically biased directly from the charger input supply through the PV_{IN} and SENSVIN pins. This supply provides large switched currents, so a high quality, low ESR decoupling capacitor is recommended to minimize voltage glitches on the V_{IN} supply. Placing a smaller ceramic capacitor (0.1 μF to 10 μF) close to the IC in parallel with the input decoupling capacitor is also recommended for high frequency noise reduction. The SENSVIN pin is a Kelvin connection from the V_{IN} supply at the primary V_{IN} side switch FET (A); separate decoupling for that pin is not recommended. The charger input supply decoupling capacitor (C_{VIN}) absorbs all input switching ripple current in the charger, so it must have an adequate ripple current rating. RMS ripple current ($I_{\text{CVIN(RMS)}}$) is highest during step down operation, and follows the relation:

$$I_{\text{CVIN(RMS)}} \sim I_{\text{MAX}} \cdot \text{DC} \cdot \sqrt{\frac{1}{\text{DC}} - 1},$$

which has a maximum at $\text{DC} = 0.5$, or $V_{\text{IN}} = 2 \cdot V_{\text{OUT}}$, where:

$$I_{\text{CVIN(RMS)}} = \frac{I_{\text{MAX}}}{2}$$

The simple worst-case of $\frac{1}{2} \cdot I_{\text{MAX}}$ is commonly used for design, where I_{MAX} is the programmed inductor current limit.

Bulk capacitance ($C_{\text{IN(BULK)}}$) is a function of desired input ripple voltage (ΔV_{IN}). For step-down operation, $C_{\text{IN(BULK)}}$ follows the relation:

$$C_{\text{IN(BULK)}} \geq I_{\text{MAX}} \cdot \frac{V_{\text{OUT(MAX)}}}{V_{\text{IN(MIN)}}} \cdot \frac{1}{\Delta V_{\text{IN}} \cdot f_0},$$

where f_0 is the operating frequency, $V_{\text{OUT(MAX)}}$ is the DC/DC converter maximum output voltage and $V_{\text{IN(MIN)}}$ is the regulation voltage corresponding to 2.5V on $V_{\text{IN_REG}}$. If the input regulation feature is not being used, use the minimum expected input operating voltage.

If an application does not require step-down operation, during step-up operation, input ripple current is equivalent to inductor ripple current (ΔI_{MAX}), so $C_{\text{IN(BULK)}}$ follows the relation:

$$C_{\text{IN(BULK)}} = \frac{\Delta I_{\text{MAX}}}{\Delta V_{\text{IN}} \cdot f_0}$$

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I_{LIMIT} Pin

Maximum average inductor current can be dynamically adjusted using the I_{LIMIT} pin as described in the Pin Description section. Active servos can also be used to impose voltages on the I_{LIMIT} pin, provided they can only sink current. Active circuits that source current cannot be used to drive the I_{LIMIT} pin.

Figure 6. Using the I_{LIMIT} Pin for Digital Control of Maximum Average Inductor Current

Figure 7. Driving the I_{LIMIT} Pin with a Current Sink Active Servo Amplifier

Inductor Selection

The primary criterion for inductor value selection in an LTC4020 charger is the ripple current created in that inductor. Once the inductance value is determined, an inductor must also have a saturation current equal to or exceeding the maximum peak current in the inductor.

An inductor value (L) is calculated given the maximum desired amount of ripple current (ΔI_{MAX}). Maximum inductor ripple current should generally be in the range of 0.2 to 0.5 (as a fraction of maximum average inductor current, I_{MAX}). When stepping down, ripple current gets larger with increased V_{IN} , and is maximized when $V_{OUT} = V_{IN}/2$. When stepping up, ripple current gets larger with increased V_{OUT} , and is maximized when $V_{IN} = V_{OUT}/2$. The inductor value must be chosen using the greatest expected operational difference between these values.

A minimum inductor value for a given maximum ripple current and operating frequency (f_0) can be determined

using whichever relation yields the largest inductor value for L_{MIN} :

If $V_{IN} > V_{OUT}$ (step-down conversion):

$$L_{MIN} = \frac{V_{OUT} \cdot \left(1 - \left[V_{OUT} / V_{IN(MAX)}\right]\right)}{f_0 \cdot \Delta I_{MAX} \cdot I_{MAX}}$$

If $V_{IN} < V_{OUT}$ (step-up conversion):

$$L_{MIN} = \frac{V_{IN} \cdot \left(1 - \left[V_{IN} / V_{OUT(MAX)}\right]\right)}{f_0 \cdot \Delta I_{MAX} \cdot I_{MAX}}$$

For step-down conversion, use the maximum expected operating voltage for $V_{IN(MAX)}$. If the expected V_{OUT} operating range (typically from $V_{FBMIN} = 2.125V$ to $V_{FBMAX} = 2.75V$) includes $V_{IN(MAX)}/2$, use that value for V_{OUT} . If the entire operating range is below $V_{IN(MAX)}/2$, use the value corresponding to $V_{FBMAX} = 2.75V$. If the entire operating range is above $V_{IN(MAX)}/2$, use the value corresponding to $V_{FBMIN} = 2.125V$.

For step-up conversion, use the maximum output voltage (typically corresponding to pin $V_{FBMAX} = 2.75V$) for $V_{OUT(MAX)}$. If the expected V_{IN} operating range includes $V_{OUT(MAX)}/2$, use that value for V_{IN} . If the entire input operating range is below $V_{OUT(MAX)}/2$, use the maximum operating voltage for V_{IN} . If the entire input operating range is above $V_{OUT(MAX)}/2$, use the minimum input operating voltage for V_{IN} .

Magnetics vendors typically specify inductors with maximum RMS and saturation current ratings. Select an inductor that has a saturation current rating at or above $1.25 \cdot I_{MAX}$, and an RMS rating above I_{MAX} .

Output Decoupling

During periods when the LTC4020 DC/DC converter output is not connected to the battery through the PowerPath FET, the system load is driven directly by the converter. The converter creates large switched currents, so a high quality, low ESR decoupling capacitor is recommended to minimize voltage glitches on the V_{OUT} supply. Placing a smaller ceramic decoupling capacitor ($0.1\mu F$ to $10\mu F$) in parallel with the output decoupling capacitor is also recommended for high frequency noise reduction. The V_{OUT} decoupling capacitor (C_{VOUT}) absorbs the majority of

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the converter ripple current, so it must have an adequate ripple current rating. RMS ripple current ($I_{\Delta RMS}$) is highest during step up operation, and follows the relation:

$$I_{\Delta RMS} \sim I_{MAX} \cdot DC \cdot \sqrt{\frac{1}{DC} - 1},$$

having a maximum at $DC = 0.5$, or $V_{OUT} = 2 \cdot V_{IN}$, where:

$$I_{CVOUT(RMS)} = \frac{I_{MAX}}{2}$$

The simple worst-case of $\frac{1}{2} \cdot I_{MAX}$ is commonly used for design, where I_{MAX} is the programmed inductor current limit.

Bulk capacitance is a function of desired output ripple voltage (ΔV_{OUT}), and follows the relations:

For step-up operation:

$$C_{OUT(BULK)} \geq I_{MAX} \cdot \frac{V_{OUT(MAX)} - V_{IN(MIN)}}{V_{OUT(MAX)}} \cdot \frac{1}{\Delta V_{OUT} \cdot f_0},$$

where $V_{OUT(MAX)}$ is the DC/DC converter safety limit, and $V_{IN(MIN)}$ is the V_{IN} regulation threshold. If the V_{IN} regulation feature is not being used, use the minimum expected operating voltage.

For step-down operation, output ripple current is equivalent to inductor ripple current (ΔI_{MAX}), so $C_{OUT(BULK)}$ follows the relation:

$$C_{OUT(BULK)} \geq \frac{\Delta I_{MAX}}{\Delta V_{OUT} \cdot f_0},$$

Switch FET Selection

The LTC4020 requires four external N-channel power MOSFETs, as shown in Figure 1.

Specified parameters used for power MOSFET selection are: breakdown voltage ($V_{BR(DSS)}$), threshold voltage ($V_{GS(TH)}$), on-resistance ($R_{DS(ON)}$), reverse transfer capacitance (C_{RSS}), and maximum inductor current (I_{LMAX}).

The drive voltage is set by the $INTV_{CC}$ supply pin, which is typically 5V. Consequently, logic-level threshold MOSFETs must be used in LTC4020 applications.

Transition Losses (P_{TR}): During maximum power operation, all 4 switches change state once per oscillator cycle, so the maximum switching transient power losses (P_{TR}) remain constant over condition.

$$P_{TR(A, B)} \approx (k)(V_{IN})^2 (I_{LMAX})(C_{RSS})(f_0)$$

$$P_{TR(C, D)} \approx (k)(V_{OUT})^2 (I_{LMAX})(C_{RSS})(f_0)$$

$P_{TR(A, B)}$ is the transition loss for the V_{IN} side switch FETs A and B, and $P_{TR(C, D)}$ is the transition loss for V_{OUT} side switch FETs C and D, with the switch FETs designated as in Figure 1. The constant k , which accounts for the loss caused by reverse recovery current, is inversely proportional to the gate drive current and has an empirical value approximated by $k = 1$ in LTC4020 applications. I_{LMAX} is the converter maximum inductor current as programmed by the two sense resistors.

Conductive Losses (P_{ON}): Conductive losses are proportional to switch duty cycle. The average conductive losses in a switch at maximum inductor current (I_{LMAX}) is:

$$P_{ON} = I_{LMAX}^2 \cdot \rho T \cdot R_{DS(ON)} \cdot (T_{ON} \cdot f_0)$$

where ρT is a normalization factor (unity at 25°C) accounting for the significant variation in on-resistance with temperature. For a maximum junction temperature of 125°C, using a value of $\rho T = 1.5$ is reasonable.

If $V_{IN} > V_{OUT}$ (step-down conversion):

$$P_{ON(A)} = I_{LMAX}^2 \cdot \rho T \cdot R_{DS(ON(A))} \cdot (V_{OUT}/V_{IN})$$

$$P_{ON(B)} = I_{LMAX}^2 \cdot \rho T \cdot R_{DS(ON(B))} \cdot (1 - V_{OUT}/V_{IN})$$

$$P_{ON(C+D)} = I_{LMAX}^2 \cdot \rho T \cdot R_{DS(ON(C, D))}$$

If $V_{IN} < V_{OUT}$ (step-up conversion):

$$P_{ON(A+B)} = I_{LMAX}^2 \cdot \rho T \cdot R_{DS(ON(A, B))}$$

$$P_{ON(C)} = I_{LMAX}^2 \cdot \rho T \cdot R_{DS(ON(C))} \cdot (1 - V_{IN}/V_{OUT})$$

$$P_{ON(D)} = I_{LMAX}^2 \cdot \rho T \cdot R_{DS(ON(D))} \cdot (V_{IN}/V_{OUT})$$

Optional Schottky Diode (Db, Dd) Selection

Schottky diodes can be placed in parallel with the synchronous FETs B and D, as shown in Figure 1 as Db and Dd. These diodes conduct during the dead time between the conduction of the power MOSFET switches and are intended to prevent the body diode of synchronous switches from storing charge.

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To maximize effectiveness of the diodes, the inductance between the switches and the synchronous switches must be minimized, so the diodes should be placed adjacent to their corresponding FET switch.

The Dd diode also reduces power dissipation in the D switch during periods of reverse current inhibit operation, during which time the D switch is disabled. Load currents are low during reverse inhibit, and diode Db only conducts during switch dead times, so both can have current ratings well below the DC/DC converter inductor current maximum. Typically, a diode with an average current rating at or above one-tenth of I_{LMAX} is adequate, provided the diode has an instantaneous current rating that exceeds the maximum inductor current, or $I_{LMAX} + \frac{1}{2} \Delta I_{MAX}$.

Db reverse voltage rating must exceed V_{IN} . Dd reverse voltage rating must exceed V_{OUT} .

INTV_{CC} LDO Output, and BST1 and BST2 Supplies

Power for the top and bottom MOSFET drivers and most other internal circuitry is derived from the INTV_{CC} pin. An internal 5V low dropout regulator (LDO) supplies INTV_{CC} power from the PV_{IN} pin. INTV_{CC} is decoupled to PGND using a 2.2 μ F ceramic capacitor.

The BST1 and BST2 bootstrapped supply pins power internal high side FET gate drivers, which output to pins TG1 and TG2. BST1 provides switch gate drive above the input power supply voltage for switch FET A, and BST2 provides switch gate drive above the output power supply voltage for switch FET D, as designated in Figure 1. These boosted supply pins allows the use of NFET switches for increased conversion efficiency. These bootstrapped supplies are regenerated through external Schottky diodes from the INTV_{CC} pin.

Connect two low leakage 1A Schottky diode anodes to the INTV_{CC} pin. Connect one Schottky cathode to the BST1 pin. This diode must be rated for reverse voltage standoff exceeding the maximum input supply voltage. Connect the other diode cathode to the BST2 pin. This diode must be rated for reverse voltage standoff exceeding the converter safety limit output, $V_{OUT(MAX)}$.

Connect a ceramic capacitor from the BST1 pin to the SW1 pin and another from BST2 pin to the SW2 pin. The value of these two capacitors should be at least 50

times greater than the equivalent total gate capacitance of the corresponding switch FET. Total FET gate charge ($Q_{G(TOT)}$) is typically specified at a specific gate-source voltage ($V_{GS(Q)}$). Using those parameters, the required boost capacitor values (C_{BST}) follow the relation:

$$C_{BST} > 50 \cdot Q_{G(TOT)} / V_{GS(Q)}$$

$C_{BST} = 1\mu\text{F}$ is typically adequate for most applications.

During low load operation, start-up, and nonoverlap periods, inductor current is conducted by the silicon body diode of the synchronous FET. This diode stores a significant amount of charge, so when the primary switch turns on for the next switch cycle, reverse recovery current is conducted by the main switch to discharge this diode. The resultant short-duration current spike can be orders of magnitude greater than the inductor current itself, resulting in an extremely fast dV/dt on the switched node. Consequently, parasitic inductance associated with the switch FET packaging and/or less-than-ideal layout can induce a voltage spike of 10 or more volts at the leading edge of a switching cycle. This can be particularly problematic on the step-up side of the inductor, as these voltage spikes are negative, and can cause a build-up of voltage on the BST2-SW2 capacitor. This would generally occur when the step-up synchronous switch (D) is disabled, such as during low load operation and during start-up. If voltage build-up on the boosted supply proves excessive, it could potentially violate absolute maximum voltage ratings of the IC and cause damage. This effect can be greatly reduced by implementing a Schottky diode across the step-up synchronous FET, shown as D_D in Figure 1, which reduces reverse recovery charge in the synchronous FET body diode. A low current 6V Zener (0.1A) in parallel with the BST2-SW2 capacitor will also effectively shunt any errant charge and prevent excessive voltage build-up.

External Power for BST1 and BST2 Supplies

Power for the top and bottom MOSFET drivers can be supplied by an external supply, provided that a precision 5V supply is available ($\pm 5\%$).

The INTV_{CC} internal supply is a linear regulator, which transfers current from the V_{IN} pin. As such, power dissipation can be excessive with high V_{IN} pin voltages and/

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or large gate drive requirements. The power dissipation in the linear pass element (P_{INTVCC}) is:

$$P_{INTVCC} = (V_{IN} - 5V) \cdot Q_{G(TOT)ABCD} \cdot f_0,$$

where $Q_{G(TOT)ABCD}$ is the sum of all four switch total gate charges, and f_0 is the LTC4020 switching frequency.

Figure 8. INTV_{CC} Pass Element SOA (Safe Operating Area)

If desired operation places the internal 5V regulator out of the allowable SOA region, deriving gate drive power externally is required.

For driving the LTC4020 with an external 5V regulator, connect the PV_{IN} and $INTV_{CC}$ pins to that regulator output as shown in Figure 9. The $SENSVIN$ pin remains connected to the input supply.

Figure 9. Connection of External 5V Regulator for Reduced Internal Power Dissipation

For operation with tightly regulated low voltage input supplies (4.5V to 5.5V), the LTC4020 internal gate drivers and BST refresh functions can be powered directly by the input supply, eliminating the requirement for a 5V regulator to supply the $INTV_{CC}$ pin. Connect the input supply to the PV_{IN} , $INTV_{CC}$, and $SENSVIN$ pins, as shown in Figure 10.

Figure 10. Connection of Low-Voltage Input Supply

In this configuration, the $INTV_{CC}$ pin cannot collapse when the LTC4020 is in shutdown. As a result of the pin bias being maintained during shutdown, current will flow into the $INTV_{CC}$ pin, increasing input supply current. The total shutdown current flowing into the $INTV_{CC}$ pin in this configuration is approximately 150 μ A.

BATTERY CHARGER SECTION

Battery Charge Voltage Programming

The LTC4020 uses an external feedback resistive divider from the BAT pin to ground to program battery voltages. This divider provides feedback to the V_{FB} pin, and sets the final voltage that the battery charger will achieve at the end of a charge cycle. The feedback reference of 2.5V corresponds to the battery float voltage during CC/CV mode charging ($MODE = 0V$).

Figure 11. Battery Voltage Programming

The resultant feedback signal is compared with the internal 2.5V voltage reference by the converter error amplifier. The output voltage is given by the equation:

$$V_{(FLOAT)(CC/CV)} = 2.5V \left(1 + \frac{R_{FB1}}{R_{FB2}} \right)$$

where R_{FB1} and R_{FB2} are defined as in Figure 11.

If charging in CC mode ($MODE = -NC-$), R_{FB1} and R_{FB2} corresponding to $V_{FB} = 2.5V$ programs a maximum V_{BAT} voltage, if constant-voltage functionality at that level is desired.

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During lead-acid charging ($MODE = INTV_{CC}$), the absorption mode voltage corresponds to 2.5V on the V_{FB} pin. Battery float voltage (maintenance) corresponds to 2.3125V on the V_{FB} pin, or 92.5% of the absorption voltage. These voltages typically correspond to 14.4V and 13.3V respectively for a 6-cell (12V) battery.

The values for R_{FB1} and R_{FB2} are typically the same as those used for the divider that programs the converter safety limit (converter output to the V_{FBMAX} pin; see DC/DC Converter section), which yields a DC/DC converter maximum regulation voltage, or safety limit, that is 10% higher than the maximum battery charge voltage.

Common Battery Types: Normalized R_{FB1} Resistor Values ($R_{FB2} = 1$)

BATTERY TYPE	VOLTAGE	R_{FB1}
1-Cell LiFePO ₄	3.6V Float	0.44
1-Cell Li-Ion	4.2V Float	0.68
2-Cell LiFePO ₄	7.2V Float	1.88
2-Cell Li-Ion	8.4V Float	2.36
6-Cell Lead-Acid	12V Battery	4.76
3-Cell LiFePO ₄	10.8V Float	3.32
3-Cell Li-Ion	12.6V Float	4.04
4-Cell LiFePO ₄	14.4V Float	4.76
6-Cell LiFePO ₄	21.6V Float	7.64
12-Cell Lead-Acid	24V Battery	10.52

R_{CS} : Battery Charge Current Programming

The LTC4020 senses battery charge current using a sense resistor that is connected between the CSP and CSN pins. Maximum average battery charge current (I_{CSMAX}) is programmed by setting the value of this current sense resistor. The resistor value is selected so the desired maximum charge current through that sense resistor creates a 50mV drop, or:

$$R_{CS} = \frac{0.05V}{I_{CSMAX}}$$

For example, for a maximum average charge current of 5A, use a 0.01 Ω sense resistor.

PowerPath FET Function and Instant-On

The LTC4020 controls an external PMOS with its gate connected to the BGATE pin. This PowerPath FET controls current flow to and from the battery.

During a normal battery charge cycle, the BGATE pin is pulled low (clamped at $V_{GS} = 9.5V$), which operates the FET as a low impedance connection from the DC/DC converter output to the battery, effectively shorting the battery to the converter output. This minimizes power dissipation from charge current passing through the FET. When there is no V_{IN} power or when the IC is in shutdown, LTC4020 connects the battery to the converter output by holding the BGATE pin low, again effectively shorting the battery to the converter output. This minimizes power dissipation while the output is powered by the battery.

The LTC4020 controls the PowerPath FET to perform instant-on operation when a charge cycle is initiated into a heavily discharged battery. If the battery voltage is below a programmed minimum operational output voltage, corresponding to $V_{FBMIN} = 2.125V$, the PowerPath FET is configured as a linear regulator, allowing the DC/DC converter output to rise above the battery voltage while still providing charge current into the battery. During instant-on operation, the BGATE pin is driven by the LTC4020 to maintain the minimum programmed voltage on the PowerPath FET source, the FET acting as a high impedance current source, providing charge current to the battery, independent of the battery voltage.

Figure 12. Instant-On DC/DC Converter Output vs Battery Voltage Characteristics

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The resultant feedback signal is compared with the internal 2.125V voltage reference by a dedicated instant-on error amplifier, the output of which serves the BGATE pin. The output voltage is given by the equation:

$$V_{OUT} = 2.125V \left(1 + \frac{R_{MIN1}}{R_{MIN2}} \right)$$

where R_{MIN1} and R_{MIN2} are defined as in Figure 13.

Figure 13. V_{OUT} Instant-On Programming

The values for R_{MIN1} and R_{MIN2} are typically the same as those used for the divider that programs battery voltage (to the VFB pin; see Battery Charger section), to yield a DC/DC converter minimum operational regulation voltage corresponding to 85% of the battery charge voltage.

During instant-on operation, if the drain-to-source voltage across the PowerPath FET ($V_{CSN} - V_{BAT}$) exceeds 0.45V, the maximum charge current is automatically reduced. Maximum charge current is reduced linearly across the range of $0.45V < V_{CSN} - V_{BAT} < 1.95V$ to one-fifteenth of the current programmed by the battery charger sense resistor, RCS. This reduction in charge current helps to prevent excessive power dissipation in the PowerPath FET.

Figure 14. Instant-On Charger Current Sense Limit Reduction

When the DC/DC converter is operating, but the battery charger is not in a charging cycle, the PowerPath FET is automatically configured as an ideal diode between the BAT pin (anode) and the CSN pin (cathode). The ideal diode function allows the battery to remain disconnected from the converter output while the converter is supplying power, but also allows the battery to be efficiently engaged for additional power should a load exceed the DC/DC converter's capability. This ideal diode circuit regulates the external FET to achieve low loss conduction, maintaining a voltage drop of 14mV across from the BAT pin to the CSN pin, provided the battery current load though the ideal diode does not exceed $14mV/R_{DS(ON)}$. With larger currents, the FET will behave like a fixed value resistor equal to $R_{DS(ON)}$.

In certain applications, the PowerPath function is not required. For example, lead-acid chargers do not terminate (they remain in float charging mode indefinitely), so the battery need never be disconnected from the output, provided the instant-on feature is not desired. The PowerPath FET can be eliminated in these applications by tying the CSN side of the sense resistor to BAT, connecting V_{FBMIN} to ground, and connecting a 100pF capacitor from the BGATE pin to CSN. See Typical Application Circuits section.

RNG/SS: Dynamic Current Limit Adjust

Maximum charge current can be dynamically adjusted using the RNG/SS pin as described in the Pin Description section. Active servos can also be used to impose voltages on the RNG/SS pin, provided they can only sink current. Active circuits that source current cannot be used to drive the RNG/SS pin.

Figure 15. Using the RNG/SS Pin for Digital Control of Maximum Charge Current

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Figure 16. Driving the RNG/SS Pin with a Current Sink Active Servo Amplifier

RNG/SS: Soft-Start

Soft-start functionality is also supported by the RNG/SS pin. $50\mu\text{A}$ is sourced from the RNG/SS pin, so connecting a capacitor from the RNG/SS pin to ground ($C_{\text{RNG/SS}}$) creates a linear voltage ramp. The maximum charge current follows this voltage, thus increasing the charge current capability from zero to the full programmed value as the capacitor gets charged from 0 to 1V. The value of $C_{\text{RNG/SS}}$ is calculated based on the desired time to full current (T_{SS}) following the relation:

$$C_{\text{RNG/SS}} = 50\mu\text{A} \cdot T_{\text{SS}}$$

The RNG/SS pin is pulled to ground internally when charging is terminated so each new charging cycle begins with a soft-start cycle. RNG/SS is also pulled to ground during bad battery and NTC fault conditions.

Figure 17. Using the RNG/SS Pin for Soft-Start

Status Pins

The LTC4020 reports charger status through two open collector outputs, the STAT1 and STAT2 pins. These pins can accept voltages as high as 55V when disabled, and can sink up to 5mA when enabled.

If the LTC4020 is configured for a CC/CV charging algorithm, the STAT1 pin is pulled low while battery charge currents exceed 10% of the programmed maximum ($C/10$). The STAT1 pin is also pulled low during NTC faults. The STAT2 pin is pulled low during NTC faults or after a bad battery fault occurs. The STAT1 pin becomes high impedance when a charge cycle is terminated or when charge current is below the $C/10$ threshold, and the STAT2 pin remains high impedance if no fault conditions are present.

If the LTC4020 is configured for a CC charging algorithm, the STAT1 pin is pulled low during the entire charging cycle, and the STAT2 pin is pulled low during NTC faults. The STAT1 pin becomes high impedance when the charge cycle is terminated.

If the LTC4020 is configured for a lead-acid charging algorithm, the STAT1 and STAT2 pins are used as charge cycle stage indicator pins. The STAT1 pin is pulled low during the bulk and absorption charging stages and is high impedance during the float charging period and during NTC or bad battery faults. The STAT2 pin is pulled low during bulk and float charging stages, and is high impedance during the absorption charging stage and during NTC or bad battery faults.

The STAT1 and STAT2 status pins are binary coded, and signal following the table below, where ON indicates pin pulled low, and OFF indicates pin high impedance:

STATUS PINS STATE		CC/CV (MODE = 0V)	LEAD-ACID (MODE = INTV _{CC})	CC (MODE = -NC-)
STAT1	STAT2			
OFF	OFF	Not Charging — Standby or Shutdown Mode, $I_{\text{CS}} < C/10$	Not Charging — NTC/Bad Battery Fault or Shutdown	Not Charging — Standby or Shutdown Mode, $I_{\text{CS}} < C/10$
OFF	ON	Bad Battery Fault	Float Charge	Not Used
ON	OFF	Charging Cycle OK: Trickle Charge or $I_{\text{CS}} > C/10$	Absorption Charge	Charge Cycle OK
ON	ON	NTC Fault	Bulk Charge	NTC Fault

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TIMER: C/10 Termination

The LTC4020 supports a low current based termination scheme. This termination mode is engaged by shorting the TIMER pin to ground.

When in CC/CV charge mode, a battery charge cycle terminates when the current output from the charger falls to below one-tenth the maximum charge current, or I_{CSMAX} , as programmed with R_{CS} . The C/10 threshold current corresponds to 5mV across R_{CS} .

During lead-acid charging, the LTC4020 initiates float charging when the absorption stage charge current is reduced to one-tenth of the programmed maximum current.

When charging in CC mode, the current source function remains active indefinitely.

There is no provision for bad battery detection if C/10 termination is used.

TIMER: Timed Functions

The LTC4020 supports timer based functions, where battery charge cycle control occurs after a specific amount of time elapses. Timer termination is engaged when a capacitor (C_{TIMER}) is connected from the TIMER pin to ground. C_{TIMER} for a desired end-of-cycle time (T_{EOC}) follows the relation:

$$C_{TIMER} = T_{EOC} \cdot 6.87 \times 10^{-2} (\mu F)$$

where T_{EOC} is hours.

A typical timer T_{EOC} for Li-Ion charge cycle termination is three hours, which requires a 0.2 μ F timer capacitor. The timer cycle starts when the charger transitions from constant-current to constant-voltage charging, thus, termination at the end of the timer cycle only occurs if the charging cycle was successful. When timer termination is used, the STAT1 status pin is pulled low during a charging cycle until the battery charge current falls below the C/10 threshold. The STAT1 pin stays high impedance with charge currents below C/10, but the charger continues to top off the battery until timer T_{EOC} , when the LTC4020 terminates the charging cycle and the PowerPath FET disconnects the battery from the DC/DC converter output.

During lead-acid charging, the timer acts as an absorption mode safety timer. Normally, the LTC4020 initiates

float charging when the absorption stage charge current is reduced to one-tenth of the programmed maximum current, however, the maximum duration of absorption charging is limited by the timer. If the charge current does not fall to one-tenth of the programmed maximum current by T_{EOC} , the LTC4020 forces the battery charger to begin float mode charging. A typical timer T_{EOC} for lead-acid charging is six to eight hours, which is accommodated by a 0.47 μ F timer capacitor.

When charging in CC mode, after charge termination, once the timer reaches T_{EOC} and the charge cycle terminates, input power or SHDN must be cycled to initiate another battery charge cycle.

A bad battery detection function is available during CC/CV or lead-acid charging. This fault condition is achieved if the battery does not respond to preconditioning ($V_{FB} < 1.75V$), such that the charger remains in (or enters) precondition mode after one-eighth of the programmed T_{EOC} time. A bad battery fault halts the charging cycle, and the fault condition is reported on the status pins. The bad battery fault remains active until the battery voltage rises above the precondition threshold, or until power or SHDN is cycled.

Battery Temperature Qualified Charging: NTC

The LTC4020 can accommodate battery temperature monitoring by using an NTC (negative temperature co-efficient) thermistor close to the battery pack. The temperature monitoring function is enabled by connecting a 10k Ω , $\beta = 3380$ NTC thermistor from the NTC pin to ground. If the NTC function is not desired, leave the pin unconnected.

The NTC pin sources 50 μ A, and monitors the voltage dropped across the 10k Ω thermistor. When the voltage on this pin is above 1.35V (0 $^{\circ}$ C) or below 0.3V (40 $^{\circ}$ C), the battery temperature is out of range, and the LTC4020 triggers an NTC fault. The NTC fault condition remains until the voltage on the NTC pin corresponds to a temperature within the 0 $^{\circ}$ C to 40 $^{\circ}$ C range. Both hot and cold thresholds incorporate hysteresis that corresponds to 5 $^{\circ}$ C.

If higher operational charging temperatures are desired, the temperature range can be expanded by adding series resistance to the 10k NTC resistor. Adding a 910 Ω resistor will increase the effective HOT temperature threshold to 45 $^{\circ}$ C. The effect of this additional resistance on the COLD threshold is negligible.

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During an NTC fault, charging is halted and an NTC fault is indicated on the status pins. If timer termination is enabled, the timer count is suspended and held until the fault condition is relieved. The RNG/SS pin is also pulled low during this fault, to accommodate a graceful restart, in the event that a soft-start function is being incorporated (see Dynamic Charge Current Adjust and Soft-Start section).

DC/DC Converter: External Compensation and Filtering Components

The LTC4020 average current mode architecture employs two integrating compensation nodes. The current setting loop is compensated at the output of the current sense amplifier on the VC pin, generally with a series R-C network (R_{VC} , C_{VC}). The voltage generated on the VC pin is compared with an internal ramp, providing control of the converter duty cycle.

The voltage loop is compensated at the output of the error amplifier on the ITH pin, generally with a series R-C network (R_{ITH} , C_{ITH}). The voltage on the ITH pin is imposed onto the current sense amplifier, setting the current level to which the current loop will servo.

While determining compensation components, the LTC4020 should initially be configured to eliminate any functional contribution from the battery charger section. This can be easily accomplished by connecting the NTC pin to ground, which disables all battery charging functions and puts the PowerPath FET into a high impedance state.

The current loop compensation (VC pin) transfer function crossover frequency is typically set to approximately one-half of the switching frequency; the voltage loop compensation (ITH pin) transfer function crossover frequency is typically set to approximately one-tenth of the switching frequency.

Compensation values must be tested at high and low input voltage operational limits, and also $V_{IN} \sim V_{OUT}$, so that stable operation during all switching modes (buck, boost, buck-boost) is verified.

If a network analyzer is not available for determining compensation values, use procedures as outlined in Application Note 19 for adjusting compensation. Application Note 19 can be found at <http://www.linear.com/docs/4176>.

VC pin compensation:

1. $V_{NTC} = V_{FBMAX} = 0V$
2. Fix V_{IN} at typical voltage.
3. Fix V_{OUT} at V_{FB} regulation voltage. A charged battery, battery simulator, or a 2-quadrant power supply can be used for V_{OUT} .
4. Impose 1V to 1.5V square wave (1kHz) on ITH pin
5. Monitor inductor current using current probe
6. Adjust compensation values as per AN19 until response is critically damped

ITH pin compensation:

1. $V_{NTC} = 0V$ (disables charger)
2. Bring to regulation ($V_{FBMAX} = 2.75V$)
3. Step load current on output (25% to 75% of I_{MAX})
4. Monitor V_{OUT} voltage
5. Adjust compensation values as per AN19 until response is critically damped and settled in ~10 to 25 cycles
6. $V_{NTC} = 0.8$ (enable charger)
7. Exercise battery charger and verify stability in all modes

Battery Charger Functions: Filtering Components

Voltage Regulation Loop (VFB):

The charger voltage regulation loop monitors battery voltage, and as such is controlled by a very slow moving node. Battery ESR, however, can produce significant AC voltages due to ripple currents, which can cause unstable operation. This ESR effect can be reduced by adding a capacitor to the VFB input, producing a low frequency pole.

Figure 18. VFB Ripple Suppression

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Current Sense Regulation Loop (CSN, CSP):

The charger current regulation loop monitors and regulates battery charge current. Ripple voltage on the DC/DC converter output, however, gets directly imposed across the charger sense resistor, and can produce significant ripple currents. Large ripple currents can corrupt low level current sensing, and can also cause unstable operation. This ripple current effect can be greatly reduced by adding a capacitor (C_{CS}) across the CSN and CSP pins, producing a low frequency pole with the two 100Ω resistors that are required for those pins. The filter frequency is typically set to reduce voltage ripple across the current sense inputs at the CSP and CSN pins to less than $1mV_{PP}$.

The ripple-reduction filter on the current sense inputs creates a phase shift in the charger current loop response, which can result in instability. A resistor (R_{CSZ}) in series with C_{CS} creates a zero that can be employed to recover phase margin. This zero setting resistor will reintroduce ripple error, so R_{CS} should be minimized. CSOUT can be coupled into ITH for a similar feedforward zero with $R_{CS} = 0$.

Current sense information, or differential voltage at the CSN to CSP pins, is amplified by a factor of 20 then output on pin CSOUT. This signal is compared to a reference voltage that is proportional to the maximum charge current at the input of a transconductance amplifier, which creates an error current that modulates the ITH compensation pin. A feedforward zero can be employed to recover phase margin by putting a capacitor from the CSOUT pin to the ITH pin (C_{CSOUT}). The output impedance of the CSOUT pin is $\sim 100k\Omega$, so if compensation requirements are appropriate, the C_{CSOUT} capacitor can perform double-duty as both the primary pole ITH capacitor along with a $100k\Omega$ zero-setting resistance, and as feed forward coupling from CSOUT to ITH.

Figure 19. CSN/CSP Ripple Suppression

Instant-On/Ideal Diode Regulation Loop (BGATE):

The instant-on function regulates the voltage across the PowerPath FET by servoing the voltage at the BGATE pin. Gate capacitance of the PowerPath FET is typically sufficient to stabilize this loop. Additional capacitance can be added to the BGATE pin (C_{BGATE}) to stabilize the current foldback loop during instant-on operation if necessary:

Figure 20. Instant-On/Ideal Diode Compensation

Layout Considerations

The LTC4020 is typically used in designs that involve substantial switching transients. The switch drivers on the IC are designed to drive large capacitances and, as such, generate significant transient currents themselves. Supply bypass capacitor locations must be carefully considered to avoid corrupting the signal ground reference (SGND) used by the IC. Typically, high current paths and transients from the input supply and any local drive supplies must be kept isolated from SGND, to which sensitive circuits such as the error amp reference and the current sense circuits are referred.

Effective grounding can be achieved by considering switch current in the ground plane, and the return current paths of each respective bypass capacitor. The V_{IN} bypass return, $INTV_{CC}$ bypass return, and the sources of the ground-referred switch FETs carry PGND currents. SGND originates at the negative terminal of the V_{OUT} bypass capacitor, and is the small signal reference for the LTC4020.

Do not be tempted to run small traces to separate ground paths. A good ground plane is important as always, but PGND referred bypass elements must be oriented such that transient currents in these return paths do not corrupt the SGND reference.

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During the dead time between synchronous switch and main switch conduction, the body diode of the synchronous FET conducts inductor current. Commutating the body diode requires a significant charge contribution from the main switch during initiation of main switch, creating a current spike in the main switch. At the instant the body diode commutates, a current discontinuity is created between the inductor and main switch, with parasitic inductance causing the switch node to transition in response to this discontinuity. High currents and excessive parasitic inductance can generate extremely fast $\delta V/\delta t$ times during this transition. These fast $\delta V/\delta t$ transitions can sometimes cause avalanche breakdown in the synchronous FET body diode, generating shoot-through currents via parasitic turn-on of the synchronous FET. Layout practices and component orientations that minimize parasitic inductance on the switched nodes is critical for reducing these effects.

Orient power path components such that current paths in the ground plane do not cross through signal ground areas. Power ground currents are controlled on the LTC4020 via the PGND pin, and this ground references the high current synchronous switch drive components, as well as the local INTV_{CC} supply. It is important to keep PGND and SGND voltages consistent with each other. Separating these grounds with thin traces is not recommended.

When a ground referenced switch FET is turned off, gate drive currents return to the LTC4020 PGND pin from the switch FET source. The BOOST supply refresh surge currents also return through this same path. The switch FETs must be oriented such that these PGND return currents do not corrupt the SGND reference.

The high $\delta i/\delta t$ loop formed by the switch MOSFETs and the input capacitor (C_{VIN}) should have short wide traces to minimize high frequency noise and voltage stress from inductive ringing. Surface mount components are preferred to reduce parasitic inductances from component leads. Switch path currents can be controlled by orienting switch FETs, the switched inductor, and input and output decoupling capacitors in close proximity to each other. Locate the INTV_{CC}, BST1, and BST2 decoupling capacitors in close proximity to the IC. These capacitors carry the switch FET gate drive currents. Locate the small signal components away from high frequency switching nodes (TG1, BG1, TG2, BG2, SW1, SW2, BST1, BST2, and INTV_{CC}). High current switching nodes are oriented across the top of the LTC4020 package to simplify layout and prevent corruption of the SGND reference.

Locate the output and battery charger feedback resistors in close proximity to the LTC4020 and minimize the length of the high impedance feedback nodes.

The SENSVIN and SENSTOP traces should be routed together and SENSBOT and SENSNGND should be routed together. Keep these traces as short as possible, and avoid corruption of these lines by high current switching nodes.

The LTC4020 packaging has been designed to efficiently remove heat from the IC via the exposed pad on the backside of the package. The exposed pad is soldered to a copper footprint on the PCB. The exposed pad is electrically connected to SGND, so a good connection to a PCB ground plane effectively reduces the thermal resistance of the IC case to ambient air.

Please refer to LTC Application Note 136, which discusses guidelines, techniques, and considerations for switching power supply PCB design and layout: <http://www.linear.com/docs/42146>.

APPLICATIONS INFORMATION

LTC4020 Constant-Current/Constant-Voltage (CC/CV) Charging Diagram

4020 CD01

4020fd

APPLICATIONS INFORMATION

LTC4020 Lead-Acid Charging Diagram

4020 CD02

4020fd

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LTC4020 Constant-Current Charging Diagram

4020 CD02

TYPICAL APPLICATIONS

5V to 30V to 6-cell lead-acid PowerPath charger/system supply. 6A inductor current limit with 2.5A battery charge current limit. Instant-on functionality incorporated for battery voltages below 12.25V, 14.4V absorption voltage, 13.3V float voltage, and 15.6V maximum output voltage (Instant-On and NTC fault only). Status pins light LEDs for visible charge-state monitoring.

4020 TA02

TYPICAL APPLICATIONS

15V to 55V to 6-cell Li-Ion PowerPath charger/system supply. 6A inductor current limit with 2.5A battery charge current limit. Instant-on functionality for battery voltages below 20.4V, 24V charge termination voltage, and 26.4V maximum output voltage. Status pins light LEDs for visible charge-state monitoring.

TYPICAL APPLICATIONS

9V to 55V to 9-cell lead-acid (18V) charger/system supply with no PowerPath.
External 5V regulator for boosted supplies. 5A inductor current limit with 1.67A battery charge current limit.
21.5V absorption voltage output, 19.9V float voltage output.

9-CELL LEAD-ACID (18V) 4020 TA04

PACKAGE DESCRIPTION

Please refer to <http://www.linear.com/product/LTC4020#packaging> for the most recent package drawings.

UHF Package
38-Lead Plastic QFN (5mm × 7mm)
 (Reference LTC DWG # 05-08-1701 Rev C)

RECOMMENDED SOLDER PAD LAYOUT
 APPLY SOLDER MASK TO AREAS THAT ARE NOT SOLDERED

- NOTE:
1. DRAWING CONFORMS TO JEDEC PACKAGE OUTLINE MO-220 VARIATION WHKD
 2. DRAWING NOT TO SCALE
 3. ALL DIMENSIONS ARE IN MILLIMETERS

4. DIMENSIONS OF EXPOSED PAD ON BOTTOM OF PACKAGE DO NOT INCLUDE MOLD FLASH. MOLD FLASH, IF PRESENT, SHALL NOT EXCEED 0.20mm ON ANY SIDE
5. EXPOSED PAD SHALL BE SOLDER PLATED
6. SHADED AREA IS ONLY A REFERENCE FOR PIN 1 LOCATION ON THE TOP AND BOTTOM OF PACKAGE

REVISION HISTORY

REV	DATE	DESCRIPTION	PAGE NUMBER
A	01/14	Changed V_{IN} to PV_{IN}	2 to 5
		Modified $I_{SENSTOP}$ Operating Current spec	3
		Modified Error Amp Transconductance spec	3
		Changed C/10 Detection Enable Units	4
		Modified C/10 Detection Hysteresis spec	4
		Changed Conditions for Gate Clamp Voltage	4
		Changed Conditions for BGATE tests	5
		Changed Conditions for Pin Current (Disabled) spec	5
		Changed cathode to anode for BST1	8
		Changed anode to cathode for BST1	8
		Modified equations for T_{EOC} and T_{PRE} and associated TIMER text	9
		Modified equations for R_{FB1}/R_{FB2} and R_{MIN1}/R_{MIN2}	10
		Changed cathode to anode for BST2	12
		Changed anode to cathode for BST2	12
		Modified Error Amplified Transconductance	14
		Modified step-up and step-down equations in Switch FET section	24
		Modified C_{TIMER} equation and associated text	30
Modified Typical Applications circuit	38		
Modified Typical Application circuit to 12-cell	42		
B	09/14	Added "(Application Circuit on Page 37)" to efficiency curve title	1
		Added Ω unit to R_{FBG} specification	5
		Changed "INTV _{CC} Short Circuit Current Limit vs Temperature" curve y-axis units to 'mA'	6
		Added text to the end of the NTC (Pin 16) section	10
		Corrected formula: $(V_{OUTMAX}/2.75) - 1$	12
		Changed BST1 on lower-right of block diagram to BST2; Insert " V_{SENS} " below '2mV' near VC pin	14
		Added 2V Zener diode symbol from NTC pin (cathode) to ground (anode)	15
		Added "average" to first line; change "Charge" to "Average Inductor" in Figure 6 title	23
		Changed "inductor" to "charge"	28
		Added ground symbol to bottom of IC symbol (backside connection)	37
		Flipped PMOS symbol vertically (Si7461DP); add ground symbol to bottom of IC symbol (backside connection)	38
		Added ground symbol to bottom of IC symbol (backside connection)	39
		Moved connection of BZX84C6V2L anode from BG2 to SW2 (diode between BST2 and SW2); add ground symbol to bottom of IC symbol (backside connection)	42
C	09/15	Added pin names to Typical Application IC drawing	1
		Added text to end of SENSBOT (5) pin description section	8
		Changed text in RNG/SS section: "Inductor" to "Charge"	9
		Changed I_{LIMIT} text, "...pin, so maximum charge current..." to "...pin, so maximum inductor current..."	12
		Changed Operation section to "a 0.47 μ F capacitor on the TIMER pin is typically used, which generates a 6.8 hour absorption stage safety timeout"	20
		Changed " $C_{SENSBOT,SENSGND}$ " to " C_{SENSB} "	22
		Changed "...BGATE pin to ground" to "...BGATE pit to CSN"	28
		Changed "CSN" to "CSN". Replaced " R_{CS} with R_{CSZ} " in the text and in Figure 19. Replaced " R_{SENSE} " with R_{CS} in Figure 19	32
Replaced " R_{SENSE} " with " R_{CS} " in schematic	37-39, 42		
D	04/16	Modified bulk capacitance equation	24

LTC4020

TYPICAL APPLICATION

Remote 24V to 55V (48V system) input to 12-cell Li-Ion (48V) PowerPath charger/system supply. 5A inductor current limit with 2.5A battery charge current limit. Minimum V_{IN} is 24V as input regulation limits voltage loss due to line impedance. Battery termination voltage is 48V with maximum output voltage of 52.8V. Instant-on functionality limits minimum regulated output voltage to 40.8V.

RELATED PARTS

PART NUMBER	DESCRIPTION	COMMENTS
LTC3789	High Efficiency, Synchronous, 4 Switch Buck-Boost Controller	Improved LTC3780 with More Features
LT3845	High Voltage Synchronous Current Mode Step-Down Controller	For Medium/High Power, High Efficiency Supplies
LT3650	High Voltage 2A Monolithic Li-Ion Battery Charger	3mm × 3mm DFN-12 and MSOP-12 Packages
LT3651	High Voltage 4A Monolithic Li-Ion Battery Charger	4A Synchronous Version of LT3650 Family
LT3652/LT3652HV	Power Tracking 2A Battery Chargers	Multi-Chemistry, Onboard Termination
LTC4009	High Efficiency, Multi-Chemistry Battery Charger	Low Cost Version of LTC4008, 4mm × 4mm QFN-20
LTC4012	High Efficiency, Multi-Chemistry Battery Charger with PowerPath Control	Similar to LTC4009 Adding PowerPath Control
LT3741	High Power, Constant Current, Constant Voltage, Step-Down Controller	Thermally Enhanced 4mm × 4mm QFN and 20-Pin TSSOP
LT8705	80VIN/VOUT Sync Buck-Boost 4-SW Controller	Single Inductor, TSSOP-38 and 5mm × 7mm QFN-38

4020fd

A.6. Battery Cells

LiFePO4 Akku 26650 3,2V 3,3Ah

6,50 € *

Inhalt: 1 Stück

inkl. MwSt. zzgl. [Versandkosten](#)[Versand ca. 2-5 Werktage](#)

1

 [Merken](#) [Bewerten](#)

Artikel-Nr.: 5000766
Hersteller: [i-tecc](#)
Hersteller-Nr.: 5000766

Eigenschaften

Eigenschaften: "LiFePO4 Akku 26650 3,2V 3,3Ah"

Zellchemie:	LiFePO4
Nennspannung:	3,2V (3,3V)
Nenn-Kapazität:	3,3Ah
Entladestrom :	9,9A
Pulsentladung :	15A
Ladestrom max.:	3,3A, empfohlen $\leq 0,5C$
Arbeitsbereich:	2,5 bis 3,6V (nicht unter 2,0V)
Innenwiderstand (mΩ):	≤ 24

Temperatur (Entladen):	-20°C bis +60°C
Temperatur (Laden):	0°C bis +45°C
Lagertemperatur:	-20°C bis +60°C
Zyklusfestigkeit:	>1000 (100%DOD), >2000 (80%DOD)
Eigenentladung (monatlich):	<5%
Anschlüsse:	flat
Gehäuse:	Metall
Gewicht:	84g
Abmessung (lxbxh):	26x65mm

Ähnliche Artikel

LiFePO4 Akku
26650 3,3Ah mit

Inhalt 1 Stück

7,45 € *

Zuletzt angesehen

LiFePO4 Zelle 18650
1,5Ah

* Alle Preise inkl. gesetzl. Mehrwertsteuer zzgl. Versandkosten und ggf. Nachnahmegebühren, wenn nicht anders beschrieben

A.7. FET for the antenna release mechanism

Dual N-Channel 40 V (D-S) MOSFET

FEATURES

- TrenchFET® Gen III power MOSFET
- PWM optimized
- 100 % R_g and UIS tested
- Material categorization: for definitions of compliance please see www.vishay.com/doc?99912

RoHS
COMPLIANT
HALOGEN
FREE

APPLICATIONS

- Backlight inverter for LCD displays
- DC/DC converter

PRODUCT SUMMARY	
V _{DS} (V)	40
R _{DS(on)} max. (Ω) at V _{GS} = 10 V	0.0190
R _{DS(on)} max. (Ω) at V _{GS} = 4.5 V	0.0220
Q _g typ. (nC)	4.9
I _D (A)	20
Configuration	Dual

ORDERING INFORMATION	
Package	PowerPAK SO-8
Lead (Pb)-free and halogen-free	Si7288DP-T1-GE3

ABSOLUTE MAXIMUM RATINGS (T _A = 25 °C, unless otherwise noted)			
PARAMETER	SYMBOL	LIMIT	UNIT
Drain-source voltage	V _{DS}	40	V
Gate-source voltage	V _{GS}	± 20	
Continuous drain current (T _J = 150 °C)	I _D	T _C = 25 °C	20
		T _C = 70 °C	17
		T _A = 25 °C	10 a, b
		T _A = 70 °C	8.2 a, b
Pulsed drain current	I _{DM}	50	A
Source-drain current diode current	I _S	T _C = 25 °C	
		T _A = 25 °C	3 a, b
Single pulse avalanche current	I _{AS}	10	mJ
Avalanche energy	E _{AS}	5	
Maximum power dissipation	P _D	T _C = 25 °C	15.6
		T _C = 70 °C	10
		T _A = 25 °C	3.6 a, b
		T _A = 70 °C	2.3 a, b
Operating junction and storage temperature range	T _J , T _{stg}	-55 to +150	°C
Soldering recommendations (peak temperature) c, d		260	

THERMAL RESISTANCE RATINGS					
PARAMETER		SYMBOL	TYP.	MAX.	UNIT
Maximum junction-to-ambient a, e	t ≤ 10 s	R _{thJA}	29	35	°C/W
Maximum junction-to-case (drain)	Steady state	R _{thJC}	6.5	8	

Notes

- Surface mounted on 1" x 1" FR4 board
- t = 10 s
- See solder profile (www.vishay.com/doc?73257). The PowerPAK SO-8 is a leadless package. The end of the lead terminal is exposed copper (not plated) as a result of the singulation process in manufacturing. A solder fillet at the exposed copper tip cannot be guaranteed and is not required to ensure adequate bottom side solder interconnection
- Rework conditions: manual soldering with a soldering iron is not recommended for leadless components
- Maximum under steady state conditions is 80 °C/W

SPECIFICATIONS (T _J = 25 °C, unless otherwise noted)						
PARAMETER	SYMBOL	TEST CONDITIONS	MIN.	TYP.	MAX.	UNIT
Static						
Drain-source breakdown voltage	V _{DS}	V _{GS} = 0 V, I _D = 250 μA	40	-	-	V
V _{DS} temperature coefficient	ΔV _{DS} /T _J	I _D = 250 μA	-	47	-	mV/°C
V _{GS(th)} temperature coefficient	ΔV _{GS(th)} /T _J	I _D = 250 μA	-	-5.2	-	
Gate threshold voltage	V _{GS(th)}	V _{DS} = V _{GS} , I _D = 250 μA	1.2	-	2.8	V
Gate-body leakage	I _{GSS}	V _{DS} = 0 V, V _{GS} = ± 20 V	-	-	100	nA
Zero gate voltage drain current	I _{DSS}	V _{DS} = 40 V, V _{GS} = 0 V	-	-	1	μA
		V _{DS} = 40 V, V _{GS} = 0 V, T _J = 85 °C	-	-	10	
On-state drain current ^b	I _{D(on)}	V _{DS} ≥ 5 V, V _{GS} = 10 V	20	-	-	A
Drain-source on-state resistance ^b	R _{DS(on)}	V _{GS} = 10 V, I _D = 10 A	-	0.0156	0.0190	Ω
		V _{GS} = 4.5 V, I _D = 7 A	-	0.0180	0.0220	
Forward transconductance ^b	g _{fs}	V _{DS} = 10 V, I _D = 10 A	-	39	-	S
Dynamic^a						
Input capacitance	C _{iss}	V _{DS} = 20 V, V _{GS} = 0 V, f = 1 MHz	-	565	-	pF
Output capacitance	C _{oss}		-	100	-	
Reverse transfer capacitance	C _{rss}		-	42	-	
Total gate charge	Q _g	V _{DS} = 20 V, V _{GS} = 10 V, I _D = 10 A	-	10	15	nC
		V _{DS} = 20 V, V _{GS} = 4.5 V, I _D = 10 A	-	4.9	7.4	
Gate-source charge	Q _{gs}		-	1.4	-	
Gate-drain charge	Q _{gd}		-	1.5	-	
Gate resistance	R _g	f = 1 MHz	0.6	2.7	5.4	Ω
Turn-on delay time	t _{d(on)}	V _{DD} = 20 V, R _L = 2 Ω I _D ≅ 10 A, V _{GEN} = 4.5 V, R _g = 1 Ω	-	12	24	ns
Rise time	t _r		-	14	28	
Turn-off delay time	t _{d(off)}		-	16	32	
Fall time	t _f		-	10	20	
Turn-on delay time	t _{d(on)}	V _{DD} = 20 V, R _L = 2 Ω I _D ≅ 10 A, V _{GEN} = 10 V, R _g = 1 Ω	-	7	14	
Rise time	t _r		-	8	16	
Turn-off delay time	t _{d(off)}		-	14	28	
Fall time	t _f		-	8	16	
Drain-Source Body Diode Characteristics						
Continuous source-drain diode current	I _S	T _C = 25 °C	-	-	13	A
Pulse diode forward current ^a	I _{SM}		-	-	50	
Body diode Voltage	V _{SD}	I _S = 3 A	-	0.77	1.2	V
Body diode reverse recovery time	t _{rr}	I _F = 5 A, di/dt = 100 A/μs, T _J = 25 °C	-	15	30	ns
Body diode reverse recovery charge	Q _{rr}		-	7.5	15	nC
Reverse recovery fall time	t _a		-	8	-	ns
Reverse recovery rise time	t _b		-	7	-	

Notes

- a. Guaranteed by design, not subject to production testing
- b. Pulse test; pulse width ≤ 300 μs, duty cycle ≤ 2 %

Stresses beyond those listed under "Absolute Maximum Ratings" may cause permanent damage to the device. These are stress ratings only, and functional operation of the device at these or any other conditions beyond those indicated in the operational sections of the specifications is not implied. Exposure to absolute maximum rating conditions for extended periods may affect device reliability.

TYPICAL CHARACTERISTICS (25 °C, unless otherwise noted)

Output Characteristics

Transfer Characteristics

On-Resistance vs. Drain Current

Capacitance

Gate Charge

On-Resistance vs. Junction Temperature

TYPICAL CHARACTERISTICS (25 °C, unless otherwise noted)

Source-Drain Diode Forward Voltage

On-Resistance vs. Gate-to-Source Voltage

Threshold Voltage

Single Pulse Power

Safe Operating Area, Junction-to-Ambient

TYPICAL CHARACTERISTICS (25 °C, unless otherwise noted)

Current Derating^a

Power Derating, Junction-to-Case

Power Derating, Junction-to-Ambient

Note

- a. The power dissipation P_D is based on T_J max. = 150 °C, using junction-to-case thermal resistance, and is more useful in settling the upper dissipation limit for cases where additional heatsinking is used. It is used to determine the current rating, when this rating falls below the package limit

TYPICAL CHARACTERISTICS (25 °C, unless otherwise noted)

Normalized Thermal Transient Impedance, Junction-to-Ambient

Normalized Thermal Transient Impedance, Junction-to-Case

Vishay Siliconix maintains worldwide manufacturing capability. Products may be manufactured at one of several qualified locations. Reliability data for Silicon Technology and Package Reliability represent a composite of all qualified locations. For related documents such as package / tape drawings, part marking, and reliability data, see www.vishay.com/ppg?65366.

PowerPAK® SO-8, (Single/Dual)

- Notes**
1. Inch will govern.
 2. Dimensions exclusive of mold gate burrs.
 3. Dimensions exclusive of mold flash and cutting burrs.

DIM.	MILLIMETERS			INCHES		
	MIN.	NOM.	MAX.	MIN.	NOM.	MAX.
A	0.97	1.04	1.12	0.038	0.041	0.044
A1		-	0.05	0	-	0.002
b	0.33	0.41	0.51	0.013	0.016	0.020
c	0.23	0.28	0.33	0.009	0.011	0.013
D	5.05	5.15	5.26	0.199	0.203	0.207
D1	4.80	4.90	5.00	0.189	0.193	0.197
D2	3.56	3.76	3.91	0.140	0.148	0.154
D3	1.32	1.50	1.68	0.052	0.059	0.066
D4	0.57 typ.			0.0225 typ.		
D5	3.98 typ.			0.157 typ.		
E	6.05	6.15	6.25	0.238	0.242	0.246
E1	5.79	5.89	5.99	0.228	0.232	0.236
E2	3.48	3.66	3.84	0.137	0.144	0.151
E3	3.68	3.78	3.91	0.145	0.149	0.154
E4	0.75 typ.			0.030 typ.		
e	1.27 BSC			0.050 BSC		
K	1.27 typ.			0.050 typ.		
K1	0.56	-	-	0.022	-	-
H	0.51	0.61	0.71	0.020	0.024	0.028
L	0.51	0.61	0.71	0.020	0.024	0.028
L1	0.06	0.13	0.20	0.002	0.005	0.008
θ	0°	-	12°	0°	-	12°
W	0.15	0.25	0.36	0.006	0.010	0.014
M	0.125 typ.			0.005 typ.		

ECN: S17-0173-Rev. L, 13-Feb-17
 DWG: 5881

PowerPAK[®] SO-8 Mounting and Thermal Considerations

by Wharton McDaniel

MOSFETs for switching applications are now available with die on resistances around 1 mΩ and with the capability to handle 85 A. While these die capabilities represent a major advance over what was available just a few years ago, it is important for power MOSFET packaging technology to keep pace. It should be obvious that degradation of a high performance die by the package is undesirable. PowerPAK is a new package technology that addresses these issues. In this application note, PowerPAK's construction is described. Following this mounting information is presented including land patterns and soldering profiles for maximum reliability. Finally, thermal and electrical performance is discussed.

THE PowerPAK PACKAGE

The PowerPAK package was developed around the SO-8 package (figure 1). The PowerPAK SO-8 utilizes the same footprint and the same pin-outs as the standard SO-8. This allows PowerPAK to be substituted directly for a standard SO-8 package. Being a leadless package, PowerPAK SO-8 utilizes the entire SO-8 footprint, freeing space normally occupied by the leads, and thus allowing it to hold a larger die than a standard SO-8. In fact, this larger die is slightly larger than a full sized DPAK die. The bottom of the die attach pad is exposed for the purpose of providing a direct, low resistance thermal path to the substrate the device is mounted on. Finally, the package height is lower than the standard SO-8, making it an excellent choice for applications with space constraints.

Fig. 1 PowerPAK 1212 Devices

PowerPAK SO-8 SINGLE MOUNTING

The PowerPAK single is simple to use. The pin arrangement (drain, source, gate pins) and the pin dimensions are the same as standard SO-8 devices (see figure 2). Therefore, the PowerPAK connection pads match directly to those of the SO-8. The only difference is the extended drain connection area. To take immediate advantage of the PowerPAK SO-8 single devices, they can be mounted to existing SO-8 land patterns.

Fig. 2

The minimum land pattern recommended to take full advantage of the PowerPAK thermal performance see Application Note 826, *Recommended Minimum Pad Patterns With Outline Drawing Access for Vishay Siliconix MOSFETs*. Click on the PowerPAK SO-8 single in the index of this document.

In this figure, the drain land pattern is given to make full contact to the drain pad on the PowerPAK package.

This land pattern can be extended to the left, right, and top of the drawn pattern. This extension will serve to increase the heat dissipation by decreasing the thermal resistance from the foot of the PowerPAK to the PC board and therefore to the ambient. Note that increasing the drain land area beyond a certain point will yield little decrease in foot-to-board and foot-to-ambient thermal resistance. Under specific conditions of board configuration, copper weight and layer stack, experiments have found that more than about 0.25 in² to 0.5 in² of additional copper (in addition to the drain land) will yield little improvement in thermal performance.

APPLICATION NOTE

PowerPAK® SO-8 Mounting and Thermal Considerations

PowerPAK SO-8 DUAL

The pin arrangement (drain, source, gate pins) and the pin dimensions of the PowerPAK SO-8 dual are the same as standard SO-8 dual devices. Therefore, the PowerPAK device connection pads match directly to those of the SO-8. As in the single-channel package, the only exception is the extended drain connection area. Manufacturers can likewise take immediate advantage of the PowerPAK SO-8 dual devices by mounting them to existing SO-8 dual land patterns.

To take the advantage of the dual PowerPAK SO-8's thermal performance, the minimum recommended land pattern can be found in Application Note 826, *Recommended Minimum Pad Patterns With Outline Drawing Access for Vishay Siliconix MOSFETs*. Click on the PowerPAK 1212-8 dual in the index of this document.

The gap between the two drain pads is 24 mils. This matches the spacing of the two drain pads on the PowerPAK SO-8 dual package.

REFLOW SOLDERING

Vishay Siliconix surface-mount packages meet solder reflow reliability requirements. Devices are subjected to solder reflow as a test preconditioning and are then reliability-tested using temperature cycle, bias humidity, HAST, or pressure pot. The solder reflow temperature profile used, and the temperatures and time duration, are shown in figures 3 and 4.

For the lead (Pb)-free solder profile, see www.vishay.com/doc?73257.

Fig. 3 Solder Reflow Temperature Profile

Ramp-Up Rate	+ 3 °C /s max.
Temperature at 150 - 200 °C	120 s max.
Temperature Above 217 °C	60 - 150 s
Maximum Temperature	255 + 5/- 0 °C
Time at Maximum Temperature	30 s
Ramp-Down Rate	+ 6 °C/s max.

Fig. 4 Solder Reflow Temperatures and Time Durations

APPLICATION NOTE

PowerPAK® SO-8 Mounting and Thermal Considerations

THERMAL PERFORMANCE

Introduction

A basic measure of a device's thermal performance is the junction-to-case thermal resistance, R_{thJC} , or the junction-to-foot thermal resistance, R_{thJF} . This parameter is measured for the device mounted to an infinite heat sink and is therefore a characterization of the device only, in other words, independent of the properties of the object to which the device is mounted. Table 1 shows a comparison of the DPAK, PowerPAK SO-8, and standard SO-8. The PowerPAK has thermal performance equivalent to the DPAK, while having an order of magnitude better thermal performance over the SO-8.

TABLE 1 - DPAK AND POWERPAK SO-8 EQUIVALENT STEADY STATE PERFORMANCE			
	DPAK	PowerPAK SO-8	Standard SO-8
Thermal Resistance R_{thJC}	1.2 °C/W	1 °C/W	16 °C/W

Thermal Performance on Standard SO-8 Pad Pattern

Because of the common footprint, a PowerPAK SO-8 can be mounted on an existing standard SO-8 pad pattern. The question then arises as to the thermal performance of the PowerPAK device under these conditions. A characterization was made comparing a standard SO-8 and a PowerPAK device on a board with a trough cut out underneath the PowerPAK drain pad. This configuration restricted the heat flow to the SO-8 land pads. The results are shown in figure 5.

Fig. 5 PowerPAK SO-8 and Standard SO-0 Land Pad Thermal Path

Because of the presence of the trough, this result suggests a minimum performance improvement of 10 °C/W by using a PowerPAK SO-8 in a standard SO-8 PC board mount.

The only concern when mounting a PowerPAK on a standard SO-8 pad pattern is that there should be no traces running between the body of the MOSFET. Where the standard SO-8 body is spaced away from the pc board, allowing traces to run underneath, the PowerPAK sits directly on the pc board.

Thermal Performance - Spreading Copper

Designers may add additional copper, spreading copper, to the drain pad to aid in conducting heat from a device. It is helpful to have some information about the thermal performance for a given area of spreading copper.

Figure 6 shows the thermal resistance of a PowerPAK SO-8 device mounted on a 2-in. 2-in., four-layer FR-4 PC board. The two internal layers and the backside layer are solid copper. The internal layers were chosen as solid copper to model the large power and ground planes common in many applications. The top layer was cut back to a smaller area and at each step junction-to-ambient thermal resistance measurements were taken. The results indicate that an area above 0.3 to 0.4 square inches of spreading copper gives no additional thermal performance improvement. A subsequent experiment was run where the copper on the back-side was reduced, first to 50 % in stripes to mimic circuit traces, and then totally removed. No significant effect was observed.

Fig. 6 Spreading Copper Junction-to-Ambient Performance

APPLICATION NOTE

PowerPAK® SO-8 Mounting and Thermal Considerations

SYSTEM AND ELECTRICAL IMPACT OF PowerPAK SO-8

In any design, one must take into account the change in MOSFET $R_{DS(on)}$ with temperature (figure 7).

Fig. 7 MOSFET $R_{DS(on)}$ vs. Temperature

A MOSFET generates internal heat due to the current passing through the channel. This self-heating raises the junction temperature of the device above that of the PC board to which it is mounted, causing increased power dissipation in the device. A major source of this problem lies in the large values of the junction-to-foot thermal resistance of the SO-8 package.

PowerPAK SO-8 minimizes the junction-to-board thermal resistance to where the MOSFET die temperature is very close to the temperature of the PC board. Consider two devices mounted on a PC board heated to 105 °C by other components on the board (figure 8).

Suppose each device is dissipating 2.7 W. Using the junction-to-foot thermal resistance characteristics of the PowerPAK SO-8 and the standard SO-8, the die temperature is determined to be 107 °C for the PowerPAK (and for DPAK) and 148 °C for the standard SO-8. This is a 2 °C rise above the board temperature for the PowerPAK and a 43 °C rise for the standard SO-8. Referring to figure 7, a 2 °C difference has minimal effect on $R_{DS(on)}$ whereas a 43 °C difference has a significant effect on $R_{DS(on)}$.

Minimizing the thermal rise above the board temperature by using PowerPAK has not only eased the thermal design but it has allowed the device to run cooler, keep $r_{DS(on)}$ low, and permits the device to handle more current than the same MOSFET die in the standard SO-8 package.

CONCLUSIONS

PowerPAK SO-8 has been shown to have the same thermal performance as the DPAK package while having the same footprint as the standard SO-8 package. The PowerPAK SO-8 can hold larger die approximately equal in size to the maximum that the DPAK can accommodate implying no sacrifice in performance because of package limitations.

Recommended PowerPAK SO-8 land patterns are provided to aid in PC board layout for designs using this new package.

Thermal considerations have indicated that significant advantages can be gained by using PowerPAK SO-8 devices in designs where the PC board was laid out for the standard SO-8. Applications experimental data gave thermal performance data showing minimum and typical thermal performance in a SO-8 environment, plus information on the optimum thermal performance obtainable including spreading copper. This further emphasized the DPAK equivalency.

PowerPAK SO-8 therefore has the desired small size characteristics of the SO-8 combined with the attractive thermal characteristics of the DPAK package.

APPLICATION NOTE

Fig. 8 Temperature of Devices on a PC Board

RECOMMENDED MINIMUM PADS FOR PowerPAK[®] SO-8 Dual

Recommended Minimum Pads
Dimensions in Inches/(mm)

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